

**Methods for Weak Lensing Systematics in the Era of the Vera C. Rubin
Observatory**

by

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PREFACE

This dissertation is based on work I performed at the University of Michigan between 2019 and 2024. Additionally, during the last year of my PhD, I had the opportunity to work on a project I designed and proposed at Argonne National Laboratory (ANL). In my PhD I was an active member of the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (LSST-DESC), and all projects presented here have the upcoming Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) as their primary motivation.

Chapter 2 is based on the publication [I. Mendoza et al. \(2025\)](#), and was coauthored with several LSST-DESC members including Andrii Torchylo, Thomas Sainrat, Axel Guinot, Alexandre Boucaud, Maxime Paillasa, among others. This chapter completed LSST-DESC internal review and was published in The Open Journal of Astrophysics (OJA). This project grew out of the need within LSST-DESC to centralize simulations and algorithms related to visually overlapping sources, i.e., *blended* sources. Blending is expected to be a particularly important systematic for optical Stage-IV surveys such as LSST.

Chapter 3 is based on a paper coauthored with LSST-DESC members, and statisticians at UofM and the University of California Berkeley. The coauthors include: Axel Guinot, Derek Hansen, Runjing Liu, Zhe Zhao, Ziteng Pang, and Jeffrey Regier. The paper corresponding to this chapter will be resubmitted for a second round of internal review in LSST-DESC. This project explores how probabilistic machine learning techniques can be used to improve measurements of blended galaxies.

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ABSTRACT

One of the biggest mysteries in Cosmology today relates to the nature of dark energy. Dark energy drives the observed cosmic expansion of the universe by counteracting the effects of gravity. The existence of dark energy could imply an exotic new type of substance, or the breakdown of General Relativity at cosmological scales. Any of these options would have significant implications for fundamental physics. Modern dark energy surveys, such as the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), are designed to improve our understanding of dark energy by precisely measuring its properties.

A powerful probe of dark energy is *weak lensing*, which refers to the deflection of light rays from distant astronomical sources due to matter along their path to us. Weak lensing induces a coherent alignment of observed galaxy shapes which directly depends on the integrated matter density along the line of sight, so-called *cosmic shear*. Measurements of cosmic shear can be used to understand the distribution and evolution of matter in our Universe, which in turn allow us to constrain dark energy properties. LSST will dramatically increase the statistical power of weak lensing surveys by observing tens of billions of galaxies during its 10 year mission. However, their power will be limited by a wide range of theoretical and observational systematics.

This thesis develops software tools and algorithms to explore and mitigate weak lensing related systematics the LSST survey will face. One such systematic is blending, which refers to the visual overlap of light sources in astronomical images. Given the increased depth and number density of sources in LSST, we expect a large fraction of observable sources will be blended. Blending can create several types of biases in weak lensing measurements, and some of these remain unaccounted for by contemporary algorithms.

First, we present a software package, the *BlendingToolKit*, with the goal of providing a framework to study blending-related measurement biases in a controlled way. It provides customizable simulations of galaxy blends; a framework to standardize the input and output of deblenders; and a library of relevant metrics related to detection, morphology reconstruction, and flux recovery of these sources. This package is actively being used in the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration to aid the development of new deblending methods.

The next portion of the thesis is devoted to a probabilistic algorithm to mitigate blending-

related biases: *BLISS*. This novel method uses simulation based inference (SBI) to produce a probabilistic catalog of blended galaxies which captures corresponding measurement uncertainty. We test our approach in LSST-like image simulations and demonstrate a significant improvement in recovering the flux of highly blended sources.

Finally, we present a modern implementation of the hierarchical Bayesian shear inference framework in [M. D. Schneider et al. \(2015\)](#). Our implementation leverages GPUs and gradient-based samplers to improve upon its runtime by an order of magnitude. We rigorously test our algorithm on a set of 300k isolated parametric galaxies with realistic pixel and shape noise levels. We find that resulting shear measurements present no significant level of pixel noise bias, and that these meet the LSST requirement.

Together, these three studies represent a significant contribution towards leveraging modern statistical and hardware tools to reduce the impact of image-level systematics in weak lensing measurements for dark energy surveys.

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Standard Model of Cosmology

Our Universe was born approximately 13.7 billion years ago in what is known as the Big Bang. This was followed by a rapid expansion of space, which is known as inflation. Currently, the standard model of cosmology Λ CDM (e.g., [D. H. Weinberg et al., 2013](#)) represents our best understanding of how the universe has evolved after these events. It assumes that the universe is *isotropic* and *homogeneous* at very large scales (> 100 Mpc). Isotropic means that there is no preferred direction, and homogeneous means that there is no preferred location. This model assigns our Universe three components: dark energy, (cold) dark matter, and ordinary or baryonic matter. Dark energy, denoted by the Λ in the acronym, drives the accelerated expansion of the universe acting against the effects of gravity. This effect was first directly measured by two independent supernova experiments ([A. G. Riess et al., 1999](#); [S. Perlmutter et al., 1999](#)). We currently know very little about the nature of this substance. The next component, cold dark matter (CDM), is postulated to consist of a substance whose interaction with electromagnetic radiation and ordinary matter is very weak ('dark'), and that moves very slowly relative to the speed of light ('cold'). Currently, dark matter can only be observed indirectly via its gravitational interaction with visible matter sources in the universe. The clearest evidence for this component is the over 100σ discrepancy between baryon and matter density measured by several experiments such as the *Planck* mission (e.g., [Planck Collaboration et al., 2020](#)). Several independent cosmological surveys have estimated the relative abundances of these components to be approximately: 70% for dark energy, 25% for dark matter, and 5% for baryons ([S. Alam et al., 2017](#); [Planck Collaboration et al., 2020](#); [T. M. C. Abbott et al., 2022](#); [M. A. Karim et al., 2025](#)).

It is difficult to overstate how successful Λ CDM is as a theory. It accurately explains the entire history of the universe from a fraction of a second after the big bang ([M. S. Turner, 2022](#)). For instance, it predicts that gravitationally collapsed structures of dark matter

particles, so-called dark matter *halos*, form the building blocks for the *large scale structure* (LSS) of the universe (C. S. Frenk & S. D. White, 2012). These building blocks assemble *hierarchically*: small dark matter halos form first and these merge together to form larger halos whose gravitational wells are the birthplaces of galaxies and stars (R. H. Wechsler & J. L. Tinker, 2018). This prediction for the structure of the universe is in remarkable agreement with matter density maps from observations in cosmological surveys. Another example, is the cosmic microwave background (CMB), which is the result of baryons falling into the potential wells formed by halos as the Universe entered the matter-dominated era ($t \sim 64,000$ years). These baryons eventually formed neutral atoms as a result of *recombination* ($t \sim 378,000$ years) and the remaining photons were able to stream freely to become the CMB (M. S. Turner & J. A. Tyson, 1999). Λ CDM successfully predicted the near exact black-body spectrum of the CMB and its temperature anisotropies (e.g. G. F. Smoot et al., 1992; D. J. Fixsen, 2009).

1.2 Dark energy and Cosmic Expansion

1.2.1 Mathematical characterization

Some of the most important open questions in cosmology relate to the nature and properties of dark energy, which drives the accelerated expansion of the universe. Cosmic expansion is typically quantified using the scale factor a , which represents the change in physical distance between two objects due to this effect. Additionally, the expansion implies that other galaxies and light sources recede from us with some velocity (*Hubble flow*), so that their light emitted appears redder. In particular, if a distance galaxy emits light with wavelength λ_{emit} , we would receive it at a wavelength $\lambda_{\text{obs}} = \lambda_{\text{emit}}/a$. The scale factor is thus defined as:

$$\frac{1}{a} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{obs}}}{\lambda_{\text{emit}}} = 1 + z, \quad (1.1)$$

where z is then the *redshift* of the distance light source. The expansion of an isotropic and homogeneous universe follows the Friedman equations (e.g., D. Huterer, 2023; S. Dodelson & F. Schmidt, 2024):

$$H^2(a)/H_0^2 = \Omega_m a^{-3} + \Omega_r a^{-4} + \Omega_\psi \frac{u_\psi(a)}{u_\psi(a=1)}, \quad (1.2)$$

where $H(z)$ is the *Hubble parameter*, defined as:

$$H(z) = \dot{a}/a, \quad (1.3)$$

and $H_0 = H(a = 1)$ is the present-day value, the so-called *Hubble constant*. The $\Omega_m, \Omega_r,$ and Ω_ψ are the present-day energy densities of matter, radiation, and dark energy respectively. These are expressed in units of the *critical density* of the Universe today to ensure that it is flat (no curvature):

$$\rho_{\text{crit}} = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi G}, \quad (1.4)$$

so that:

$$\Omega_x = \frac{u_x(a = 1)}{\rho_{\text{crit}}c^2}, \quad (1.5)$$

for each component $x \in \{m, r, \psi\}$. In the standard Λ CDM model, dark energy density Ω_Λ does not change with time per its definition as a cosmological constant.

Dark energy is not necessarily characterized by a cosmological constant Λ with fixed energy density. It could also correspond to a scalar field ψ with an energy density that varies slowly. The equation of state of a scalar field with pressure p and energy density u is defined by the dimensionless ratio $w \equiv p/u$. In the standard model, $w = -1$ at all times.

Alternative theories for dark energy can be tested by parameterizing the dependence of w on a . The most common model is a linear relation:

$$w(a) = w_0 + w_a(1 - a), \quad (1.6)$$

where w_0 is the value at $a = 1$ (the present), and w_a determines how w varies with time. The dark energy density can be related to $w(a)$ via (e.g., [D. H. Weinberg et al., 2013](#)):

$$\frac{u_\phi(z)}{u_\phi(a = 1)} = \exp \left[3 \int_1^a (1 + w(a')) d \ln a' \right]. \quad (1.7)$$

An important special case is that of w being constant:

$$\frac{u_\phi(a)}{u_\phi(a = 1)} = a^{-3(1+w)}, \quad (1.8)$$

where for $w = -1$ (Λ CDM) implies no density evolution, as expected.

Combining Equations 1.2 and 1.7 implies that dark energy properties can be constrained via precise measurements of $H(a)$. In turn, the Hubble parameter can be determined from redshift and distance measurements of distance light sources, such as Type Ia supernova

(A. G. Riess et al., 1999; S. Perlmutter et al., 1999; A. Goobar & B. Leibundgut, 2011). It is also necessary to accurately measure the matter and radiation densities.

1.2.2 Outlook

While the existence of dark energy (as it relates to cosmic accelerated expansion) has been conclusively established, cosmologists currently confront an exotic new substance or the breakdown of General Relativity (GR) (E. Abdalla et al., 2022). Measurements of the dark energy equation of state parameters (w_0, w_a) at sub-percent precision is the current goal of “Stage-IV” dark energy experiments which include: the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (*DESI*, DESI Collaboration et al. (2016)), *Euclid* (G. D. Racca et al., 2016), and the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (*LSST*, Ž. Ivezić et al. (2019a)). Combining measurements from multiple state-of-art telescopes targeting different cosmological probes (Section 1.3) will likely be necessary to achieve sub-percent precision (A. Albrecht et al., 2006). Moreover, as these surveys become more sophisticated and the amount of data collected increases, we must account for increasingly complex systematic effects that bias and degrade measurements (e.g., R. Laureijs et al., 2011a; The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al., 2018) (Section 1.4).

We live in an exciting time for cosmology and dark energy. Recently, results from DESI DR2 (M. A. Karim et al., 2025) have shown significant evidence for beyond Λ CDM physics using their BAO measurements in combination with supernova (D. Scolnic et al., 2022; D. Brout et al., 2022; D. Rubin et al., 2023; DES Collaboration et al., 2024) and CMB (Planck Collaboration et al., 2020) data. Specifically, these data combination prefers a time-varying dark energy model over Λ CDM at 3.1σ . Cosmological measurements from ongoing and future experiments like LSST, Euclid, and the *Roman* Space Telescope (D. Spergel et al., 2015) will further shed light on the significance of this result, and could eventually lead to the discovery of new physics.

1.3 Cosmological Probes

There are several cosmological probes that inform the measurement of dark energy properties. For an optical survey such as LSST these probes include (T. L. D. E. S. Collaboration, 2020):

- *Weak Lensing (WL)*: This is related to the deflection of light from sources far away from us due to the gravitational potential of matter along their path to us (see Figure 1.1). WL can be used to infer the matter density distribution of the Universe and when combined with redshift information (tomography), its evolution (D. Huterer, 2002; M.

Kilbinger, 2015; J. Prat & D. Bacon, 2025). WL is one of the most constraining probes for dark energy. See Section 1.5 for more information on this probe.

- *Strong Lensing (SL)*: This phenomenon refers to a more extreme version of what occurs in WL. In the case that the lensing foreground objects are very massive, light rays from background sources can become distorted in a dramatic fashion producing arcs (see Figure 1.3) or even produce multiple images of the same source. Time delay measurements of these multi-imaged sources allows for determination of the Hubble constant H_0 (T. Treu et al., 2022).
- *Type Ia Supernova*: Type Ia Supernova are supernova that occur in a binary star systems where one of the stars is a white dwarf. The corresponding explosion peaks at approximately the same intrinsic brightness making these events *standard candles*, that can be used to measure the distance to the host galaxy. By combining this measurement with galaxy redshift information, an estimate cosmic expansion can be obtained (A. Goobar & B. Leibundgut, 2011).
- *Large Scale Structure (LSS)*: Measuring the clustering of galaxies allows for measurement of the universe expansion history via the imprint from Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO). This imprint represents the phases of acoustic waves at recombination as set by the sound horizon and their wavelengths then in that epoch. Clustering measurement also constrain the power matter spectrum.
- *Galaxy Clusters*: These are the most massive objects in the universe (an example of a galaxy cluster is also shown in Figure 1.3). Cosmology parameters such as the matter density Ω_m and the amplitude of of matter density fluctuations σ_8 can be constrained by using cluster abundances as a function of halo mass (i.e., the halo mass function,, HMF). This is because the high-mass end of the HMF is highly cosmology dependent (e.g., H. Miyatake, 2025).

Figure 1.2 shows the forecasted constraints on dark energy using the LSST survey data with with these different probes. This thesis will focus primarily on the weak lensing probe (Section 1.5).

1.4 Precision cosmology

In recent decades, cosmology has become an “industrial” science: international teams consisting of hundreds of scientists devote their efforts to understand the fundamental nature

Credit: Jessie Muir 2020

Figure 1.1: This drawing illustrates the impact of weak lensing on the observed shapes of light sources. The gravitational potential of (baryonic and dark) matter in the Universe distorts the light coming from distant sources, which distorts the shapes we observed in our telescopes. *Image credit:* Jessie Muir (<https://www.jessiemuir.com>).

of our universe. This trend is driven by the vast amounts of data produced by past and ongoing surveys that transformed the field from “data-starved” to “data-rich”. Ultimately, this has allowed for percent and sub-percent measurement of cosmological parameters, which has led cosmologists to declare the *precision era of cosmology* (M. S. Turner, 2022). As the amount of available data has increased, the statistical uncertainty in cosmological parameters has decreased and mitigating the impact of systematics has gained increased relevance.

Systematic errors or *systematic biases* refer to quantifiable offsets in final or intermediate cosmological measurements due to astrophysical or observational phenomena. The actual value of these corrections tends to be unimportant. However, imperfect knowledge of the underlying phenomena leads to an uncertainty in the correction applied, which is referred to as *systematic uncertainty*. This uncertainty is critical to quantify and minimize for modern cosmological experiments (The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al., 2018).

The limit in which systematic uncertainty is larger than statistical uncertainty is known as the *systematics-limited* regime. This is the regime of in which most modern cosmological experiments operate. Thus, one of the most important aspects of cosmology experiments today is the understanding and mitigation of systematics uncertainties to prevent their

Figure 1.2: Forecast of dark energy constraints from LSST Y10 measurements. The axes Δw_0 and Δw_a are the difference between w_0 and w_a from their fiducial values of -1 and 0 . The contours shown in all cases represent 68% confidence intervals. The different colors represent constraints from LSST individual probes: Galaxy Clusters (light blue), strong lensing (yellow), supernova (green), and weak lensing and large scale structure (blue). The red contours are the expected constraint from Stage-III surveys, and the black contours combine all LSST probes under a Stage-III prior. **Image credit:** [The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al. \(2018\)](#).

domination of the error budget. We discuss systematics related to weak lensing measurements in Section 1.8.

1.5 Weak Lensing

1.5.1 Inferring cosmology with lensing

Gravitational lensing is the deflection of light rays from distant light sources due to the gravitational potential of all (baryonic and dark) matter in its path to our telescopes (S. Dodelson, 2017). This can cause galaxies and other light sources to appear distorted in telescope images (Figure 1.1). Most of the observed gravitational lensing is ‘weak’, which only causes subtle differences in the brightness, size, and shapes of objects. This work focuses

Figure 1.3: This figure shows an image of the Abell 2813 galaxy cluster taken with the Hubble Space Telescope, which dramatically illustrates the process of gravitational lensing. The crescent shapes close to the center of the image are examples of background galaxies that are strongly-lensed by the foreground galaxy cluster. **Image credit:** Hubble Space Telescope (NASA).

on this regime, so-called *weak lensing* (P. Schneider, 2005; M. Kilbinger, 2015). Weak lensing manifests in astronomical images through *magnification* and *shear*. Magnification refers to the increase in the flux and size of light sources, while shear refers to changes in their shapes.

Weak lensing can be used to learn about structures in our Universe: galaxies close to each other have their light pass through same structure when coming to us, which spatially correlates their shapes. This correlation drops as both the angular or redshift separation increases (M. Kilbinger, 2015; S. Dodelson, 2017; R. Mandelbaum, 2018; J. Prat & D. Bacon, 2025). By studying both the amplitude and scale-dependence of these correlations, we can learn about the matter distribution, and if we combine this information with *tomography* (i.e., galaxy redshift information), we can also learn how the cosmic structure has evolved with time. Finally, we can use this information to constrain dark energy parameters, since cosmic expansion directly counteracts the clustering of matter due to gravity (W. Hu, 2001; D. Huterer, 2002).

The 2-point correlation function of galaxy shapes is referred to as *cosmic shear*. Inferring cosmology from galaxy shapes requires three main components (R. Mandelbaum, 2018): (1) analyses of images to extract the cosmic shear signal as a deviation from random galaxy

Figure 1.4: This figure schematically shows the effects (black) of shear ($\gamma_{1,2}$) and magnification (κ) on a circular source (light blue). **Image credit:** J. Prat & D. Bacon (2025).

orientations (2) redshift data for each galaxy so shape distortions can be connected to cosmology, and (3) external data from simulations or other other surveys to calibrate shear and redshift.

1.5.2 Formalism for shear and shapes

Weak lensing can be described via a linear transformation between unlensed (x_u, y_u) and lensed (x_l, y_l) coordinates, where the origins are at the unlensed and lensed positions of the galaxy (R. Mandelbaum, 2018):

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_u \\ y_u \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \gamma_1 - \kappa & -\gamma_2 \\ -\gamma_2 & 1 + \gamma_1 - \kappa \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_l \\ y_l \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.9)$$

The transformation is characterized by the complex valued lensing shear $\gamma = \gamma_1 + i\gamma_2$ and the convergence κ . The lensing shear describes the stretching of galaxies due to lensing, while convergence describes the change in size and brightness of lensed objects (see Figure 1.4). This equation is typically rewritten as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_u \\ y_u \end{pmatrix} = (1 - \kappa) \begin{pmatrix} 1 - g_1 & -g_2 \\ -g_2 & 1 + g_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_l \\ y_l \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.10)$$

in terms of the *reduced shear* $g_i = \gamma_i/(1 - \kappa)$. This reparameterization is useful because g_i fully determines the effect of lensing on galaxy shapes.

Galaxy shapes are typically defined in terms of measurements of the *second moments* Q_{ij}

of galaxies

$$Q_{ij} = \frac{\int d^2x I(\mathbf{x})W(\mathbf{x})x_ix_j}{\int d^2x I(\mathbf{x})W(\mathbf{x})} \quad (1.11)$$

where $I(\mathbf{x})$ is the galaxy image light profile and $W(\mathbf{x})$ is a weighting function. The latter is required because astronomical images contain *pixel noise* arising from background sources and instrumental effects (N. Kaiser et al., 1995). The most common definition of complex ellipticity uses the second moments like so:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_1 + i\varepsilon_2 = \frac{Q_{11} - Q_{22} + 2iQ_{12}}{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 2(Q_{11}Q_{22} - Q_{12}^2)^{1/2}} \quad (1.12)$$

the response of this ellipticity parametrization to shear can be expressed as (P. Schneider, 2005):

$$\varepsilon' = \frac{\varepsilon + \mathbf{g}}{1 + \mathbf{g}^*\varepsilon} \quad (1.13)$$

where ε' is the sheared ellipticity, ε is the intrinsic ellipticity, and \mathbf{g} the (reduced) shear applied.

Given that this ellipticity definition has a well-defined response to shear, measured ellipticities can be used to estimate shear. Specifically, if we assume that the intrinsic orientation of the galaxies is random, the average of an ensemble of measured ellipticities approximates the reduced shear $\langle \varepsilon \rangle \approx \mathbf{g}$. The typical value of intrinsic galaxy shapes is an order of magnitude larger than shear values, so a large number of galaxies is required to measure shear precisely. The scatter in the ellipticity distribution of galaxies is typically referred to as *shape noise*. A larger value of shape noise makes precise measurements of shear more difficult.

1.6 Optical Survey Science

Optical astronomical surveys such as LSST infer the weak lensing signal by measuring galaxy shapes in astronomical images. This theoretically simple procedure is complicated by the myriad of observational effects on astronomical images that we discuss briefly in this section.

The process undergone by photons from faraway light sources in an optical survey are outlined in Figure 1.5. First, the photons of a given galaxy propagate through the universe across the gravitational potential of intervening LSS and shear is applied, making the image appear elongated. Next, the light rays are convolved by a *Point Spread Function* (PSF), which is realized by the time average of light propagation through the atmosphere and telescope optics. This has a blurring effect on the image which makes it difficult to resolve substructure

in the morphology of the galaxy. Finally, the light passes through a detector which pixellates the image and adds noise. Using the resulting astronomical images to infer the shear applied makes weak lensing a difficult undertaking.

Figure 1.5: Effects of cosmic shear, telescope optics, atmosphere, and pixelization on galaxy images. **Image credit:** R. Mandelbaum (2018).

1.7 Stage IV Survey: Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST)

The LSST survey uses observations from the NSF (National Science Foundation) Vera C. Rubin Observatory at Cerro Pachón, Chile. The camera used is the 3.2 gigapixel DOE (Department of Energy) LSST Science Camera, which is also the largest digital camera in the world. Observations are taken through the Simonyi Survey Telescope, a three-mirror system with an 8.4 m primary mirror. This allows for a 10 deg^2 field of view that records the entire sky every three nights. The telescope will survey about 20,000 square degrees of the night sky in its 10 year duration. Each position in the sky will be visited about 100 times per year. Each visit is comprised by 30 second exposures. The telescope will use six photometric bands *ugrizy* in the range between 320 nm to 1050 nm.¹ LSST will process approximately 30TBs of data every night of observation for 10 years, and analyze a total of 20 billion objects (LSST Science Collaboration et al., 2009). The LSST survey is scheduled to start later **this** year and conclude on 2035.

The LSST survey is uniquely position to maximize the scientific returns of weak lensing science (LSST Science Collaboration et al., 2009). The key observables for this science is the shear from galaxy shapes and photometric redshift estimates for each source. this implies

¹<https://rubinobservatory.org/for-scientists/rubin-101/key-numbers>

that we need to maximize the number of observable and usable galaxies for lensing. LSST will be comprised of approximately billions of galaxies, dramatically improving the statistical power of the weak lensing probe. Additionally, the very wide footprint from LSST will help reduce cosmic variance at very large scales. It is estimated that LSST will have an **effective number density** of sources for lensing of approximately 26 per square arcmin (C. Chang et al., 2013) (see Figure 1.6).² Although the authors note that this density could improve by up to 20% as new weak lensing algorithms are developed.

Figure 1.6: This figure shows the source density (in units of arcmin⁻²) and probed volume (in Gpc³) for current and upcoming weak lensing surveys. The shaded regions separate Stage III from Stage IV experiments. The color of the dot represents the average photometric redshift uncertainty for the Stage III surveys. **Figure Credit:** J. Prat & D. Bacon (2025).

1.8 Lensing Systematic Effects

The systematic bias in shear measurements is typically characterized using two numbers, m the *multiplicative bias* and c the *additive bias* (e.g., R. Mandelbaum et al., 2014):

$$\hat{g} = (1 + m)g + c \quad (1.14)$$

²The effective number density takes into account the extent to which signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), blending, and masking impacts the contribution of galaxy shapes to extract the shear signal.

where $\hat{\mathbf{g}}$ is the chosen shear estimator value and \mathbf{g} is the true shear. This expression can be thought as the Taylor expansion of $\hat{\mathbf{g}}$ in terms of \mathbf{g} (centered around 0). The matrix in the linear term is typically assumed to have zero off-diagonal components and equivalent on-diagonal components m . The second-order term is not included because shear (like ellipticity) is a spin-2 quantity (e.g. X. Li et al., 2022). Finally terms of order $\mathcal{O}(g^3)$ are usually neglected because for weak lensing the typical value of shear is $g \sim 1\%$. The additive bias \mathbf{c} is the result of measurement biases introducing a favored direction in the image plane. For example, due to insufficient correction of the effects of the PSF. In principle, additive bias can be predicted with sufficient knowledge of the survey, and identified via *null tests* (R. Mandelbaum, 2018). Multiplicative bias tends to be trickier as it depends on the distribution of galaxy properties used for the analysis. Simulations that closely match the survey data are usually required to quantify it.

There are many sources for systematic error in cosmic shear, a few include (E. Huff & R. Mandelbaum, 2017):

- noise bias: shear estimation for low-resolution and/or low signal-to-noise ratio galaxies (T. Kacprzak et al., 2012; A. Refregier et al., 2012; J. Sanchez et al., 2021; X. Li et al., 2025a)
- selection and detection biases (J. Hartlap et al., 2011; Euclid Collaboration et al., 2019; E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020; S. Liang et al., 2025a)
- model bias: galaxy modeling, realistic galaxy morphology, and ellipticity gradients (G. M. Bernstein, 2010; L. Voigt & S. Bridle, 2010; P. Melchior et al., 2010; B. Remy et al., 2022)
- blending and deblending (J. Sanchez et al., 2021; N. MacCrann et al., 2022)
- chromatic bias: wavelength-dependent effects, such as color gradients (L. M. Voigt et al., 2012; J. E. Meyers & P. R. Burchat, 2015; X. Er et al., 2018; M. Eriksen & H. Hoekstra, 2018; S. G. Carlsten et al., 2018; S. Kamath et al., 2019; F. Berlfein et al., 2025)
- star-galaxy separation (M. T. Soumagnac et al., 2015)
- instrumental defects and nonlinearities
- non-white pixel noise
- cosmic rays and other image artifacts

There already exists calibration algorithms that can account for many of these effects. For example, METADETECTION (E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020, 2023) was evaluated on LSST-like image simulations that included semi-realistic galaxies, stars, representative distributions of magnitudes and galactic spatial density, cosmic rays, bad CCD columns, and saturated bright stars with “bleed trails”. In this context, METADETECTION was found to measure shear within the LSST requirements (see Section 1.10 for more details on METADETECTION). The most pressing biases to understand and mitigate in LSST are blending and chromatic biases. Blending will be discussed in more detail in Section 1.9, but there is currently no algorithm to handle the shear bias introduced by overlapping galaxies at different redshifts. This effect has been estimated to introduce a -2% multiplicative bias in DES Y3 simulations (N. MacCramm et al., 2022), and likely worsen significantly in LSST. In terms of chromatic... In what follows we discuss some of these effects in detail. In the next section (1.10), we discuss the modern algorithms used to calibrate these effects.

Noise bias refers to the bias induced in shear measurement related to the relative brightness of observed objects and the pixel-noise present in astronomical images. Faint sources might get overwhelmed by the noise present which makes it difficult to detect and accurately measure their properties. P. Melchior & M. Viola (2012) outlines three layers of noise bias: (1) pixel noise propagates to non-linear galaxy observables such as ellipticity, (2) how a given shape measurement method’s output reacts to the small amount of information available in noisy images, and (3) the response of the shear statistic chosen to ellipticity outliers and the presence of noise. Ellipticity is a non-linear quantity that relies on second-moment measurements of the light profile (see Equation 1.12). This implies that even when the pixel noise distribution is symmetric, the resulting measured ellipticity distribution will very likely be more complicated, potentially non-symmetric and skewed. A. Refregier et al. (2012) presents analytical derivations for the best-fitting model bias in ellipticities due to noise for parametric light profiles of galaxies. They demonstrate that the bias is non-zero and significant for common ellipticity definitions even if the form of the light profile of galaxies is perfectly known. The second aspect relates to specific shape measurements methods and their limitations. P. Melchior & M. Viola (2012) identifies three categories of common problems for measurement methods, which have to do with inaccurate centroid determination, misalignment of elliptical model or weight functions, and inaccurate modeling of the real galaxy profile. Finally, the method used to aggregate ellipticity measurements into a shear statistic can be impacted by pixel-noise. Specifically, due to the choice of ellipticity weights; how it handles the presence of ellipticity outliers; and, depending on the ellipticity definition chosen, the ellipticity response to shear might be non-linear, leading to biases.

Selection bias occurs when the criteria for selecting the galaxies used for shear measurement

depend on their shapes. In this case, given that the shapes of galaxies are directly impacted by the shear and any anisotropies present in the PSF, the final lensing sample will also depend on these two quantities. If the sample membership depends on shear, this bias will manifest as a multiplicative bias, and if it depends on PSF ellipticity, as an additive bias (R. Mandelbaum, 2018). There are several potential causes for selection bias on a cosmological survey. These include: (1) if the selection for galaxies depends on shapes, the assumption that galaxy ellipticities in the sample are randomly oriented is no longer valid, which introduces a bias. (2) Closely overlapping (*blended*) objects are sometimes excluded from the sample due to the difficulty in ascertaining the properties of individual objects (see Section 1.9 for further discussion). J. Hartlap et al. (2011) argues that excluding blends can introduce bias by changing the redshift distribution of source galaxies and by correlating the foreground lens mass distribution with the background source galaxy distribution. (3) Weight assigned to galaxies which are then used to take ensemble averages of shapes could lead to selection biases (I. Fenech Conti et al., 2017).

Detection bias is an important type of selection bias (E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020). It occurs when the sources detected by a detection algorithm depend on the shear applied to these sources. Typical detection algorithms identify sources by finding bright interconnected regions in an image. Shear is an invertible transformation that preserves surface brightness (Liouville’s theorem), which should imply that the number of connected regions above a given surface brightness threshold stays constant. However, in astronomical imaging the shear transformation is followed by PSF convolution due to the atmosphere and telescope optics, as well as degradation from detector effects (Figure 1.5). In this setting, the number objects detected will depend on the shear applied, which can induce a bias on the shear measurement. This effect will be particularly acute if there is a large number of blended sources in the images used. Figure 1.7 visually illustrates shear detection bias.

In the next section, we discuss the *blending* systematic in the context of weak lensing measurements in detail. This systematic correlates with and amplifies many of the biases discussed in this section will be particularly relevant for LSST.

1.9 Blending

Blending refers to the visual overlap of two or more light sources in a given astronomical image. More specifically, when any given pixel in an astronomical image receives flux from more than one light source. Depending on the specifics of the blended configuration, determining the properties of individual sources can become challenging (P. Melchior et al., 2021). Blending can systematically bias measurements of galaxy fluxes, shapes, sizes, and centroids (A.

Figure 1.7: This figure illustrates shear-dependent detection bias. The three panels show two simulated galaxies convolved with a PSF. The white contours in each panel denote constant brightness. In the first panel, the galaxies are drawn with no shear applied. In the second panel, shear is applied *after* the PSF convolution. The number of contours stays the same (one) given that shear is an invertible mapping that preserves surface brightness. In the last panel, the shear is applied *before* the PSF (like in real observations) and the number of contours changes. An algorithm identifying independent light sources by looking at connected regions in an image above some brightness threshold will suffer shear-dependent detection bias. **Figure Credit:** E. S. Sheldon et al. (2020).

Boucaud et al., 2020). In extreme cases, where the sources are very closely overlapping or when one of the sources is much brighter than the rest, the total number of sources can also become ambiguous. This case is known as *unrecognized blending* (W. A. Dawson et al., 2016; Euclid Collaboration et al., 2019; M. A. Troxel et al., 2023). See Figure 1.8 for some examples of images of unrecognized blends observed simultaneously in a ground-based and space-based instrument.

Blending has turned into a more urgent problem for Stage-IV surveys as these become deeper and the density of light sources increases. Higher density implies a larger probability that any two sources will be overlapping, which leads to more blending. In LSST for instance, it is expected that approximately 60% of sources will be blended to some degree and between 20% and 30% of sources will be unrecognized blends (M. A. Troxel et al., 2023). This has led to studies seeking to understand the effect of blending on galaxy catalogs and downstream cosmological constraints (e.g., J. Sanchez et al., 2021; E. Nourbakhsh et al., 2022; B. Levine et al., 2024; S. Liang et al., 2025b).

Blending can systematically bias cosmic shear in several ways. First, there is the shear-dependent detection bias discussed above (E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020), which becomes increasingly likely as more objects are closely overlapping. Second, galaxy photometry could become inaccurate as it becomes difficult to disentangle the flux contribution of each individual galaxy (A. Boucaud et al., 2020). A downstream effect could be photometric-

Figure 1.8: Illustration of unrecognized galaxy blends. Each pair of images show the same galaxy blend system, but the left stamps are obtained from the ground-based telescope and the right stamps from a space-based one. The galaxy shapes from the detection are shown in red (ground-based) and green (space-based). In all of these images we see examples of two or more galaxies that are well-resolved in the space instrument but confused as one object in the ground instrument. **Image credit:** [W. A. Dawson et al. \(2016\)](#).

redshift errors and outliers. Third, unrecognized blending could lead to a selection bias (J. Hartlap et al., 2011). It can also alter the ellipticity distribution of the galaxy sample, leading to a multiplicative bias (W. A. Dawson et al., 2016). Finally, an effect that has not been studied until recently is the coupled effect of blending in both shear and photometric redshift calibration (N. MacCrann et al., 2022). This arises when the galaxies in a blended system are at different redshifts and thus experience different shears, which will be the typical case in modern surveys (e.g., W. A. Dawson et al., 2016). The corresponding bias induced in the lensing analysis cannot be corrected by self-calibration algorithms such as METADETECTION (E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020), which are discussed in Section 1.10. This is because each galaxy in the blend would have to be sheared independently, which is not possible without perfect deblending and detection in the real image. N. MacCrann et al. (2022) instead proposes a formalism based on the *effective redshift distribution for lensing* to encode the bias produced by this effect. They propose and implement a calibration scheme using a suite of specialized image simulations with input shear signals that vary with redshifts. This approach was tested in the context of DES Y3 shape measurements.

Several avenues have been explored to address blending in the context of astronomical surveys. One approach is by using so-called *deblenders* (P. Melchior et al., 2021). Deblenders are algorithms that attempt to disentangle the properties or flux contribution of the individual sources in a blend. This is usually done via an internal model of galaxy morphology and a optimization procedure. Most recent deblenders have used intensity gradients and interpolation (Y. Zhang et al., 2015), constrained optimization (P. Melchior et al., 2018) and machine learning (B. Arcelin et al., 2021; D. L. Hansen et al., 2022; B. Biswas et al., 2024; M. L. Sampson et al., 2024) techniques. Our own deblender *BLISS*, discussed in Chapter 3, uses machine learning techniques for joint detection and deblending of sources. In the best case, deblending algorithms can produce accurate reconstructions of individual sources, particularly when the centroids of sources are accurately known. This might lead to reductions in model shear biases. In the worst case, deblenders can become an additional source of systematic bias by further correlating the noise in images.

An additional way to address blending is to incorporate additional data from other surveys or filters (R. Joseph et al., 2016). For example, if the blended objects have significant different colors, using images of the same blend from multiple bands simultaneously might offer complementary information and improve detection accuracy (S. Liang et al., 2025b). Separately, if a different instrument is used to observe the same blend with better resolution or seeing (e.g., space-based vs ground-based telescope), the individual objects in the blend could be identified (M. A. Troxel et al., 2023). A better characterization of the number of sources and their centroid is usually critical for deblending objects accurately (P. Melchior

et al., 2021).

Blending is inherently a phenomena that increases the uncertainty in measurement of the individual galaxy properties. Thus, one final way to address blending is by marginalizing over the uncertainty it introduces in the galaxy configuration. This line of reasoning naturally leads to *Bayesian* methods, whose formalism theoretically allows for a way to perform this marginalization. Unfortunately, Bayesian approaches tend to be very computationally expensive, which could be prohibitive in the era of Stage-IV surveys, since more data needs to be analyzed than ever before (see Section 1.7). However, in recent years, new computational and machine learning tools have spurred the development of efficient Bayesian algorithms whose application could be feasible in this context (e.g., D. P. Kingma & M. Welling, 2019; I. Kobyzev et al., 2020). Bayesian methods at the image level could mitigate many important systematics and allow for extracting the maximum amount of cosmological information from the data. We discuss Bayesian methods and new developments relevant for cosmology in Section 1.11.

In the next section we discuss algorithms that have been used to calibrate the shear systematics discussed including blending.

1.10 Shear bias calibration

Several algorithms have been developed to calibrate these biases in shape measurements. The currently dominant paradigm is an approach known as *self-calibration* (E. Huff & R. Mandelbaum, 2017; E. S. Sheldon & E. M. Huff, 2017; E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020). This approach has successfully applied to calibrate shear biases in DES Y1, Y3, and Y6 measurements (J. Zuntz et al., 2018; M. Gatti et al., 2021; M. Yamamoto et al., 2025).

The basic premise of this paradigm is using the real survey images themselves to calibrate shape measurements rather than relying exclusively on external simulations for this purpose. The method hinges on the fact that the effect of shear can be simulated on any type of image, and uses a finite-difference approach to isolate the response of shape measurements to shear. Self-calibration has been shown to significantly mitigate many of the shear biases discussed above. In some cases, the correction from image simulations was reduced by an order of magnitude compared to traditional approaches (J. Prat & D. Bacon, 2025). One reason for the success of self-calibration method is that using real images reduces uncertainty related to unknown galaxy morphology (i.e., model bias). More broadly, this method allows for direct characterization of how the real galaxy population responds to shear empirically. This is powerful because it is becoming increasingly difficult to include all relevant observational effects in image simulations.

Mathematically, self-calibration starts by Taylor expanding (to first order) some measured sheared ellipticity ϵ' around zero shear:

$$\epsilon' = \epsilon' \Big|_{g=0} + \frac{\partial \epsilon'}{\partial \mathbf{g}} \Big|_{g=0} \mathbf{g} = \epsilon + \mathbf{R}\mathbf{g}, \quad (1.15)$$

where $\epsilon'|_{g=0} = \epsilon$ since this is the definition of intrinsic ellipticity, and we have defined $\partial \epsilon' / \partial \mathbf{g} \equiv \mathbf{R}$. This quantity is known as the *response*. Next, we take the average of both sides:

$$\langle \epsilon' \rangle = \langle \epsilon \rangle + \langle \mathbf{R}\mathbf{g} \rangle, \quad (1.16)$$

where the first term is the average of intrinsic ellipticities of galaxies in our sample. Assuming that these are randomly oriented we can construct our shear estimator $\hat{\mathbf{g}}$ as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{g}} = \langle \mathbf{R} \rangle^{-1} \langle \epsilon' \rangle. \quad (1.17)$$

The next big idea in self-calibration is that \mathbf{R} can be directly estimated using the real survey images themselves. Some amount of artificial shear Δg_j can be applied to an astronomical image and the response is estimated via a finite difference:

$$R_{ij} = \frac{\epsilon'_i(+\Delta g_j) - \epsilon'_i(-\Delta g_j)}{2\Delta g_j}, \quad (1.18)$$

where $\epsilon'_i(\pm \Delta g_j)$ is the ellipticity measured when a small amount of positive or negative shear is applied in the j component. It is important to stress that any sufficiently well-behaved shape measurement algorithm could be used within this framework.

The first implementation of this approach is called METACALIBRATION, which was introduced in [E. Huff & R. Mandelbaum \(2017\)](#). In this work, the authors demonstrate that METACALIBRATION can measure shear at an accuracy better than 0.1% using image simulations adjacent to the GREAT3 challenge ([R. Mandelbaum et al., 2014](#)). They tested this approach across various galaxy morphologies (realistic and parametric), PSF properties, and several otherwise biased shape measurement algorithm. A companion paper ([E. S. Sheldon & E. M. Huff, 2017](#)) extends the METACALIBRATION approach to correct for both shear response and selection biases. They also test METACALIBRATION on a large set of image simulations with additional realism including PSF ellipticity, star contamination, missing data, and detection thresholds. In all cases, shear was recovered within Stage-IV survey requirements. The next iteration of this method is METADETECTION ([E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020](#); [H. Hoekstra, 2021](#); [H. Hoekstra et al., 2021](#)), which accounts for detection shear (Section 1.8) and blending biases in the case that sources are at the same redshift. The idea for this extension is to

follow the self-calibration algorithm, but redo the detection after artificially shearing images. It has been demonstrated to successfully calibrate LSST-like image simulations with constant shear applied (E. S. Sheldon et al., 2023).

One important note on METACALIBRATION and METADETECTION is that shear must be applied on the PSF-deconvolved galaxy images. Typically images are first deconvolved by the true PSF, sheared by some small amount, and then reconvolved by some reference PSF. The problem here is that the original image has pixel noise, and this procedure will introduce correlated noise which could bias subsequent ellipticity measurement. The solution usually adopted is to add additional noise to the final image that cancel this anisotropy, which preserves the correction but increases the shear measurement uncertainty. Mitigation strategies for this degradation in SNR is being developed using deep integration fields (Z. Zhang et al., 2023).

A related method for self-calibration, is the more recent Anacal method (X. Li et al., 2022, 2023a, 2024, 2025b,a), which analytically calibrates shear bias by projecting galaxy images into a set of basis functions. This method has been shown in simulations to achieve the same level of accuracy as METACALIBRATION and METADETECTION, but is significantly faster (about 1000 galaxies can be processed per CPU second).

Another set of algorithms have taken a different direction and use a Bayesian approach for estimating shear from a set of images. For instance, the *Bayesian Fourier Domain* (BFD) algorithm analytically models the likelihood of shear on a set of measured moments (in Fourier space) from galaxies in the lensing sample G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong (2014); G. M. Bernstein et al. (2016). It relies on a set of deep-field galaxies to approximate the true intrinsic moment distribution. This method is promising but has not been applied on real images yet. Finally, there algorithms that forward model galaxy images in real space to measure shapes. The goal is to include sources of systematics in the forward model and automatically calibrate shear biases by marginalizing over these (L. Miller et al., 2007; L. Miller et al., 2013; M. D. Schneider et al., 2015; J. J. Buchanan et al., 2023; Euclid Collaboration et al., 2024). These methods are traditionally more computationally expensive than self-calibration or moment-based approaches, but in principle could enable the extraction of the maximum amount of information from astronomical images with no external calibrations required (L. Miller et al., 2007). In Chapter 4, I present innovations on one such framework (M. D. Schneider et al., 2015), which improve its feasibility and potential applicability on real data.

1.11 Bayesian Statistics and Forward Modeling

Bayesian statistics provides a rigorous framework to quantify the effect of prior knowledge in our uncertainty of a new measurement. The foundational equation for this area of statistics is the so-called *Bayes rule* or *Bayes theorem*:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A)P(B|A)}{P(B)}, \quad (1.19)$$

where A and B are two events and $P(\cdot)$ denotes the probability of a given event. The quantity $P(A|B)$ denotes the probability that A occurs given that B occurs, which also captures the correlation between these events.

When Bayes rule is applied to the scientific context, we imagine an underlying (statistical) model f that relates a set of parameters Θ with observed data X . Bayes theorem then becomes:

$$P(\Theta|X) = \frac{P(\Theta)P(X|\Theta)}{P(X)}. \quad (1.20)$$

In this light, each part of this equation takes on an important meaning. The quantity $P(\Theta)$ is known as the *prior* and encodes our knowledge of the parameters we want to learn (e.g., from previous experiments). Next, $P(X|\Theta)$ is the *likelihood*, which is usually determined by the model f . Then, the *posterior* $P(\Theta|X)$ which represents our updated knowledge on the uncertainty of the parameter of interest Θ . Finally, $P(X)$ is known as the *evidence*, which can be rewritten as:

$$P(X) = \int d\theta P(X|\theta)P(\theta), \quad (1.21)$$

where θ is a specific value of Θ . In other words, $P(X)$ is the likelihood of the data marginalized over all possible values of Θ weighted by the prior. This last quantity is fundamentally why Bayesian statistics is difficult: the integral in Equation 1.21 can become intractable as the dimensionality of Θ grows. See also Section 3.9 for an interpretation of Bayesian statistics in the context of probabilistic cataloging.

Bayesian inference refers to the process by which we can obtain samples from the posterior distribution or otherwise some statistic of interest (e.g., mode, mean, expected values, etc.). The classical way to perform Bayesian inference is by using a *Markov Chain Monte Carlo* or *MCMC* for short (C. J. Geyer, 1992). At a high level, MCMC samples the posterior distribution by creating a *Markov Chain* (J. R. Norris, 1998) whose stationary distribution³ converges to the desired posterior distribution. The classical and most popular variation of

³The stationary distribution of a Markov chain is the distribution of states of the chain after a very large number of steps has been taken.

MCMC is known as *random walk Metropolis-Hastings*, it constructs a specific acceptance probability of a new state in the chain that guarantees the stationary distribution is the posterior, and uses a multi-dimensional Gaussian centered around the current state to propose new states for transition (M. Betancourt, 2017). One problem with this version of MCMC is that can exhibit pathological behavior in high dimensions or when probability densities have difficult geometries, rendering it inefficient.

A more recent variation of MCMC is *Hamiltonian Monte Carlo* (HMC) (R. M. Neal et al., 2011), which takes advantage of the geometry induced by the probability distribution to improve the sampling of MCMC. Specifically, it takes advantage of gradients of the likelihood distribution to propose transitions that are closer to regions of high probability (M. Betancourt, 2017). One problem with HMC is that it requires very careful tuning to be efficient and reliably achieve convergence. These problems are solved by a variation of HMC called No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) (M. D. Hoffman et al., 2014), which implements an adaptation scheme to remove most of the tuning necessary. NUTS is currently the industry standard for sampling high-dimensional posteriors (M. D. Hoffman et al., 2014). In Chapter 4 we take advantage of NUTS and GPUs to sample from hierarchical Bayesian model for shear.

More modern approaches use machine learning to efficiently approximate the posterior distribution, as *variational inference* (D. P. Kingma & M. Welling, 2019; K. Cranmer et al., 2020). This is a supervised learning approach where the loss function is defined by probability distributions, and neural networks (NNs) output the parameters of these distributions. The idea is that, through optimization, NNs will learn to assign more uncertainty in difficult prediction examples and smaller uncertainty to easy ones. *Simulation based inference* (SBI) is a variational inference procedure which uses a training set obtained from simulations of the physical phenomena of interest (K. Cranmer et al., 2020). The biggest drawback of SBI is that simulations are usually an imperfect representation of measurement data, and characterizing biases incurred by NNs is difficult given their very large parameter space. In Chapter 3 we present an application of simulation based inference to galaxy deblending.

More broadly, Bayesian approaches are part of a recent trend in cosmology to build fast *forward models*. Building and inverting forward models has become feasible with the advent of new computational techniques and hardware (i.e., GPUs), either via ML or gradient-based MCMCs. One concrete application of this is *field-level inference*, where a forward model is used to extract cosmological information using the field data directly without using summary statistics. This in principle would allow to extract the maximum information possible from cosmological data, including all higher-order statistics (e.g., all N -point statistics from correlation functions in lensing maps). One concrete example of field-level inference is the work from A. J. Zhou et al. (2024), which develops a catalog-to-cosmology framework that

provides access to cosmology information in shear and convergence maps beyond 2-pt statistics. Both Chapters 3 and 4 develop efficient forward models to extract information from galaxy images.

1.12 Chapters Summary

My thesis focuses on new tools and techniques to address image-level systematics relevant to weak lensing in the context of Stage-IV surveys.

Chapters 2 and 3 focus on blending, which will become increasingly relevant in surveys like LSST as their depth increases (J. Sanchez et al., 2021). More specifically, Chapter 2 focuses on aiding the development of new deblending algorithms (i.e., deblenders) via a Python software package called BTK. This package aims to centralize algorithms for generation of synthetic galaxy blends and the evaluation of deblending methods. Next, in Chapter 3, we develop a novel deblender based on probabilistic machine learning techniques (Section 1.11), and evaluate it on a simulated dataset of LSST-like images of parametric galaxy and star blends. Finally, in Chapter 4 we develop a new shear inference algorithm based on the hierarchical Bayesian framework in M. D. Schneider et al. (2015). We rigorously test our new approach on a dataset consisting of LSST-like images of isolated parametric galaxies, and demonstrate that, in this context, the shear estimated is within the Stage-IV multiplicative bias requirement.

CHAPTER 2

The Blending ToolKit: A Simulation Framework for Evaluation of Galaxy Detection and Deblending

2.1 Preface

This chapter is reproduced in its entirety from the paper “The Blending ToolKit: A Simulation Framework for Evaluation of Galaxy Detection and Deblending” published in the Open Journal of Astrophysics, Volume 8, page E14 (I. Mendoza et al., 2025), with co-authors Andrii Torchylo, Thomas Sainrat, Axel Guinot, Alexandre Boucaud, Maxime Paillassa, Camille Avestruz, Prakruth Adari, Eric Aubourg, Biswajit Biswas, James Buchanan, Patricia Burchat, Cyrille Doux, Remy Joseph, Sowmya Kamath, Alex I. Malz, Grant Merz, Hironao Miyatake, Cécile Roucelle, and Tianqing Zhang. As the first author of this publication my contributions included: leading project within LSST-DESC, being the maintainer and lead developer of the codebase, writing bulk of paper text, and mentoring undergraduate student (Andrii Torchylo).

The paper presents a software package developed with the DESC collaboration to aid studies of galaxy blending and the development of deblending algorithms.

2.2 Abstract

We present an open source Python library for simulating overlapping (i.e., *blended*) images of galaxies and performing self-consistent comparisons of detection and deblending algorithms based on a suite of metrics. The package, named *Blending Toolkit* (BTK), serves as a modular, flexible, easy-to-install, and simple-to-use interface for exploring and analyzing systematic effects related to blended galaxies in cosmological surveys such as the Vera Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST). BTK has three main components: (1) a set of

modules that perform fast image simulations of blended galaxies, using the open source image simulation package GALSIM; (2) a module that standardizes the inputs and outputs of existing deblending algorithms; (3) a library of deblending metrics commonly defined in the galaxy deblending literature. In combination, these modules allow researchers to explore the impacts of galaxy blending in cosmological surveys. Additionally, BTK provides researchers who are developing a new deblending algorithm a framework to evaluate algorithm performance and make principled comparisons with existing deblenders. BTK includes a suite of tutorials and comprehensive documentation. The source code is publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/LSSTDESC/BlendingToolKit>.

2.3 Introduction

Modern ground-based cosmological surveys, including the Dark Energy Survey ([Dark Energy Survey Collaboration et al., 2016](#)), the Hyper Suprime-Cam Subaru Strategic Program ([H. Aihara et al., 2018](#)), and the upcoming Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST, [Ž. Ivezić et al. \(2019b\)](#)) will detect an unprecedented number of galaxies and have the potential to significantly improve our understanding of the Universe. As the sensitivity of these surveys increases, so does the density of detectable light sources (stars and galaxies), which in turn increases the rate at which sources overlap with each other in images. This phenomenon, known as *blending*, is a major potential source of systematic bias and uncertainty for modern surveys ([P. Melchior et al., 2021](#)); blending undermines our ability to identify individual sources in a given image ([W. A. Dawson et al., 2016](#); [M. A. Troxel et al., 2023](#)) and disentangle their properties, such as flux and shape, from those of neighboring sources ([W. A. Dawson et al., 2016](#); [H. Hoekstra et al., 2017](#); [Euclid Collaboration et al., 2019](#)).

In LSST, simulations have been used to estimate that about 60% of galaxies will be blended to some degree (at full-depth, i.e. $r \simeq 27.2$) ([J. Sanchez et al., 2021](#)), 51% of galaxies will be overlapping with sources that can be detected individually (at depth $r \simeq 24$) ([K. Eckert et al., 2020](#)), and that between 15% and 30% of galaxies in i -band images will be part of *unrecognized blends* (at depth $i \simeq 27$ and $i \simeq 26$ respectively) ([W. A. Dawson et al., 2016](#); [M. A. Troxel et al., 2023](#)) – i.e., blends that are detected as a single object, but actually correspond to two or more sources. For HSC, it was estimated that about 58% of the detected objects in the i -band wide survey are blended sources (at depth $r \simeq 26$) ([J. Bosch et al., 2017](#)). Since a large fraction of the galaxies detected in modern surveys will be impacted by blending, blended objects cannot be discarded without losing a significant amount of statistical power ([C. Chang et al., 2013, 2015](#)) and inducing selection bias in the cosmological probes ([J. Hartlap et al., 2011](#)). Thus, we need an accurate understanding of the systematic

errors that blending contributes to our measurements, and robust algorithms to mitigate these errors.

Blending impacts the two most important static probes of dark energy for ground-based cosmological surveys: weak gravitational lensing and galaxy clusters. Weak gravitational lensing uses the fact that observed galaxy shapes trace the underlying dark matter distribution (D. Huterer, 2002; M. Kilbinger, 2015). In principle, blending impacts the three types of two-point statistics (cosmic shear, galaxy-galaxy lensing, and galaxy clustering) commonly used in weak lensing analyses, although its effect on cosmic shear has been most widely studied. *Cosmic shear* is the relatively small, approximately linear distortion of shapes by weak lensing from large-scale mass distributions. Blending can introduce several types of potential bias in measured shear: selection bias due to detection inefficiency for blended galaxies (N. Kaiser, 2000; G. M. Bernstein & M. Jarvis, 2002; C. Hirata & U. Seljak, 2003a; W. A. Dawson et al., 2016); shape bias for blended galaxies (W. A. Dawson et al., 2016; H. Hoekstra et al., 2017; S. Samuroff et al., 2018; Euclid Collaboration et al., 2019); and increased pixel-noise bias and reduced statistical sensitivity (J. Sanchez et al., 2021). Additionally, blending impacts galaxy photometry (S. Huang et al., 2018a; A. Boucaud et al., 2020), and even causes (rare) catastrophic outliers in photometry measurements (S. Everett et al., 2022). Because blending will occur between galaxies at different redshifts (e.g., W. A. Dawson et al., 2016), photometric redshift (photo- z) estimates, which are an essential ingredient of weak lensing cosmological analyses, are impacted by blending (R. Mandelbaum, 2018). Algorithms are already in development for measuring photo- z in the presence of blends (D. M. Jones & A. F. Heavens, 2019a,b). However, more studies are needed to fully understand the impact of blending on photo- z estimation for cosmic shear analyses.

Quantities of interest in cluster cosmology, including total cluster mass and redshifts of member galaxies, provide another important cosmological probe (e.g., Planck Collaboration et al., 2016; G. F. Lesci et al., 2022; T. M. C. Abbott et al., 2020; T. Sunayama et al., 2023; S. Bocquet et al., 2024; A. B. Mantz et al., 2014), as they describe the high density peaks in the mass power spectrum, providing complementary information to the weak lensing results. Galaxy clusters host a particularly high density of galaxies, which increases the rate of blending (S. Liang, 2022); therefore, blending has the potential to bias these important measurements. The best known way to calibrate the total cluster mass is by measuring the weak lensing distortion of background source galaxies (e.g., C. A. Metzler et al., 1999). Recent studies show that *recognized* galaxy blends – i.e., blends in which each galaxy member is accurately identified as an individual galaxy – in clusters could bias the weak lensing profile ($\Delta\Sigma(r)$) by about 20% (M. Ramel et al., 2023), likely due to shape misestimation. One of the main sources of bias in estimating the cluster mass is the misidentification of cluster

members as background galaxies (e.g., [T. N. Varga et al., 2019](#)). The classification accuracy is strongly dependent upon precise photo- z estimates for cluster member and background galaxies (e.g., [J. H. Esteves et al., 2024](#)). Blending has the potential to increase the rate of misidentification in two ways: (1) cluster and background galaxies could be blended to the extent that they become unrecognized blends, at which point contamination becomes unavoidable; (2) blending from faint sources could impact the observed colors of galaxies ([D. Gruen et al., 2019](#)), which would bias estimates of photo- z s.

Given the plethora of complicated biases blending can induce in cosmology probes, it is essential to leverage simulations to understand the impact of blending on these probes and to calibrate blending related biases in analyses ([P. Melchior et al., 2021](#)). A widely used package for generating simulated galaxy images is GALSIM ([B. T. P. Rowe et al., 2015](#)), which can generate galaxy images for a range of galaxy profiles, point spread functions (PSF), and noise levels. GALSIM has been used to calibrate blending biases for weak lensing (e.g., [N. MacCrann et al., 2022](#); [R. Dalal et al., 2023a](#)), and forms the basis for several large-scale simulations of cosmological surveys. One such simulation emulating LSST observations is the LSST DESC second data challenge (DC2) Simulated Sky Survey ([LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration \(LSST DESC\) et al., 2021a](#)), which uses a full end-to-end approach – starting from N-body cosmological simulations and outputting catalogs based on forward-modeled astronomical images processed by the LSST Science Pipelines. DC2 has already been used to support various blending studies in the context of LSST ([J. J. Buchanan et al., 2022](#); [M. Ramel et al., 2023](#)). Finally, another powerful tool is to use multiple surveys with different angular resolutions, such as a ground-based and a space-based survey, to characterize the rate of blending ([R. Mandelbaum et al., 2018](#); [M. A. Troxel et al., 2023](#)) or improve deblending ([R. Joseph et al., 2021](#)).

Another approach to mitigating the blending problem is the development and application of *deblenders*: algorithms designed to measure the individual properties of each galaxy in a blend. In principle, an ideal deblender would allow the recovery of these individual properties and the corresponding catalogs could be analyzed ignoring blending altogether. However, in practice, detection and deblending can fail in various ways: blends may not be identified (unrecognized blends), and the deblending process might infer galaxy properties inaccurately depending on the severity of the blend. The former effect can introduce an additional source of systematic error in cosmic shear measurements ([E. Nourbakhsh et al., 2022](#)). SourceExtractor (SExtractor) is an early deblender that uses a thresholding technique for object detection and a multiple isophotal analysis for deblending ([E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996](#)). More modern deblenders use non-parametric constrained optimization techniques ([R. Joseph et al., 2016](#); [P. Melchior et al., 2018](#)), such as the SCARLET deblender, or machine learning techniques ([B.](#)

Arcelin et al., 2021; D. L. Hansen et al., 2022; R. Liu et al., 2023; G. Merz et al., 2023; M. L. Sampson et al., 2024; B. Biswas et al., 2024).

Despite the range of available simulation packages and deblenders, there is currently no standard framework dedicated to creating customizable simulations of blended galaxies, or comparing the performance of different deblending algorithms using consistent simulated galaxy densities, fluxes, noise levels, image resolutions, etc., and consistent deblending metrics. To address this limitation, we introduce the *Blending Toolkit* (BTK), a modular Python-based software package that leverages GALSIM to generate reproducible and customizable astronomical images of galaxy blends under the observing conditions of several dark energy surveys. BTK also includes a module standardizing existing deblenders such that their outputs can be directly compared against one another when applied to the same images. Finally, our package includes a growing library of deblending metrics to enable evaluation of the performance of deblenders.

We will first describe the design philosophy for BTK in Section 2.4. Then, we describe the software modules comprising BTK in detail Section 2.5, followed by an outline of the existing Jupyter Notebook tutorials and documentation in Section 2.6. We provide a brief summary and outlook for the future in Section 2.7.

2.4 Development Approach

The original motivation for BTK was to build a framework that could bring together the various simulation and deblending efforts within the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC) Blending Working Group and the broader cosmology community. We learned of a number of ideas for deblenders being developed; however, it was difficult to assess their relative performance compared to existing state-of-the-art deblenders, or their strengths and weaknesses. This was mainly because the majority of deblender studies used a different set of astronomical images (or simulations) and metrics to evaluate their deblenders. In order to make progress in deblender development, a way to assess and benchmark existing deblenders consistently was needed, and this is one of the main purposes of BTK.

BTK is designed to be:

- **Modular:** The simulation, deblending, and metric components of BTK can be connected together to form a full analysis pipeline, as demonstrated in the tutorials available for BTK (see Section 2.6); however, these components are also designed to be usable independently.
- **Customizable:** Users can customize the various BTK modules to fit their desired

blending analysis. For example, the simulations of blended galaxies within BTK contain many options for changing the configuration of galaxy blends (e.g., the rate of blending) or the observing conditions (e.g., noise level or PSF). Comprehensive documentation and examples make it clear how to change the various options within the package.

- **Parallelizable and Reproducible:** Every computationally intensive process in BTK (e.g., producing simulations or running deblenders) can be split across multiple CPUs to improve efficiency. We carefully ensured that all simulations produced by BTK are reproducible given a single random seed. Randomness is propagated using a `numpy.random.SeedSequence` object during multiprocessing to guarantee said reproducibility.
- **Easy-to-Install:** BTK only has a few Python dependencies, the main one being GALSIM. This ensures that the package is easily installable with a single `pip` command.

2.5 Structure

The overall structure of BTK is summarized in Figure 2.1. The *Generation* module provides the simulated data containing blended galaxy images, isolated galaxy images, and ground truth properties of galaxies in the blend. Then, with the *Deblending* module, detection or deblending algorithms can be applied to the generated images of galaxy blends. Users can choose to implement their own algorithm or use one of the existing ones in BTK. Finally, in the *Metrics* module, users can evaluate the performance of their detection or deblending algorithms by comparing their output to the ground truth data. This module also contains functionality to perform measurements on the simulated images, including photometry and galaxy shapes, which makes it possible to measure the impact of blending on relevant physical quantities.

2.5.1 Generation Module

The Generation module renders simulations of galaxy blends that can be used as an input to deblenders for their evaluation. Specifically, this module provides a `DrawBlendsGenerator` class that outputs galaxy blend images in batches i.e., a small collection of objects that can fit in computer memory. This class is implemented as a python generator object, which at each iteration outputs the galaxy blend images, as well as auxiliary galaxy images and truth galaxy catalogs. This generator class also supports multiprocessing to increase the speed of the generation procedure.

Figure 2.1: **Overall BTK structure.** The software package consists of three main modules: *Generation*, *Deblending*, and *Metrics*. Each arrow indicates the data flow between modules.

Simulated galaxy blends are produced by simulating individual galaxy images with GALSIM according to the provided galaxy properties and specified survey observing conditions. Then, these individual galaxy images are combined into a single galaxy blend image, and noise is added. Additionally, the `DrawBlendsGenerator` keeps track of the true properties of every galaxy in each blend, and these properties are returned alongside the galaxy blend images and the (noiseless) images of each individual galaxy. These additional outputs are helpful when evaluating or training deblenders, as is the case for ML-based algorithms. For convenience and validation, the output is handled by the `BlendBatch` class. An outline of the overall structure of this module is presented in Figure 2.2.

The user can customize the blend generation procedure by modifying the following:

Catalog: The `Catalog` class standardizes the input information about the galaxies that will be used for rendering. The underlying structure of the catalog is an `astropy` table (Astropy Collaboration et al., 2013, 2018, 2022), where each row contains information about a given galaxy’s properties such as ellipticity, magnitude in different bands, and size. BTK currently supports two types of catalog formats: CatSim’s parametric catalogs (A. J. Connolly et al., 2014a) and GALSIM’s COSMOS catalogs (R. Mandelbaum et al., 2012). Each of these types of catalogs has its dedicated class in BTK.

The `CatsimCatalog` class used in BTK uses an `astropy` table containing parameters for

Figure 2.2: **Generation Module of BTK.** This module contains the functionality and configurations for creating galaxy simulations in BTK. The `sampling_function` submodule encodes how galaxies are organized into blends. The `surveys` submodule specifies the observing conditions. Finally, the `catalog` submodule encodes the properties of each individual galaxy. The red blocks are intended to be easily customized by the user, while green blocks are intended to be used ‘as-is’ and can only be modified by advanced users. Yellow blocks indicate the outputs of a given module. See Section 2.5.1 for more details on this module.

simulating galaxies based on a three component model: a bulge, a disk and an AGN¹. Each galaxy has an overall total flux, each component has an associated flux fraction, and the bulge and disk components have independent sizes and ellipticities. All galaxy properties except for the flux are fixed across all LSST bands. The input catalog for this class follows the format used by CatSim (A. J. Connolly et al., 2014a), which is the earliest version of an end-to-end LSST simulation framework. BTK provides a sample catalog of approximately 85000 galaxies taken from the original CatSim simulation². The galaxy properties from the CatSim catalog were designed to match the key observables in the LSST survey, and are taken from previous studies on galaxy formation and SDSS observations (G. Bruzual & S. Charlot, 2003; G. De Lucia et al., 2006; J. E. González et al., 2009).

Alternatively, the image-based COSMOS catalog (R. Mandelbaum et al., 2012) can be used to generate realistic galaxy profiles. The COSMOS catalog consists of about 80,000 galaxies extracted from the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) COSMOS survey (A. M. Koekemoer et al., 2007), which are used for the base catalog in GALSIM (B. T. P. Rowe et al., 2015). Currently,

¹Some galaxies have an Active Galactic Nucleus, which means that their nucleus is much brighter than usual, sometimes as much as the rest of the galaxy.

²<https://www.lsst.org/scientists/simulations/catsim>

the `CosmosCatalog` class within BTK enables using the COSMOS catalog to render BTK blends by combining multiple GALSIM `RealGalaxy` profiles that were constructed from HST images.³ When using COSMOS galaxies in a multi-band survey within BTK, the same F814W magnitude is used for all bands, though accounting for the different filters' zeropoints and exposure times. However, a user may also provide multi-band information, which will then be used by BTK to provide an independent flux in each band. Importantly, this functionality does not account for color gradients within a galaxy profile.

Sampling Function: The sampling functions are customizable functions that select galaxies from a large catalog to form a given output blend, as well as their relative location within the blend. These functions are designed to be flexible, for example, one of the default sampling functions in BTK randomly selects pairs of galaxies in a catalog and outputs 2-galaxy blends with the brightest galaxy fixed to the center of the stamp, while the dimmer galaxy is a uniformly random distance from the central galaxy. Most sampling functions currently implemented support various input parameters that control the degree of blending and total number of galaxies in the galaxy blends produced. Users are additionally encouraged to create their own sampling functions depending on their scientific needs. One of the tutorials, `01-advanced-generation`, detailed in Section 2.6, provides guidelines and examples on how to achieve this.

Survey: The `Survey` class contains all information of a given astronomical survey, including the telescope optics, which guarantee that generated images approximately reproduce the observing conditions of the ones observed with that particular survey.

To organize this information, BTK uses `SURVEYCODEX`⁴, a tiny Python library with referenced survey parameters for the current main galaxy surveys as well as their filters. For more information about `SURVEYCODEX` and currently supported surveys, see Section 2.9. Importantly, the `Survey` class also contains the point-spread function (PSF) that is applied to galaxies, which can also be easily specified and changed by the user.

Once the catalog, sampling function, and survey are specified, simulated data in the form of `BlendBatch` objects can be easily generated using the `DrawBlendsGenerator` class.

2.5.2 Deblending

In the context of BTK, we refer to a *deblender* as any algorithm that takes as input images of galaxy blends and attempts to output properties of the individual sources (e.g., centroid location) or a reconstruction of the individual galaxies composing the blend.

³For more details see https://galsim-developers.github.io/GalSim/_build/html/real_gal.html

⁴<https://github.com/LSSTDESC/surveycodex>

One of the main goals of BTK is to allow users to test their preferred detection or deblending algorithm in a controlled setting. We provide a framework that enables running such algorithms directly on the `BlendBatch` output of the Generation module (Section 2.5.1). The results can then be analyzed by the user separately or compared with other algorithms using a set of BTK built-in blending metrics, as described in Section 2.5.3. An outline of overall structure of the deblending module is presented in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: **Deblending Module** of BTK. This module contains a standardized library of deblenders that can be used within BTK. The module is designed to allow users to run their preferred detection or deblending algorithm on simulated data from the Generation module of BTK. Additionally, users can implement a new algorithm by creating a new subclass of the `Deblender` class. The output of `Deblender` in BTK is a `DeblendBatch` object, which can contain a predicted catalog, deblended images, and segmentation. See Section 2.5.2 for more details on this module.

Our deblender framework is facilitated by the `Deblender` class, which aims to standardize the inputs and outputs of any given deblending algorithm. The input is always an instance of the `BlendBatch` class (defined in Section 2.5.1), and the outputs are structured into the `DeblendBatch` class containing the following attributes:

1. **Predicted catalog:** contains detection information about each galaxy (i.e., centroid locations), as well as additional optional measurements of galaxy properties.
2. **Deblended images:** contains the reconstruction of each individually detected galaxy.
3. **Segmentation:** contains pixel level segmentation information of the blended image, i.e., for each detected source, and for each pixel of the blended image, a value of 0 or 1 indicating whether the given source contributes flux to that pixel.⁵

⁵We opt to use this data format for image segmentation, rather than allowing are more flexible representation

Note that not all of these outputs are required as output of a given `Deblender` subclass. This means that our framework accommodates algorithms that only perform detection or only reconstruction, for instance.

Users are encouraged to contribute to our growing library of BTK deblenders by implementing their own algorithm as a subclass of `Deblender`. This would enable other BTK users to use their deblender and consistently compare with existing ones. We provide several examples of ready-to-use deblenders, and provide tutorials on how this class should be structured.

Currently in BTK, the following deblenders are implemented:

- Peak-finding (S. van der Walt et al., 2014): Basic algorithm for finding local maxima. It takes as input a target image with one or more light sources, the minimum distance between detected peaks, the minimum intensity of peaks, and the maximum number of peaks that can be detected. It outputs a detection catalog corresponding to the detected peaks.
- Source Extractor (E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996; K. Barbary, 2016): We use the python implementation (SEP) of this widely-used software for generating light source catalogs. In the context of BTK, the input to this function is the target image, the minimum distance between matches (in arcseconds), and the minimum pixel value for detection. This algorithm outputs a detection catalog and a segmentation, which is in turn used to provide a basic reconstruction (by extracting the pixels corresponding to the segmentation from the target image).
- SCARLET (P. Melchior et al., 2018): Deblending algorithm using non-parametric constrained optimization, and which is integrated into the LSST software pipeline. The input includes the detections, the choice of SCARLET models be optimized for each detection, the PSF, and the noise level. The output is a deblended galaxy reconstruction for each detection.

Specifically, for Source Extractor, we use the SEP (Source Extractor in Python) implementation (K. Barbary, 2016), and the `peak_local_max` function⁶ within `scikit-image` (S. van der Walt et al., 2014) for the peak-finding algorithm.

2.5.3 Metrics and Measurement

BTK provides a suite of metrics for evaluating deblending algorithms, which is designed to be applied given the `BlendBatch` and `DeblendBatch` classes outputted from the previous two

with values between 0 and 1 (perhaps corresponding to the fraction of the flux for each source), because our current deblenders and metrics would not take advantage of the additional flexibility.

⁶https://scikit-image.org/docs/stable/api/skimage.feature.html#skimage.feature.peak_local_max

modules. However, the tutorials and documentation also demonstrate the expected input format for these metrics, so that they could also be used in isolation from the standard BTK pipeline. An outline of overall structure of this module is also presented in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: **Metrics module of BTK.** This module uses the outputs of the generation module (the ground truth) and the deblender to evaluate the quality of the deblending. Before comparison, the **matching** module is used to assign true galaxies to detected galaxies and enable the evaluation of residuals. The matched outputs are subjected to various metrics divided in three categories: *detection*, *segmentation*, and *reconstruction*. Finally, the **measurement** module uses the images or catalogs from **BlendBatch** or **DeblendBatch** to compute physical galaxy quantities for analysis including ellipticities, signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR), and blendedness. See Section 2.5.3 for more details on this module.

The BTK metrics are divided into three broad categories:

- **Detection:** These are metrics related to correctly counting the number of galaxies in a given image, as well as the accuracy of the predicted centroid of that galaxy. Examples of these metrics include *precision*, *recall*, and the *efficiency matrix*.
- **Segmentation:** These metrics evaluate the quality of assignments of individual pixels to a corresponding identified source. An example of this metric type is *intersection-over-union* (IoU).
- **Reconstruction:** These metrics relate to the correctness of the individual galaxy images obtained from a given galaxy blend. Examples of this metric type include the *peak signal-to-noise ratio* (PSNR) (N. Ponomarenko et al., 2011) and the *structural similarity index* (SSIM) (Z. Wang et al., 2004).

We provide a full list of the currently implemented metrics in BTK in Table 2.1. For each metric, we also provide the corresponding equation and a brief description. Each of these metrics has been used previously at least once in the galaxy deblending literature.

All of the metrics implemented in BTK require information about the correspondence between detections and true sources, i.e., the *matching* between the true and predicted galaxy catalog. In particular, the detection metrics require knowledge of which detections actually correspond to true objects, so that the number of true positives can be computed, while the other two types of metrics compare segmentations or reconstructions of galaxy images in a one-to-one basis. Given that the matching procedure can be subject to different user choices, we provide this functionality within BTK, through the *Matcher* class, whose implementation through subclasses performs this procedure.

We currently have implemented two different algorithms to perform matching, both of which are based on the relative distances between true centroids and detections, as well as their respective counts. The first implemented matcher is the `PixelHungarianMatcher`, which matches galaxy centroids and detections based on their pixel value. This matcher is based on the Hungarian algorithm (H. W. Kuhn, 1955a), which finds an optimal weight matching in bipartite graphs. We use the implementation available as the SciPy (P. Virtanen et al., 2020) function `linear_sum_assignment`. The other matcher implemented within BTK is the `SkyClosestNeighbourMatcher`, which performs matching using (ra, dec) coordinates using the `SkyCoord.match_to_catalog_sky` method in Astropy (Astropy Collaboration et al., 2013, 2018, 2022). This method internally uses KD Trees and a nearest neighbor algorithm to output matches. Additional custom matching algorithms can be implemented in BTK creating subclasses of the *Matcher* parent class.

Finally, for additional evaluation of the deblending output, we provide a set of utility functions that can compute “measurements” based on the simulated galaxy images generated by BTK. The output of these measurement functions could be used to further evaluate the reconstruction from deblenders, or to assess the challenge posed by a particular galaxy blend. Currently, BTK provides the following measure functions:

- *Ellipticity measurement* of galaxy shapes using the KSB shear estimator implementation from the `galsim.hsm` module.
- *Aperture Photometry*, we provide a wrapper around the SEP aperture photometry methods to compute aperture photometry fluxes in BTK.
- *Blendedness* (B), which characterizes the degree to which the flux from a given light source overlaps with the flux of its neighbors. We use the definition from J. Bosch et al. (2017).

Metric	Type	Equation	Description
Precision	Detection	$p = TP/P$	The number of detections that are matched to sources (TP) divided by the total number of detections (P). It represents the quality of detections.
Recall	Detection	$r = TP/T$	The number of detections that are matched to sources (TP) divided by the total number of true sources (T). It represents the fraction of sources successfully detected.
F1-score	Detection	$F_1 = 2 \cdot (r^{-1} + p^{-1})^{-1}$	Harmonic mean between precision p and recall r , which symmetrically represents both in one metric.
Efficiency Matrix	Detection	E_{ij}	The i -th, j -th element of this matrix is the number of times that i number of galaxies were detected and matched in a blend containing j true galaxies.
Intersection-over-Union	Segmentation	$\text{IoU} = \frac{S_{\text{true}} \cap S_{\text{pred}}}{S_{\text{true}} \cup S_{\text{pred}}}$	Ratio of the intersection area between the true S_{true} and predicted S_{pred} segmentation and their union area.
Mean-squared-error	Reconstruction	$\text{MSR} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N (x_i^{\text{true}} - x_i^{\text{pred}})^2$	The mean squared residual between the true x^{true} and the reconstructed x^{pred} image, where N is number of pixels in the images.
Peak Signal-to-Noise ratio	Reconstruction	$\text{PSNR} = \log(M/\text{MSR}^2)$	The ratio between the maximum power of the signal (M) and the corrupting noise (MSR^2).
Structural Similarity Index	Reconstruction	$\text{SSIM} = l \cdot c \cdot s$	A more nuanced measure of similarity accounting for the luminance l , the contrast c , and the structure s when comparing two images. (See Z. Wang et al. (2004) for details.)

Table 2.1: **Metrics within BTK.** List of all the metrics available along with their type, equation, and a short description.

- *Signal-to-Noise ratio (SNR)*, which characterizes the relative brightness of the source with respect to the noise level of the image. We use the definition in [B. Arcelin et al. \(2021\)](#).

2.6 Tutorials and Examples

We have included comprehensive documentation⁷ in BTK in order to make this package as accessible as possible. In addition to the complete API, it contains a step-by-step user guide, instructions on how to acquire the galaxy catalogs, as well as a set of detailed tutorials with code examples. A code example demonstrating the BTK API is presented in Section 2.8. Tutorials are available in the BTK GitHub repository⁸ as Jupyter notebooks. The tutorials start with the basics of using BTK, and progress to advanced applications and customization of the codebase.

⁷<https://lsstdesc.org/BlendingToolKit/>

⁸<https://github.com/LSSTDESC/BlendingToolKit>

2.6.1 List of tutorials

In this section, we present the current list of tutorials. Note that the numbered prefix of the notebook names indicates relative complexity in increasing order.

- **00-quickstart**: This tutorial is an introduction to BTK, which goes through the entire pipeline of simulating data, deblending, and evaluating results with metrics. It presents the simplest version of the BTK workflow, making it ideal for newcomers to the codebase. More details on each module and customization options are presented in tutorials that follow.
- **01-advanced-generation**: This tutorial is a deeper dive into the `generation` module (Section 2.5.1) within BTK and showcases the different types of sampling functions, surveys, and observing condition options. We also demonstrate with examples how users would write their own sampling functions, vary the input PSF, and customize the survey objects. Finally, we also demonstrate how to use COSMOS Real galaxies (R. Mandelbaum et al., 2012) option within BTK to simulate galaxies with realistic morphology.
- **01-advanced-deblending**: This tutorial demonstrates usage of all the deblenders currently available within BTK (Section 2.5.2), including how to customize their hyperparameters, and what type of output is available from them. Finally, we also show how to run multiple deblenders on the same BTK generated data, which enables consistent comparisons between deblenders.
- **01-advanced-metrics**: This tutorial shows how to use all of the metrics within the metric library of BTK (Section 2.5.3), as well as explanations for the output, and plots on simple examples to develop intuition. We also demonstrate the measure functions that are available, and how to use them on BTK data products. Finally, we explain in more detail the matching procedure in BTK and the types of matching algorithms that are available.
- **02-advanced-plots**: In this tutorial, we create more complex analysis plots and evaluate multiple deblenders simultaneously within the BTK framework. For example, we demonstrate a comparison of two deblenders applied on the same simulated data that perform detection, and bin their precision and recall metrics by signal-to-noise (SNR). We also demonstrate applying measure functions to the output of the SCARLET deblender to compute the corresponding ellipticity residuals binned by SNR.

2.6.2 Example analysis plots

The final tutorial `02-advanced-plots` includes a variety of useful evaluation plots involving the use of multiple deblenders and metrics. In this section, we present the plots produced in this notebook as an example of the types of analyses that BTK could facilitate. The exact definition of all the metrics applied to produce the corresponding figures in this section can be found in Table 2.1.

Dataset: For all of the analysis plots we use the same `DrawBlendsGenerator`, although a different set of blends (random seeds) are used. We choose parametric bulge+disk+AGN blends from the CATSIM catalog for all examples (Section 2.5.1), where each blend can have anywhere from 0 to 10 galaxies, and the maximum distance of any source from the center of the 120×120 pixel stamp is 15 pixels, which makes blends highly likely. We choose to use the LSST *r*-band survey for all experiments with corresponding parameters presented in Section 2.9. Finally, we apply an AB magnitude cut of 18 on the bright end and 27 on the dim end.

Deblenders: In terms of the specific settings or hyper-parameters⁹ of the deblenders used, these are as follows for all experiments:

- *Scarlet*: We use exactly the same default settings as those in the SCARLET quick start guide¹⁰.
- *SEP*: We use a `thresh` parameter of 1.5 and `min_area` of 5 pixels with the `sep.extract` function¹¹, which are close to known reasonable settings for galaxy detection and photometry (e.g., J. Sanchez et al., 2021). We allow SEP to measure the background of each stamp and use this for the corresponding noise variance. Otherwise, we use the default SEP parameters.
- *Peak-finder*: We setup the `peak_local_max` algorithm with a `threshold` argument of 5 sigma above the noise level, and a `min_distance` argument equal to the PSF FWHM. These settings for the peak-finder are chosen conservatively to ensure high precision in its detections.

First, we compare the detection efficiency of SourceExtractor in Python (SEP) and the peak-finding algorithm from `scikit-image`. Both of the efficiency matrices are displayed in Figure 2.5, where the top matrix corresponds to peak-finding and the bottom to SEP. The

⁹We emphasize that the plots presented in this sections are meant to illustrate how the codebase could be used, and not to comprehensively evaluate these deblenders. Thus, we have chosen settings for these algorithms that are reasonable for our dataset, but that might not be optimal.

¹⁰<https://pmelchior.github.io/scarlet/0-quickstart.html>

¹¹<https://sep.readthedocs.io/en/stable/api/sep.extract.html#sep.extract>

efficiency matrices have been computed by accumulating the counts from a total of 1000 blends, and normalizing each column by the sum of that column. The colorbar in the figure thus goes from 0 (fully white) to 1 (fully black), where 0 for a given cell (i, j) means that for blends containing j galaxies, the deblender reported i (matched) detections 0 times. Similarly, a value of 1 for a cell (i, j) means that the deblender reported the correct number of (matched) detections 100% of the times for blends containing j galaxies. We can see from the efficiency matrices that SEP is overall better than the peak-finding algorithm at detecting sources in the blends we simulated, as more gray squares in the SEP efficiency matrix are closer to the diagonal. Moreover, SEP is able to detect up to 6 sources in blends with more than 8 galaxies whereas the peak-finding algorithm reaches a maximum of 5 accurate detection across blends of all sizes.

Next, in Figure 2.6 we show the recall of these two detection algorithms as a function of the true minimum SNR and maximum blendedness B of the galaxies in a given blend. The recall is computed by taking the number of detections that are matched with true galaxies whose SNR or blendedness satisfies the threshold, and dividing by the number of true galaxies satisfying the threshold. In the left plot, we see that as the minimum SNR threshold is increased, the recall increases for both deblenders. This is expected as we are excluding fainter objects as the threshold increases. However, we do not expect to achieve perfect recall even at very high SNRs due to blending. This is indeed what we see for both algorithms, as they both reach only approximately 0.9 recall at the brightest threshold. In terms of the relative performance between SEP and the peak-finder, SEP achieves significantly better recall in the low-SNR bins and the peak-finder achieves slightly better recall in the high-SNR bins. This is reasonable, as Source Extractor’s thresholding approach is more suitable for detecting faint sources, whereas peak-finding is more appropriate for bright, non-diffused light sources. In the right plot, we see that both methods achieve their highest recall when restricted to galaxies with low blendedness, and their recall smoothly decreases as we include more blended objects. We see that SEP performs significantly better than the peak-finder with our settings for all blendedness thresholds. Note that we do not include the corresponding precision plots as both algorithms achieve an overall precision close to 99% for our dataset.

Third, in Figure 2.7 we show three histograms corresponding to the reconstruction metrics available within BTK (see Table 2.1), comparing SEP and the SCARLET deblender. Each of the histograms is composed of the metric applied to the reconstructions of true galaxies that were detected and matched by the SEP detection algorithm (since SCARLET does not perform detection). The SEP’s reconstruction of a given galaxy is obtained by multiplying the pixel-wise segmentation outputted by SEP with the galaxy blend image. Overall, we see from the three histograms that SCARLET’s reconstructions are higher quality than

Figure 2.5: **Efficiency matrices of SEP and Peak-finding deblenders.** In this plot we show the efficiency matrices (as defined in Table 2.1) for the SEP and Peak-finding deblenders implemented in BTK applied to the dataset of CATSIM blends detailed in Section 2.6.2. The rows correspond to the number of detections and the columns to the true number of sources in a blend. Each cell of each matrix represents the fraction of times that each deblender predicted the row number of detections for the column number of true sources in a blend. See Section 2.6.2 for more details on this figure.

SEP’s reconstructions. For instance, the Mean-Squared Error (MSE) between SCARLET’s reconstructions and the true noiseless individual galaxy images are closer to zero on average

Figure 2.6: **Recall as a function of SNR and Blendedness for SEP and Peak-finding.** In this figure, we compare the achieved recall (as defined in Table 2.1) by the peak-finding (blue) and SEP (orange) deblenders as a function of the minimum SNR and maximum blendedness (B) of true galaxies applied to the same CATSIM blend dataset as Figure 2.5. See Section 2.6.2 for more details on this figure.

than SEP’s reconstructions are.¹² Moreover, the structure similarity index is closer to 1 on average for SCARLET, indicating higher visual similarity than SEP’s reconstructions. Both of these results are expected as SCARLET uses a more sophisticated constrained matrix factorization procedure to deblend light sources than SEP.

In Figure 2.8 we show the residuals between HSM ellipticity¹³ measured on reconstructions of individual galaxies from SCARLET and on the true individual galaxy images binned by SNR, blendedness (B), and HSM ellipticity measured on the true galaxy images ($e_{1,2}^{\text{true}}$). For this figure, we condition SCARLET on the true centroids of every galaxy in the blend, thus ignoring the effect of unrecognized blends. In each figure, the curve and points correspond to the mean value of each bin, and the shaded bands correspond to the error on the mean for that bin ($\sigma/\sqrt{N_{\text{bin}}}$, where σ is the residual scatter in the bin and N_{bin} is the number of galaxies in that bin). For the ellipticity residual as a function of SNR, we see essentially unbiased reconstructed ellipticity with scatter increasing for decreasing SNR. For blendedness, we see large scatters in the mean residual for some of the bins, which suggests that a couple of outliers are driving the large deviations from mean. Finally, for the functions binned by ellipticity, we see a significant dependence on the mean residual as a function of true

¹²An important caveat is that the MSE metric improves as the size of the stamp grows bigger regardless of the quality of the reconstruction.

¹³Specifically, we are using the ‘KSB’ method within the HSM module in GALSIM (C. Hirata & U. Seljak, 2003b).

Figure 2.7: **Reconstruction metrics of SEP and Scarlet.** In this figure we show three histogram plots for each of the reconstruction metrics available in BTK: mean-squared error (MSE), peak SNR (PSNR), and structural similarity index (SSIM), as defined in Table 2.1 for the dataset of CATSIM blends detailed in Section 2.6.2. The light blue histogram in each plot corresponds to the metrics evaluated on reconstructions of galaxies from the SEP deblender, whereas the orange histogram corresponds to the SCARLET deblender. Each count of each histogram corresponds to the given metric computed from the reconstruction of either SEP or SCARLET of a given detection that was matched to a true galaxy centroid. See Section 2.6.2 for more details on this figure.

ellipticity.

We note that the galaxy blend dataset used in Figure 2.8 is very strongly blended, and, as stated above, we run SCARLET using the default settings from its basic tutorial. Therefore, this figure might not necessarily be representative of the performance of SCARLET on future survey data. Additionally, the mean of HSM shape measurements is designed to be unbiased (to some degree) only in the case of a small shear applied to a galaxy population with an isotropic distribution of ellipticities. Thus, we do not expect this residual mean to be unbiased as a function of ellipticity even in the case of no blending.

Lastly, in Figure 2.9 we show an example of a galaxy blend, the true image of each member galaxy, and the respective reconstructions from SCARLET (using the true galaxy centroid as input). We see how the reconstruction of a given individual galaxy can suffer from significant artifacts when it is highly blended or when its SNR is low.

2.7 Summary

In this paper, we have introduced BTK, an open source package that provides customizable galaxy blends, a standardized framework for deblenders, and a library of deblending metrics that enables self-consistent comparisons. We developed BTK in the context of the Blending Working Group in LSST DESC, in order to further enable the development of deblenders

Figure 2.8: **Ellipticity residuals of Scarlet deblender.** In this figure we show the HSM ellipticity residuals between the reconstructed individual galaxies from SCARLET and the true isolated galaxy images binned by signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), blendedness (B), and true measured ellipticity (e_1^{true}). The curve refers to the mean value for that bin and shaded region corresponds to the error on the mean. We emphasize that the dataset of galaxy blends used for this example is strongly blended, so that these plots might not be representative of the performance of SCARLET on future data. See Section 2.6.2 for more details on this figure.

within the collaboration. However, we anticipate that BTK will be useful to anyone interested in analyzing the systematic errors that blending induces in measurements of astronomical sources.

BTK also provides many useful subroutines for understanding galaxy blends and enables an end-to-end analysis. For instance, we provide a `match` module that provides various (customizable) ways of assigning true objects to detections for evaluating the *accuracy* of the reconstruction. This tends to be a subtle step when evaluating deblenders that is performed

Figure 2.9: **Example of Scarlet Reconstructions.** In this figure we showcase an example of a galaxy blend image (top, middle) with the centroid of each galaxy marked in red, and the true (noiseless) image of each individual galaxy (top row) along with the respective SCARLET reconstruction (bottom row). Each of the galaxies are ordered by total flux from left to right, and their positions are the same as in the original blend.

differently by different studies. Standardizing this step with its own module within BTK allows for more principled comparisons between deblenders. Additionally, BTK provides several utility functions for extracting measured quantities of individual galaxies or blends that are of interest for blending analyses. These quantities include aperture photometry flux and blendedness. Standardized functions that extract these quantities given BTK output facilitates downstream analyses.

As described in more detail in Section 2.4, BTK is an open source package hosted on GitHub, and we strive to maintain a culture of open collaboration and development. Anyone interested in galaxy blending is invited to contribute to this package. We have comprehensively tested and documented the software in preparation of the first formal release of the package, v1.0, which accompanies this publication. Finally, we hope that this package and its tutorial suite serve as a pedagogical resource for those interested in learning the basics of blending analysis

and deblenders.

The simulations generated by BTK are actively used by the LSST DESC community to test various deblenders in development (G. Merz et al., 2023; B. Biswas et al., 2024), and efforts are underway to integrate some of these deblenders into the `deblender` module within BTK. The development of BTK continues after this first release of the software and some future directions include: improving the overall realism of galaxy simulations, expanding the metrics library to allow more types of science analysis beyond those involving galaxy fluxes and shapes, and incorporating more modern galaxy catalogs such as those from the DC2 simulation (LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (LSST DESC) et al., 2021a).

Data Availability

The BlendingToolKit (BTK) is a publicly available package on GitHub at the following link: <https://github.com/LSSTDESC/BlendingToolKit>. Our software is also publicly available in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/records/13351808>. To install the software, start with the documentation at <https://lsstdesc.org/BlendingToolKit>.

2.8 Appendix: API Demonstration

In what follows we illustrate the BTK API to generate blended images, run a deblender on these, and evaluate the performance of the deblender using detection metrics within BTK. This code example is a condensed version of our “quickstart” tutorial (see Section 2.6).

```
import btk

# setup CATSIM catalog
catalog_name = "../data/input_catalog.fits"
catalog = btk.catalog.CatsimCatalog.from_file(catalog_name)

# setup survey parameters
survey = btk.survey.get_surveys("LSST")

# setup sampling function
# this function determines how to organize galaxies in catalog into blends
stamp_size = 24.0
sampling_function = btk.sampling_functions.DefaultSampling(
    catalog=catalog, max_number=5, max_mag=25.3, stamp_size=stamp_size
)
```

```

# setup generator to create batches of blends
batch_size = 100
draw_generator = btk.draw_blends.CatsimGenerator(
    catalog, sampling_function, survey, batch_size, stamp_size
)

# get batch of blends
blend_batch = next(draw_generator)

# setup deblender (we use SEP in this case)
deblender = btk.deblend.SepSingleBand(
    max_n_sources=5,
    use_band=2 # measure on 'r' band
)

# run deblender on generated blend images (all batches)
deblend_batch = deblender(blend_batch)

# setup matcher
matcher = btk.match.PixelHungarianMatcher(pixel_max_sep=5.0) # maximum
                        separation in pixels for matching

# match true and predicted catalogs
truth_catalogs = blend_batch.catalog_list
pred_catalogs = deblend_batch.catalog_list
matching = matcher(truth_catalogs, pred_catalogs) # object with matching
                        information

# compute detection performance on this batch
recall = btk.metrics.detection.Recall(batch_size)
precision = btk.metrics.detection.Precision(batch_size)
print("Recall: ", recall(matching.tp, matching.t, matching.p))
print("Precision: ", precision(matching.tp, matching.t, matching.p))

```

Survey name	Telescope	Instrument	Reference
CFHTLS	CFHT	Megacam	J. C. Cuillandre & E. Bertin (2006)
COSMOS	HST	ACS	A. M. Koekemoer et al. (2007)
DES	Victor M. Blanco	DECam	Dark Energy Survey Collaboration et al. (2016)
Euclid_VIS	Euclid	VIS	R. Laureijs et al. (2012)
HSC	Subaru	HSC	H. Aihara et al. (2018)
LSST	Simonyi	LSST camera	Ž. Ivezić et al. (2019b)

Table 2.2: Supported surveys in SURVEYCODEX and BTK for the Version 1.0 BTK release.

2.9 Appendix: SurveyCodex

BTK is made to simulate blending scenes for a variety of galaxy surveys. As such, it relies on a careful bookkeeping of the survey parameters, which are usually found scattered among various papers, websites, or code repositories, sometimes without the unit or a proper reference.

In order to improve the consistency of the simulator and prevent the occurrence of bugs in the blending scenes produced for various surveys, a subgroup of BTK developers decided to develop SURVEYCODEX¹⁴, a tiny Python library with referenced survey parameters from the current main galaxy surveys. Consistency was achieved by associating a unit to each of these parameters through the use of `astropy.units` (Astropy Collaboration et al., 2013, 2018, 2022). The available surveys in SURVEYCODEX for the 1.0 BTK release are given in Table 2.2.

SURVEYCODEX contains parameters describing the telescope (e.g., `mirror_diameter`), the camera (e.g., `pixel_scale` or `gain`), and the characteristics of each of the filters (e.g., `psf_fwhm`, `effective_wavelength`, etc.). Most values have been sourced from official documents or websites, and some like the filters `effective_wavelength` or the `zeropoint` have been computed through the `speclite`¹⁵ package that references the filter responses of most of these surveys. A description of each parameter it holds, carefully sourced or checked with specialists from each survey, can be found in the online documentation¹⁶.

SURVEYCODEX also incorporates basic utility functions, such as the computation of fluxes in electron counts from a given AB magnitude, or the mean sky level. The former is used within BTK to compute galaxy fluxes from magnitudes in the galaxy catalog and follows the usual convention

$$F = T \cdot 10^{-0.4(m-Z)}, \quad (2.1)$$

where F is the flux, T the exposure time, Z the zeropoint, and m the corresponding magnitude.

BTK includes its own `Survey` class (Section 2.5.1) that directly inherits and contains the information provided by the SURVEYCODEX library.

¹⁴<https://github.com/LSSTDESC/surveycodex>

¹⁵<https://github.com/desihub/speclite>

¹⁶<https://lsstdesc.org/surveycodex/>

CHAPTER 3

The Bayesian Light Source Separator

3.1 Preface

This chapter is reproduced in its entirety from a draft publication with the title “Simulation-Based Inference for Probabilistic Galaxy Detection and Deblending” which will be submitted for a second round of internal review in the LSST-DESC collaboration. The co-authors are: Axel Guinot, Derek Hansen, Runjing Liu, Zhe Zhao, Ziteng Pang, Camille Avestruz, and Jeffrey Regier. As the first author of this draft publication my contributions included: leading project within LSST-DESC, being one of the lead maintainers and developers of the codebase, designing and developing LSST-like image simulations to train and evaluate model, designing and implementing experiments, writing entirety of paper text, and mentoring master students (Zhe Zhao and Ziteng Pang).

This planned publication presents a probabilistic machine learning algorithm for detecting and deblending galaxies using simulation-based inference.

3.2 Abstract

Stage IV dark energy wide-field surveys such as the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) will have an unprecedented number density of galaxies, which will lead to a majority of galaxies to visually overlap with each other. This phenomenon, known as blending, is expected to be a leading source of systematic error in astronomical measurements. We present a new probabilistic method for detecting, deblending, and measuring the properties of galaxies, called the Bayesian Light Source Separator (BLISS). Given an astronomical survey image, BLISS produces a probabilistic astronomical catalog by approximating the posterior distribution of the counts, locations, and source type (star vs. galaxy) of light sources. These approximate posteriors are parametrized by convolutional neural networks. BLISS additionally includes a deterministic autoencoder deblender, which can be used to

reconstruct individual galaxies given their centroids. As a first step towards demonstrating the feasibility of BLISS for cosmological applications, we apply our method to simulated Rubin-like single-band images containing parametric galaxies and stars. We compare the detection output from BLISS to SourceExtractor and demonstrate comparable performance across a range of SNRs and blendedness. Additionally, BLISS identifies a larger fraction of low SNR and highly blended galaxies. In terms of deblending, BLISS significantly reduces the bias and scatter on measurements of flux, size, and ellipticities of simulated galaxies when the true centroids are known. Finally, we propagate the probabilistic detections from BLISS to its deblender, resulting in a per-object flux posterior. We then demonstrate that using these posteriors leads to significant improvement (up to 100%) in measured photometry compared to using only deterministic detections, especially for highly blended and faint objects. This work lays the foundation for a framework to efficiently produce and propagate uncertainty estimates from astronomical measurements to downstream cosmological analysis and mitigate a leading source of systematic errors in modern cosmological surveys. The BLISS code is open source and available online.¹

3.3 Introduction

The distribution of matter in the universe reflects the underlying cosmology describing the evolution of the universe. We can probe the matter distribution through cosmic shear, in which foreground matter coherently distorts background galaxies due to weak gravitational lensing. Cosmic shear is a powerful probe that can be used to constrain cosmology (D. Huterer, 2002; M. Kilbinger, 2015) and has been applied successfully in cosmological surveys, including the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) (E. M. Huff et al., 2014), Dark Energy Survey (DES) (L. F. Secco et al., 2022; DES Collaboration et al., 2022), Subaru Hyper Suprime-Cam (HSC) (R. Dalal et al., 2023b; X. Li et al., 2023b), and Kilo-Degree Survey (KiDS) (M. Asgari et al., 2021). Stage IV dark energy surveys, such as the Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) (LSST Science Collaboration et al., 2009; Ž. Ivezić et al., 2019a), will observe an unprecedented number density of sources, because of their increased depth compared to earlier wide-field surveys. State-of-the-art surveys like LSST and analysis of combined cosmology probes, including cosmic shear, will enable unprecedented precision and accuracy in estimates of cosmological constraints. However, cosmological constraints remain limited by systematics, which can be driven by astrophysical processes or the measurement procedure (D. H. Weinberg et al., 2013; R. Mandelbaum, 2018).

In cosmological analyses based on galaxy catalogs derived from optical surveys, a leading

¹<https://github.com/prob-ml/bliss>.

systematic is *blending* (P. Melchior et al., 2021). Blending refers to the visual overlap of light sources in astronomical images, which biases and degrades galaxy detection and measurement of their properties. For example, blending can impact the distribution of measured galaxy shapes (H. Hoekstra et al., 2017) and photometry (S. Huang et al., 2018b), the selection function of sources (J. Hartlap et al., 2011), and the estimated redshift distribution of galaxies $n(z)$ (N. MacCrann et al., 2022).

Blending already represents a significant source of systematic error on weak lensing measurements in current ground-based Stage-III surveys (e.g., N. MacCrann et al., 2022), and it is expected to become more dominant in Stage-IV surveys, given their greater depth and smaller statistical uncertainties. Simulations suggest that between 62% of galaxies in the LSST will be blended to some degree (J. Sanchez et al., 2021) and between 15% and 30% of galaxies will be unrecognized blends, in which two or more light sources are identified as one (W. A. Dawson et al., 2016; M. A. Troxel et al., 2023). Unrecognized blends can significantly impact weak lensing and cosmology measurements. Euclid Collaboration et al. (2019) finds that introducing a distribution of faint galaxies in a simulation of Euclid VIS images creates a multiplicative shear bias of at least a few times 10^{-3} . E. Nourbakhsh et al. (2021) uses simulations to forecast the effect of unrecognized blends on the derived structured growth parameter S_8 for LSST. They find that blending creates a bias greater than 2σ statistical error on this parameter.

New techniques in deblending will be needed to mitigate this important systematic. The term *deblending method*, or *deblender*, can refer to methods that perform one of the following functions on an astronomical image containing blended light sources:

1. **Detection:** Determine the number of light sources in an astronomical image and their centroids.
2. **Deblended Measurement:** For each identified source in a blend, estimate the properties of that source while attempting to remove the contribution from nearby sources.
3. **Segmentation:** For each identified source in a blend, estimate the flux contribution to each pixel in the image. From this information, individual galaxy properties, such as total flux or shape, can also be estimated.

One of the best tools to identify light profiles in an image is SourceExtractor (SExtractor) (E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996), which uses a model-independent image thresholding technique to detect objects (R. Lutz, 1980). It can also perform basic segmentation based on a multiple isophotal analysis technique (based on S. Beard et al., 1990). One major limitation of

SExtractor is that each pixel can belong to only one object. Another precursor to modern deblenders is the SDSS Photo pipeline (R. H. Lupton et al., 2005), which allows for overlap between objects and estimates the portion of flux in a pixel belonging to each object. Neither SourceExtractor nor the SDSS pipeline can account for multiband information. Deblenders developed during the last decade, like MuSCADeT (R. Joseph et al., 2016) and its successor SCARLET (P. Melchior et al., 2018), build joint nonparametric models of multiband image data. Here, the light sources are not specified with a parametrized model, such as a Sérsic fit, but with an algorithm that enforces constraints on the light distribution. In particular, SCARLET has the ability to impose an arbitrary number of constraints on each source (e.g., symmetry and monotonicity around a source’s centroid), which allow for modeling aspects such as distinct stellar populations of galaxies. More recently, deblenders based on machine learning models have demonstrated high reconstruction accuracy for simulated datasets (B. Arcelin et al., 2021; B. Biswas et al., 2024).

The majority of deblenders are deterministic and do not capture the inherent uncertainty present in estimating the properties of a blended source. To overcome this limitation, we introduce a new probabilistic deblender: the Bayesian Light Source Separator (BLISS). BLISS builds on recent ideas in deep generative modeling and variational inference (D. M. Blei et al., 2017; D. P. Kingma & M. Welling, 2019) to quantify blending uncertainty. Propagating this uncertainty to downstream cosmological analyses has the potential to mitigate blending systematics.

BLISS uses simulation-based inference (SBI) to approximate a posterior distribution of deblended galaxy properties (see Section 3.5 and Appendix 3.8). BLISS extends the approach from StarNet (R. Liu et al., 2023), which uses SBI to detect and measures stars in crowded starfields, to process images containing both stars and galaxies. Algorithmically, inference involves three encoders and a decoder as illustrated in Figure 3.1. After training these models, inference can be performed rapidly on a GPU, in just seconds for megapixel images.

In Section 3.4 we describe the image simulations we used to train and evaluate our model. Then, in Section 3.5 we describe each component of the BLISS pipeline and how these are trained via SBI. In Section 3.6 we evaluate the BLISS framework using our simulations. Each component is first evaluated separately, then in Section 3.6.6, we present results on combining the probabilistic detection and deblending capabilities of BLISS. Finally, we conclude in Section 3.7.

Figure 3.1: **BLISS inference pipeline outline**. Schematic demonstrating the procedure for detecting, deblending, and reconstructing galaxies with BLISS. The procedure starts with an astronomical image of a galaxy blend, which is split into padded tiles (orange border) that are passed through the detection encoder. The detection encoder outputs centroid locations for each detected galaxy that can be used to center each padded tile on its corresponding source. The center padded tiles are then passed to the classification and deblender encoder. Finally, the outputs of each encoder can be used to construct a full posterior catalog of the galaxy blend, and a corresponding noiseless reconstruction of the original image. For more details on each of the steps (blue circles) in this outline, see Section 3.5.5.

3.4 Simulated Images

We train and evaluate BLISS on a dataset of simulated and parametric galaxy images, which properties are chosen to be representative of LSST’s year 10 images. All our images are simulated using the GALSIM python package (B. T. P. Rowe et al., 2015).²

3.4.1 Survey Settings

Our studies target a single band, the i -band at the LSST survey pixel scale: 0.2 arcseconds. We use the same parametric point spread function (PSF) model π for all our galaxy images, which consists of an atmospheric Kolmogorov component and an optical obscured Airy pattern. We use a FWHM of 0.79 for the atmospheric component corresponding to the median zenith seeing for this filter (Ž. Ivezić et al., 2019b). We also fix the sky level b to the average expected sky level for LSST year 10. We also add Gaussian noise to our images assuming the background-dominated limit. Our setup closely resembles the simulations used in previous blending work in the context of LSST (J. Sanchez et al., 2021). The exact survey parameters are sourced from the LSST module of SURVEYCODEX.³

3.4.2 Galaxy Properties

The galaxy properties for our simulations come from a galaxy catalog produced with CatSim, an early version of an end-to-end LSST simulation framework (A. J. Connolly et al., 2014b). The galaxies simulated by this framework cover the redshift range of $0 < z < 6$ and includes a parametric model for the light profile of galaxies consisting of a bulge and disk components.⁴ The parameters of this model consist a total flux, the relative flux of each component, and the sizes and shapes of each. The two components share the same centroid and orientation. While CatSim also includes an AGN component, we have decided to not include it to keep the galaxy morphology relatively simple. The fluxes, shapes, and sizes of galaxies follow a realistic distribution designed to match LSST’s key observables, and are informed by previous SDSS observations as well as galaxy formation literature (G. Bruzual & S. Charlot, 2003; G. De Lucia et al., 2006; J. E. González et al., 2009).

²<https://github.com/GalSim-developers/GalSim>

³SURVEYCODEX is a Python library designed to archive the parameters of various surveys with references. Many of its parameters were obtained from the `WeakLensingDeblending` package (J. Sanchez et al., 2021), in some cases with corrections. This library can be found in the following URL: <https://github.com/LSSTDESC/surveycodex>

⁴The disk component corresponds to a Sérsic profile with index $n = 1$ (also known as an exponential profile) and the bulge component corresponds to a Sérsic profile with index $n = 4$ (also known as a ‘de Vaucouleurs’ profile) (J. Sérsic, 1963).

For our study, we choose the same one square degree subset of the CatSim catalog that was used in [J. Sanchez et al. \(2021\)](#). This subset of galaxies consist of approximately 850k galaxies with a limiting r-band magnitude of 28. For our datasets, we choose to impose a magnitude cut in the i -band of 27, which corresponds to galaxies with an approximate median SNR of 3. Resulting in a total of approximately 576k galaxies, which we split into three equal sets for training, validation, and testing.

3.4.3 Star Properties

Our datasets includes stars to evaluate our deblender in the context of star-galaxy blends. The star distribution and fluxes are derived from the LSST DESC Data Challenge Two (DC2) simulation catalogs ([LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration \(LSST DESC\) et al., 2021b](#)). Specifically, we use the same star catalog as previous work on performing cosmic shear measurements on LSST-like simulations ([E. S. Sheldon et al., 2023](#)). We set our star density to the average over simulated fields, while rejecting fields with density higher than 100 arcmin^{-2} . This results in a star density of 15.5 arcmin^{-2} . We apply a lower limit magnitude cut of 20 and an upper limit magnitude cut of 27 in the i -band resulting in approximately 17k stars. The former cut excludes stars with very high SNRs of over 1000. We model stars as a point source convolved by the same PSF π used by galaxies. We do not simulate saturation or other kinds of image artifacts.

3.4.4 Datasets for model training and evaluation

We create three different types of datasets to train and test our algorithms:

- **dataset-single**: This dataset consists of galaxies simulated individually and centered on a square image of size 53×53 pixels. Each galaxy is convolved with the same parametric PSF π described above. This dataset is used to train the galaxy autoencoder, which is used to create noiseless reconstructions of individual galaxies (see [Section 3.5.4](#) for details).
- **dataset-blend**: This dataset consists of galaxy and star blends on an image of size 98×98 pixels. The number of sources in each stamp is Poisson distributed using a mean density of 160 arcmin^{-2} for galaxies and 15.5 arcmin^{-2} for stars.⁵ Sources are uniformly distributed throughout the stamp, so that we do not model clustering. This dataset is used to train and evaluate the BLISS detection and classification encoders

⁵Note that these source densities correspond to the galaxies and stars drawn in the image simulation, not the density of detectable sources.

(see Section 3.5.3). It is also used to evaluate the BLISS deblender encoder (see Section 3.6.4).

- **dataset-tiles**: Uses the same properties and source density as **dataset-blend**, except that images have dimensions of 53×53 pixels and the central 5×5 region always contains exactly one galaxy whose centroid is uniformly distributed within this region. For each image of this dataset, an additional image is created of the same size and noise realization, but where the central galaxy is redrawn to be exactly centered in the image and no other sources exist outside the central 5×5 region. This dataset is used to train the BLISS deblender (see Section 3.5.4). The residual between the secondary image and the BLISS deblended reconstruction is used to evaluate the corresponding likelihood and optimize this model.
- **dataset-central**: This dataset is the same as the primary images in the **dataset-tiles**, except that images have dimensions 73×73 pixels, the central galaxy is always exactly in the middle of the image, and all sources consists of galaxies. This last dataset is used for the probabilistic detection and deblending results in Section 3.6.6. It was constructed to contain smaller images than **dataset-blend** and contain no stars for efficiency and simplicity purposes respectively.

The first two datasets are divided into training, validation, and testing. For **dataset-single**, we simulate every galaxy in our magnitude-selected sample of CatSim catalog and divide them three equal parts. For **dataset-blend**, we create three sets of 10k, 5k, and 15k blends by sampling with replacement from the corresponding training, validation, and testing galaxy catalogs in **dataset-single**. Star magnitudes are sampled with replacement from the DC2 star catalog across the three datasets. For **dataset-tiles**, only a training and validation set of 50k and 10k images are created using the corresponding galaxies as **dataset-blend**. Finally, for **dataset-central**, only a testing set of 20k images is created using the corresponding testing galaxies.

3.5 Method

BLISS infers a posterior distribution of light source properties from a given astronomical image. Our procedure decomposes the inference problem by operating in parallel on overlapping image subregions that we call padded tiles (Figure 3.1, Section 3.5.1). We train a set of three neural networks that take these padded tiles as input and are trained using amortized variational inference (L. Ambrogioni et al., 2019). These networks or *encoders* return the parameters

of distributions characterizing the light source properties in each tile (Section 3.5.2). The detection and classification encoders return posterior distributions on counts, centroid location, and type (star vs. galaxy) for each tile (Section 3.5.3). The deblender encoder outputs latent galaxy representations that can be used to obtain noiseless reconstructions of deblended galaxy images (Section 3.5.4). Once all encoders are trained, the full BLISS inference pipeline can be applied on astronomical images of any size. This pipeline outputs joint samples of light sources’ counts, centroids, classification, and galaxy properties (Section 3.5.5).⁶

3.5.1 Tiling

The tiling mechanism within BLISS allows for efficient inference of probabilistic catalogs from astronomical images. The tiling procedure used by BLISS encoders exploits the fact that dependence among well-separated light sources in a given image can be ignored in the variational distribution when measuring their properties for cataloging. We split images containing astronomical light sources into overlapping square subregions of the image that we call *padded tiles*; these are input independently to BLISS’s encoders. We constrain each encoder to output a prediction only for the source whose centroid lies in a small, central square region of each padded tile.⁷ Hereafter we will refer to this region as a *tile*. We illustrate the tiling mechanism with the orange (padded tiles) and blue (tiles) squares in steps 1. and 2. of the schematic of BLISS predictions, Figure 3.1.

As mentioned above, BLISS, by construction, outputs the prediction for at most one source that lies in a given tile. This means that if the centroid of two or more sources are present in a tile, BLISS will always output an incomplete catalog for that tile. In particular, if at least one of the sources in the tile is detectable, BLISS will output a set of properties corresponding to a single ‘hybrid’ source.⁸ We partially mitigate this by choosing small tiles of size 5 pixels, which leads to a low probability that more than one source centroid falls in any given tile. For our source (galaxy and star) density of $175.5 \text{ arcmin}^{-2}$, this probability is approximately 0.0012. Importantly, in the majority of these occurrences one of the sources involved will be below the detection threshold.

We emphasize that, despite this limitation, the BLISS framework can still accommodate the vast majority of galaxy blends. As illustrated in Figure 3.1, both padded tiles and tiles will contain flux from multiple light sources when dividing the image of a blend, even if their

⁶Samples of galaxy properties produced with our current approach do not fully capture the uncertainty in galaxy properties as that would require a probabilistic deblender encoder, which we defer to future work. See Section 3.5.4 for details.

⁷Note that, by construction, the centroid of a given star or galaxy is contained in a unique tile. That means that there is never double-counting of sources by BLISS.

⁸At training time, BLISS always targets the properties of the brightest source present in a tile.

centroids land in different tiles. BLISS encoders explicitly account for this in their training procedure. The encoders are trained to remove the contributions from light sources in nearby tiles when outputting the properties of a source in a particular tile. For all encoders, the padded tile size must be large enough to capture the morphological information of galaxies relevant to the corresponding tile. For our datasets, we find 53 pixels to be sufficiently large.

3.5.2 Variational inference

We adopt the framework of variational inference to train the BLISS encoders to approximate the posterior distribution of light source parameters. Specifically, we approximate the true posterior $P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X})$ of a light source catalog \mathcal{Z} given an astronomical image \mathcal{X} with an approximate posterior distribution, known as the *variational distribution* (see Appendix 3.9 for more details on the Bayesian approach to cataloging). We choose our variational distribution to factorize over tiles:

$$Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}) = \prod_{t=1}^T Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}_t), \quad (3.1)$$

where \mathcal{Z}_t is the catalog at tile t . We implicitly condition each product factor on \mathcal{X}_t , the padded tile corresponding to tile t . The sub-index ϕ corresponds to the weights of the neural network that takes as input a padded tile \mathcal{X}_t and outputs the parameters characterizing the distribution $Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}_t)$ for tile t .

The factorization over tiles used in Equation 3.1 simplifies the requirements of our encoders and allows us to account for the variable number of light sources in a given image. The fitted variational distribution is a good approximation of the posterior distribution if the tiles are small and the padded tiles are large. In this scenario, the number of sources in each tile will likely be 0 or 1, and each padded tile will contain enough information to characterize the source whose centroid lies in the tile, as described in Section 3.5.1.

In our approximation, the inferred tile catalog \mathcal{Z}_t contains the light source properties $\{n_t, \ell_t, b_t, z_t\}$, where $n_t \in \{0, 1\}$ is the number of sources whose centroid lies in the tile, $\ell_t \in [0, 1]^2$ is the centroid position of the tile’s source in units of tile length, $b_t \in \{0, 1\}$ is the classification of the source as a galaxy ($b_t = 1$) or star ($b_t = 0$), and $z_t \in \mathbb{R}^8$ is a latent vector characterizing galaxy morphology and brightness (for more details, see Section 3.5.4).

We explicitly define the variational distribution $Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}_t) = Q_\phi(n_t, \ell_t, b_t, z_t)$ for each tile t

to be as follows:

$$n_t \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\omega_{n,t}) \quad (3.2)$$

$$[b_t \mid n_t = 1] \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\omega_{g,t}) \quad (3.3)$$

$$[\boldsymbol{\ell}_t \mid n_t = 1] \sim \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\ell,t}, \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\nu}_{\ell,t})) \quad (3.4)$$

$$[z_t \mid n_t = 1, b_t = 1] \sim \delta_{\zeta_t} \quad (3.5)$$

where $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ is used to denote a diagonal matrix, $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$ denotes a normal distribution, and δ_x represents a delta function centered at x . We define the distributional parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_t$ are:

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_t = \{\omega_{n,t}, \omega_{g,t}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\ell,t}, \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\nu}_{\ell,t}), \zeta_t\}. \quad (3.6)$$

These distributional parameters are the output of a neural networks with weights $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ applied to a given padded tile \mathcal{X}_t . These weights are the variational parameters. We chose the variational distribution of locations to be a normal distribution for computational simplicity. Samples from this distribution that fall out of a given tile are considered non-detections in this tile. Additionally, we chose the variational distribution for the latent galaxy representation z_t to be a delta function. This implies that we only return point estimates for this quantity with no associated uncertainty.

Critically, our method is *amortized* (D. P. Kingma & M. Welling, 2013; D. J. Rezende et al., 2014), which means that $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ is shared among tiles (i.e., no t sub-index in $\boldsymbol{\phi}$); a single set of neural networks with weights $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ is used for any padded tile of any image. If our method were not amortized, as in more classical variational inference approaches (D. M. Blei et al., 2017), we would need to run an iterative optimization procedure for each tile, which would make our procedure highly inefficient. Amortization allows us to train a single set of encoders only once, which greatly speeds up inference for large datasets.

In the next two sections, we describe the numerical optimization procedure that we use to obtain the neural network weights $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ that determine our variational distribution Q_ϕ for any given padded tile \mathcal{X}_t . We describe the procedure to optimize the detection and classification encoders in Section 3.5.3, and the procedure for training the deblender encoder in Section 3.5.4.

3.5.3 Detection and classification encoders

BLISS uses Forward Amortized Variational Inference (FAVI) (L. Ambrogioni et al., 2019) to perform posterior inference for light source properties other than galaxy parameters. Two of the BLISS encoders are optimized using FAVI: the detection and classification encoders. As

presented in Equations 3.2 through 3.4, the detection encoder outputs the parameter of a Bernoulli distribution describing whether a source is present in a given tile. It also outputs two parameters describing where the source centroid is within the tile. The classification encoder outputs the parameter that describes whether a source is a star or a galaxy.

We now describe our procedure for training these encoders. In this section, we will refer to the corresponding light source parameters captured by the detection and classification encoders as \mathcal{Z} , where \mathcal{Z} is specific to a given image with T tiles:

$$\mathcal{Z} \equiv \{n_t, b_t, \ell_t\}_{t=1}^T. \quad (3.7)$$

To find the optimal weights ϕ for our neural networks, we minimize

$$L(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X}) \parallel Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z})). \quad (3.8)$$

Here $D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q)$ denotes the KL divergence between distributions P and Q , defined as

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q) \equiv \int P(z) \log \left(\frac{Q(z)}{P(z)} \right) dz. \quad (3.9)$$

The KL divergence quantifies the difference between two distributions. In particular, if two distributions P and Q are equal in law, then $D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q) = 0$. Using a specific factorization for the variational distribution and dropping terms that do not depend on ϕ , we can rewrite the loss function from Equation 3.8 as

$$\begin{aligned} L(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z} \sim P(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z})} & \sum_{t=1}^T \log Q_\phi(n_t) + \log Q_\phi(\ell_t | n_t) \\ & + \log Q_\phi(b_t | n_t, \ell_t). \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

For more details on the full derivation see Appendix 3.10. We take Equation 3.10 as our loss function to train our detection and classification encoders, together parameterized by neural network weights ϕ . The networks output a subset of the distributional parameters θ_t for each tile.

Note that the evaluation on padded tiles implicitly treats the problem as independent sub-problems in that the model outputs independent posterior approximations for each tile. However, the inputs to the encoders are padded tiles, which are not independent of each other. The padding in a given padded tile includes pixels also contained in nearby padded tiles, which means that each encoder uses the information from nearby light sources when inferring light source parameters in a given tile.

In practice, we evaluate the loss function in Equation 3.10 with the following steps:

1. Randomly sample a mini-batch of size B from our training dataset of galaxy and star blends `dataset-blend` (Section 3.4), with images $\{\mathcal{X}_b\}_{b=1}^B$ and full catalogs $\{\mathcal{Z}_b\}_{b=1}^B$.
2. Divide each image into padded tiles $\{\mathcal{X}_{b,t}\}_{t=1}^T$, and obtain the corresponding tile catalogs $\{\mathcal{Z}_{b,t}\}_{t=1}^T$ from the full catalog.⁹
3. Use a neural network with weights ϕ that takes the padded tiles as input and outputs distributional parameters θ_t , which defines the variational distributions of each tile.
4. For each variational distribution on each tile, evaluate its density on the corresponding true source parameters of that tile. The sum of relevant (see below) variational distributions corresponds to the loss of each tile.
5. Sum the loss over all tiles of each image in each mini-batch.
6. Average the loss over the mini-batch examples to evaluate the expectation. The gradient of this loss is propagated to update ϕ .

We decide to train two independent neural networks corresponding to the detection and classification encoder.

First, the neural network in the detection encoder takes padded tiles as inputs and outputs the variational parameters corresponding to source counts and centroids. On each tile t , this encoder outputs the probability of a source being present $\omega_{n,t}$ and the mean and diagonal covariance for its centroid: $\mu_{\ell,t}, \text{diag}(\nu_{\ell,t})$. These distributional parameters define a variational distribution density which is then evaluated on true source counts and centroids to obtain the loss. Training this encoder only uses the first two terms of Equation 3.10.¹⁰

Next, the classification encoder outputs $\omega_{g,t}$ for each padded tile to parameterize the Bernoulli distribution in Equation 3.3. Only the last term of the loss function (Equation 3.10), $\log Q_\phi(b_t|n_t, \ell_t)$, is used for training this encoder. The training of the classification encoder is similar to that of the detection encoder, but with one difference: the inputs to the classification encoder are padded tiles that have been centered (within a pixel) on the source in the tile by cropping pixels around its true centroid location. This is illustrated by the image on the right in Figure 3.1. We found that this centering step increased the

⁹In the case that more than one source centroid is present in a given tile of an image, we only keep the brightest source present in that tile for the corresponding tile catalog. This ensures our training procedure is well-defined, but might bias our algorithm, as discussed in Section 3.5.1.

¹⁰For all encoders, tiles not containing a light source do not contribute to their loss function, except when outputting detection probability via the term $Q_\phi(n_t)$.

performance of the classification encoder. Tiles that do not contain sources ($n_t = 0$) do not contribute to the loss function of the classification encoder.

Finally, we optimize both neural networks with a stochastic gradient procedure using Adam. We use a learning rate of 10^{-4} and otherwise default parameters of the PyTorch implementation (A. Paszke et al., 2019). We use mini-batches of size 32 from `dataset-blend`.¹¹ The neural network for these encoders follows a standard ResNet-like architecture (K. He et al., 2016) consisting of convolutions, batch norms, dropouts, and ReLUs.¹²

3.5.4 Deblender Encoder

We train the last of the BLISS encoders, the deblender encoder, using a two-step approach which is similar to the procedure in B. Arcelin et al. (2021).

First, we train an autoencoder (AE) model to capture a nonparametric description of the individual galaxies we simulate with GALSIM. Our AE consists of two pairs of neural networks: an encoder and a decoder. The encoder neural network summarizes the noisy image of an isolated and centered galaxy \mathbf{x} with a latent representation $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^8$, which captures both the flux and morphology of the noiseless galaxy image. The decoder takes this latent representation as input and outputs a noiseless reconstruction $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ of the original galaxy image.

We train our AE using the negative log-likelihood between the noisy single-centered galaxy image \mathbf{x} and its reconstruction $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ under the Gaussian approximation to the Poisson distribution:

$$L(\mathbf{x}, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}) = - \sum_{p \in \text{pixels}} \log \mathcal{N}(x_p; \tilde{x}_p, \tilde{x}_p), \quad (3.11)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(x; \mu, \sigma^2)$ refers to evaluating the density of a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$ at the point x . The AE is trained on individual galaxy images in batches of size 128 from the `dataset-single` dataset (Section 3.4) using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-5} and otherwise default parameters.

Next, we train the deblender encoder. The deblender encoder is functionally similar and uses the same neural network architecture as the encoder part of the galaxy model AE. The primary difference between the two is that the deblender encoder is trained on blended galaxies, and thus learns to ignore the flux from galaxies overlapping with the target one. The deblender encoder targets the same loss function as the AE (Equation 3.11), and training is performed using samples from `dataset-tiles` (Section 3.4). First, images with a shifted

¹¹We chose this combination of parameters because they lead to a smooth and rapid decline in the loss function curve during training. Their hyperparameters of other encoders in this work are chosen similarly.

¹²The exact implementation of our neural network can also be found in our public repository: <https://github.com/prob-ml/bliss>.

central galaxy are centered (within a pixel) at the true centroid by cropping surrounding pixels resulting in images with size 49×49 . This centered images are passed to the encoder, which produces a latent vector \mathbf{z}_t capturing the properties of the central galaxy in this image. Then, we apply the decoder model (with frozen weights) from the trained AE to create a reconstruction $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ from each of these encodings. The galaxy centroid in these reconstructions are exactly centered in the image. Finally, we compute the loss in Equation 3.11 by using the additional redrawn, centered image included in `dataset-tiles` as the target for the reconstruction $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$.

We train the deblender encoder using the Adam with a learning rate of 10^{-4} on batches of blends from the `dataset-blend` dataset of size 128. The network architecture is the same as the AE and they both consist of a series of convolutions, leaky ReLUs (J. Xu et al., 2020), and fully connected feedforward layers. Once trained, our deblender encoder can output a latent representation of each detected galaxy in an image.

Finally, we emphasize the distinct statistical approaches to detection/classification and inferring galaxy representations. In the detection and classification encoders, every light source parameter has an associated variational distribution that captures the uncertainty in that parameter. In contrast, the deblender encoder returns only point estimates with no uncertainty. Despite this, we can construct posterior catalogs on galaxy properties that capture detection uncertainty by using samples from the detection encoder as inputs to the deblender encoder. This procedure will be demonstrated in Section 3.6.6. Future work will use a VAE (as in B. Arcelin et al., 2021) to capture the full uncertainty in the properties of blended galaxies.

3.5.5 Inference pipeline

Once all the encoders have been trained, BLISS can be used to produce samples of galaxy catalogs for an astronomical image of any size containing galaxy and star blends. The full inference procedure can be summarized as follows, with each step corresponding to a blue numbered circle in Figure 3.1:

- (1) We start with a given noisy image containing a galaxy blend. In this work, we use GALSIM to simulate light sources, as described in Section 3.4.
- (2) We divide this image into padded tiles, which are image subregions indicated with the orange outline. These padded tiles consist of tiles (blue square) and border padding (pixels between blue and orange outline). Each encoder in the pipeline makes predictions on each padded tile. A given encoder uses information from the entire padded tile to

make predictions for galaxies or stars whose centroid lies in the tile. We detail the tiling procedure in Section 3.5.1.

- (3) We first input each padded tile to the detection encoder, which outputs the parameters of a variational distribution of the candidate source in each tile. We then sample a set of counts and centroid locations for each tile from its corresponding distribution. Note that the detection encoder outputs the parameters for at most one source per tile, as BLISS assumes that tiles are chosen to be small enough to likely contain at most one source centroid. See Section 3.5.3 for details of the detection encoder.
- (4) We center each padded tile (within a pixel, via cropping) on the corresponding sampled centroid.
- (5) We input the centered padded tiles to the classification encoder and the deblender encoder. For star-galaxy classification, we sample binary indicators from the classification encoder. We then output latent galaxy variables using the deblender encoder on each tile containing a galaxy. See Sections 3.5.3 and 3.5.4 for more details on the classification and deblender encoders, respectively.
- (6) Finally, we can combine the outputs of the three encoders into a galaxy catalog. The decoder from the AE can be used to create a reconstruction of the entire galaxy blend. Measurements of galaxy properties (e.g., flux or shape) can be performed using these reconstructions.

3.6 Results

We evaluate the performance of BLISS on galaxy blend images rendered with GALSIM using the set of 15k blends from the test part of `dataset-blend` described in Section 3.4. First, we define the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and blendedness of galaxies in Section 3.6.1. Next, we evaluate each of the three encoders separately in Sections 3.6.2 through 3.6.4. Then, in Section 3.6.5 we explore the uncertainty predictions of our encoders in a controlled setting where we vary the distance between a pair of galaxies. Finally, in Section 3.6.6 we explore how the probabilistic output of BLISS can be used to improve aperture flux recovery.

3.6.1 SNR and Blendedness

In several of our experiments, we analyze the performance of our models as a function of the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and the blendedness B of galaxies. We define these quantities below.

We use the aperture photometry module in SEP (K. Barbary, 2016) to measure the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) defined as:

$$\sqrt{\sum_{p \in \text{aperture}} \frac{I_p^2}{\sigma_{n,p}^2}}, \quad (3.12)$$

where I_p is the intensity of the image in pixel p , and $\sigma_{n,p}^2$ is the sky noise variance. We assign an SNR to individual galaxies. When galaxies are blended, we draw each member individually and use this equation to compute their SNR. We use an aperture radius of 5 pixels throughout our experiments.

We define blendedness using the definition in P. Melchior et al. (2018). For a galaxy with intensity \mathbf{I} , *blendedness* is

$$B = 1 - \frac{\langle \mathbf{I}, \mathbf{I} \rangle}{\langle \mathbf{I}, \mathbf{I}_{\text{total}} \rangle}, \quad (3.13)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_{\text{total}}$ is the total intensity from every source in the blend and, for intensities $\mathbf{I}_1, \mathbf{I}_2$,

$$\langle \mathbf{I}_1, \mathbf{I}_2 \rangle = \sum_{p \in \text{pixels}} I_{1,p} I_{2,p}. \quad (3.14)$$

By construction, $B \in [0, 1]$, with $B = 0$ corresponding to an isolated galaxy and $B = 1$ to a completely overlapping and subdominant galaxy. Galaxies with higher blendedness will tend to be more difficult to detect and measure than galaxies with low blendedness.

3.6.2 Detection evaluation

We evaluate the trained detection encoder applied on galaxy blends and compare it with SEP, a version of SourceExtractor written in Python (E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996; K. Barbary, 2016). Specifically, we look at the precision, recall, and F_1 score of the detection encoder using different probability thresholds for what constitutes a detection. For each tile with detection probability larger than a given threshold, we choose the centroid prediction to be the mean of the predicted centroid posterior on that tile.

We first define *matched detections* as detections that are within 2 pixels from a true centroid **and** assigned a unique true centroid using the Hungarian matching algorithm (H. W. Kuhn, 1955b) (available as the Scipy function `linear_sum_assignment`). This is a bipartite graph matching algorithm which minimizes a certain cost function on the graph edges. The cost function is:

$$\sum_i \sum_j C_{i,j} X_{i,j}, \quad (3.15)$$

where the sum is over all possible matches (between true source i and detection j) and $X_{i,j}$ is 1 if i is matched to j and 0 otherwise. Let $r_{i,j}$ be the euclidean pixel distance between the centroid of source i and the detection j , then we define $C_{i,j}$ as:

$$C_{i,j} = \begin{cases} r_{i,j} & \text{if } r_{i,j} < 2 \text{ pixels} \\ \infty & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.16)$$

Next, we define the *true SNR* of a galaxy as the SNR computed using the true centroid on an image redrawn with the same pixel-noise as the original blended image, but where only this galaxy is present. Similarly, we define the *detected SNR* for a given detection as the SNR computed on this location in the given blended image via aperture photometry.

Finally, for a given SNR bin, precision is defined as the number of matched detections whose detected SNR lies within this bin divided by the number of detections whose detected SNR is in the bin. Similarly, recall is the number of matched detections where the matched galaxy’s true SNR lies within this bin divided by the number of galaxies whose true SNR lies in the bin. The F_1 score is defined as:

$$F_1 = 2(\text{precision}^{-1} + \text{recall}^{-1})^{-1} \quad (3.17)$$

on a per-bin basis.

Figure 3.2 shows the precision, recall and F_1 score on shared SNR bins of the detection encoder using different probability thresholds (color gradients, blue to red) and SEP (dashed black). The SNR bins are equally-log-spaced between 3 and 1000. In the precision plot, we see that the redder curves have higher overall precision than the bluer curves for the detection encoder. This is expected as a higher probability threshold corresponds to a more strict requirement on the confidence of the BLISS model on detections. In comparison, SEP appears to higher precision than most BLISS probability thresholds across all SNR bins. In the recall plot, we observe the opposite trend. A lower probability threshold for the BLISS detection model corresponds to higher recall as more true objects are found. SEP has relatively higher recall than the detection encoder except for the low (< 10) SNR bins. Finally, the F_1 score shows that SEP has the most comparable performance to the detection encoder at the fiducial probability threshold (0.5).

Next, in Figure 3.3 we show the recall of the detection encoder and SEP as a function of blendedness.¹³ The blendedness is computed using the true noiseless image of each galaxy, and the recall is defined analogously for blendedness bins as for true SNR bins. In this case,

¹³We do not include the other two metrics for blendedness as there is not an obvious definition for “detected blendedness”.

Figure 3.2: **Detection performance as a function of SNR.** In this figure we present the performance of the trained BLISS detection encoder using different probability thresholds (color gradient, blue to red) and SEP (dashed, black) on our testing set of galaxy blends. We show the precision, recall, and F_1 score in the same equally-log-spaced SNR bins. For more details on this figure see Section 3.6.2.

we use bins containing the same number of sources. We see that the recall of the detection encoder increases as the probability threshold decreases, as in the previous figure. In this case, the recall of the nominal model (threshold of 0.5) slightly outperforms SEP in finding galaxies.

Overall, these results show that BLISS has the potential to recover a larger number of noisy and blended sources than SourceExtractor, while being able to achieve comparable overall performance over a wide SNR range (at certain probability thresholds).

3.6.3 Classification evaluation

In this section we evaluate the next encoder in the BLISS pipeline, the binary encoder, independently from the detection encoder. We provide the true counts and centroids of light sources to the binary encoder when processing images.

In Figure 3.4, we show the probability of a given light source being a galaxy outputted by the binary encoder as a function of the true SNR of the source (as defined in Section 3.6.2). We see that as for high SNRs of above about 100, the model is very confident about the source’s type, as expected. As the SNR decreases, the model becomes more uncertain about the classification for any given light source and we see a vertical strip in the figure with a mix of purple and green dots. As the SNR decreases even further, at about 10 SNR, we see that the model classifies with high confidence a large portion of stars as galaxies. This occurs because the model defaults to the prior in the case of low SNR sources. Given that the vast majority of sources used during training were galaxies, the model tends to classify noisy stars

Figure 3.3: **Completeness as a function of blendedness.** This figure shows the fraction of detected true objects (i.e., recall) as a function of their blendedness for SEP and the BLISS detection encoder. The BLISS detection encoder’s recall for different probability thresholds is shown in the blue to red gradient curves, while SEP’s is shown with a black dashed curve. See Section 3.6.2 for details.

as galaxies.

We additionally use the precision, recall and F_1 -Score metrics as in the previous section to evaluate the encoder. These metrics are computed differently for this classification context. First, we split these metrics into a galaxy and a star version as shown in Figure 3.5. This is helpful as `dataset-blend` is highly unbalanced with a much larger number of galaxies than stars. We say that the model classifies a light source as a galaxy if the output probability of the source being a galaxy is > 0.5 and a star otherwise. The precision for galaxies (stars) in this context corresponds to the number of correctly classified galaxies (stars) divided by the total number of sources the model classified as galaxies. The recall for galaxies (stars) is then the number of correctly classified galaxies (stars) divided by the total number of galaxies. The F_1 score is computed as in Equation 3.17. These quantities are binned and plotted in Figure 3.5 based on the true SNR of the sources. We exclude the dimmest sources with $\text{SNR} < 10$ from this figure. In the left plot, we can see that all of the galaxy metrics are above 90% for all relevant SNRs. This is expected given our highly unbalanced dataset.

Figure 3.4: **Classification probability as a function of SNR.** In this figure we show the classification probability of a given source being a galaxy as a function of true SNR, for every source in the testing `dataset-blend`. This probability is the output from the binary encoder conditioned on true counts and centroids of every source, as in Figure 3.5. Each dot is color coded with its true galaxy (green) or star (purple) classification. For more details on this figure, see Section 3.6.3.

The precision decreases rapidly from around 98% to 93% at the SNR roughly corresponding to the vertical strip in Figure 3.4. The recall increases as the SNR decreases as the model defaults to the prior and classifies most objects as galaxies. Meanwhile, we see that all the star metrics are monotonic as a function of SNR. This is consistent with Figure 3.4 as the purple dots consistently move from the top to the bottom as the SNR increases.

Our results shows our model becomes more uncertain when classifying low SNR sources, as expected. However, for very low SNR the prior dominates and a significant number of stars are classified as galaxies with high confidence. This might represent a problem for lensing applications as star contamination in the galaxy sample could bias shear measurements. One way to make progress could be to incorporate additional prior information into the network that takes into account the model of stars (i.e., the PSF). For example, using the *spread model* estimator (e.g., J. J. Mohr et al., 2012).

3.6.4 Deblending evaluation

In this section, we evaluate the deblender encoder independently from the rest of the encoders. We again use `dataset-blend` and investigate the accuracy of the corresponding galaxy reconstructions. We evaluate fluxes measured with aperture photometry, using an aperture of

Figure 3.5: **Classification performance as a function of SNR for galaxies and stars.** This figure shows the precision (green), recall (purple), and F_1 score (orange) as a function of true SNR obtained by applying the binary encoder to our testing `dataset-blend` of galaxies and star blends. The SNR bins in each case are chosen so that there are an equal number of light sources on each bin. We condition the binary encoder on the true counts and centroids of every source in this dataset. For more details on this figure, see Section 3.6.3.

5 pixels. The size and ellipticities come from the adaptive moments routine in GALSIM.¹⁴ The size is defined as $T \equiv |\det \mathbf{M}|^{1/4}$, where \mathbf{M} is the second-moments matrix. The ellipticity uses the distortion (ϵ) definition from GALSIM.¹⁵ Measurements are made on *residual images* of each galaxy obtained as follows:

1. For each galaxy in each blend of `dataset-blend`, we use the deblender encoder to encode this galaxy conditioned on its true centroid. The decoder part of the autoencoder then uses this encoding to create a reconstruction of this galaxy (Section 3.5.4).
2. Each individually reconstructed galaxy from the decoder is centered on a stamp the size of a padded tile. We use GALSIM to interpolate¹⁶ each galaxy to its true location within the padded tile. These padded tiles can be used to create a full reconstruction of the galaxy blend in the original image.
3. For each galaxy in a given blend, we use these interpolated reconstructed images to

¹⁴We use the `galsim.hsm` module: https://galsim-developers.github.io/GalSim/_build/html/hsm.html

¹⁵The definition can be found in: https://galsim-developers.github.io/GalSim/_build/html/shear.html

¹⁶We use the default settings for interpolating on GALSIM, which uses a ‘quintic’ 2D interpolation for images. See this page for details: https://galsim-developers.github.io/GalSim/_build/html/interpolant.html

subtract the contribution from all galaxies in the blend except this one. We also remove the contributions from sources in the padding and from all stars. These are the residual images for every galaxy in the dataset.

4. Finally, we perform aperture photometry flux measurements and moments as described above using the true centroid of each galaxy as input.

We use these residual images for measurements rather than the reconstructed images directly, because these contain unphysical artifacts in the tails of galaxies, which can have a large effect on measured moments. See Section 3.6.5 for additional discussion.

We plot the residuals for fluxes, sizes, and ellipticities obtained using this procedure on every galaxy in our dataset as a function of SNR and blendedness in Figures 3.6 and 3.7 (purple curves). The green curves (“No deblending”) show these measurements on the same images using true centroids, but no galaxy reconstructions are subtracted before the measurement. All stars and other light sources in the image padding are still subtracted. Finally, the true values of every galaxy measurement are computed by subtracting every other source in the image using the true individual images. We see from this figure that the scatter in measurements of all quantities is significantly reduced from the deblending. In the case of the flux and size measurements, we see that deblending unbias the residual across all SNR and blendedness bins. In the case of no-deblending, we see that the flux and sizes medians are always positive and there is no negative scatter. This is expected, as the flux and size measurements of galaxies can only get larger when flux is added to the image.

This figure shows that our deblender is overall capable of reconstructing galaxies accurately, but the biases and errors shown here will be too optimistic as it ignores detection effects. We investigate the impact of detection on flux and moments measurements in upcoming sections.

3.6.5 Example probabilistic output as a function of distance

In this section, we present probabilistic output of BLISS on a pair of example galaxies with varying separation. We explore how the uncertainty that BLISS produces for counts, locations, and fluxes are related to physical aspects of the galaxy configuration.

Our setup consists of two elliptical exponential galaxies with SNRs of approximately 120 and 70 with a variable separation between them as shown in Figure 3.8.¹⁷ The left galaxy, denoted “Galaxy 1” and labeled with a green 1 in this figure, is fixed at the center of the image. The right galaxy, denoted “Galaxy 2” and labeled with a purple 2 in this figure, shifts horizontally between 0 and 20 pixels from the center of the image in intervals of 0.1 pixels.

¹⁷These relatively high SNR galaxies are chosen to isolate the impacts of blending in this example from the impacts of missed detections of low SNR sources.

Figure 3.6: **Residual flux and size measurements as a function of SNR and blendedness.** In this plot we show the median residual flux and size measurements on galaxy blended images using true galaxy centroids. The flux (f) measurement is performed via aperture photometry with an aperture of size 5 pixels. The size ($T = |\det \mathbf{M}|^{1/4}$) The green color curves corresponds to the measurements with no deblending performed, but using the true centroid of each galaxy. The purple color curves use the reconstructed models from the deblender encoder to remove every other galaxy in the image before performing the measurement. The shaded regions correspond to quantiles of the 1σ deviation from a Gaussian distribution (i.e., 0.159 and 0.841 respectively). For more details on this figure, see Section 3.6.4.

These results in 200 images each of size 103×103 where the same gaussian noise realization is added to all images. The specific properties of these galaxies can be found in Table 3.1.

In Figure 3.8, we show the image of the galaxy pair at three different separations (5, 10, and 15 pixels) in the first column. The second column contains the noiseless reconstruction from the BLISS deblender encoder (using the predicted centroid as input), and the third column shows the residual image. We also overplot the true centroids, and the predictions from SEP and the BLISS detection encoder (using the centroid posterior mean). The figure

Figure 3.7: **Residual ellipticity measurements as a function of SNR and blendedness.** This figure is the same as Figure 3.6 except that the residual ellipticities are reported. The ellipticities (e_1 , e_2) are measured using the GALSIM adaptive moments routine. For more details on this figure, see Section 3.6.4.

shows that the detection encoder correctly identifies the total number of galaxies even at small pixel separations when they visually look like a single blob. As the separation between the objects increases, we see that accuracy of detections increases, as expected. The SEP settings used in this Figure are the same ones as in Section 3.6.2 and showed in Table 3.2.

Next, in terms of reconstructions and residuals, the third column shows image residuals improving as the separations increase. At the lowest separations, BLISS over-predicts the flux from both galaxies leading to a large positive residual. This might be because the deblender encoder’s reconstructions for each tile are done independently, which means that there is no constrain on preserving the total flux of the blend. So that, when galaxies are severely blended, the deblender includes the flux of neighbors in each independent prediction. Finally, we note that all noiseless reconstructions in the second column have noticeable non-physical features especially in the tails of galaxies. The deblender encoder does not impose any particular galaxy model or physical constraints on its reconstructions, which could explain

Property	Galaxy 1	Galaxy 2
f	2×10^5	1×10^5
SNR	120	70
a_d	1.5	1.0
q_d	0.7	0.7
β	$\pi/4$	$6\pi/4$

Table 3.1: **Galaxy properties of pair blend.** The true galaxy parameters of the galaxies in the pair blend from Figure 3.8. Both galaxies are purely comprised by a disk (exponential) component. The symbols are as follows: f is the flux, a_d is the semi-major axis of the disk, and q_d is the ratio of the semi-major and semi-minor axes, and β is the inclination angle.

these unphysical features. This effect does not impact our results significantly since we perform measurements only on images with noise added (see Section 3.6.4), which buries these features. Both of these observations suggest avenues for future work in the deblender (Section 3.7).

Next in Figure 3.9, we show the detection probability as a function of separation between the two galaxies. The detection probability for each galaxy is obtained by taking the output of the detection encoder for the tile containing the true centroid of that galaxy. We see that the detection probability for Galaxy 1 remains relatively stable and does not drop below approximately 0.75. However, the detection probability of Galaxy 2 varies in more interesting ways. There are peaks and valleys roughly corresponding with the center and boundaries (dashed lines) of tiles respectively. The second galaxy’s detection probability can drop below 0.5 depending on how close its centroid is to the tile boundary, which is an undesirable artifact of our tiling approach. We choose to defer addressing this issue to future work. However, the overall probability curve increases as the two sources become more separated, as expected. In Appendix 3.12 we also evaluate the quality of the centroid prediction from the detection encoder on these images.

In the next section, we jointly evaluate the detection and deblender encoder in the context of flux measurements using considerations from this section.

3.6.6 Joint Detection and Deblending uncertainty

One advantage of BLISS over traditional approaches is the opportunity to combine probabilistic detection and deblending of sources. BLISS could be particularly powerful in the context of unrecognized blends, where total number of sources is ambiguous. In this section,

Figure 3.8: Image residuals and detections on galaxy pairs at three separations.

In this plot we show the pair of example galaxies used throughout Section 3.6.5 at three different separations: 5, 10, and 15 pixels. The galaxy on the left (labeled with “1”, in green) is fixed at the center of the image. The galaxy on the right (labeled with “2”, in purple) is shifted horizontally at different separations from Galaxy 1. In the first column, we see the true noisy image at each separation with the true centroid of each galaxy in red and the predicted centroid from BLISS in blue. The SEP prediction for centroids is also shown with an orange circle as a reference. The second column shows the noiseless reconstruction from BLISS with the same centroids plotted as in the first column. The last column shows the residual image.

Figure 3.9: **Detection probability of each galaxy as a function of separation.** This plot shows the detection probability that BLISS assigns to the tile containing Galaxy 1 (green) and 2 (purple) as a function of the separation between them (as described in Figure 3.8). The dashed vertical lines correspond to the separations at which Galaxy 2’s centroid lands in a tile boundary. See Section 3.6.5 for more details on this figure.

we evaluate the photometry measurements obtained by using the probabilistic output from BLISS.

We created a new dataset `dataset-central` (Section 3.4) for the purpose of performing this experiment. This dataset is equivalent to the one used in Sections 3.6.2 through 3.6.4, except that no stars are included in the simulation, and, in every image, the central 5×5 tile always contains exactly a single galaxy with a i -band magnitude brighter than 25.3. We only evaluate the flux recovery of this central galaxy. We decided to exclude stars from this simulation in order to simplify the setup, but the binary encoder could have been sampled to identify stars. We also force the central galaxy to be exactly in the middle of the central tile, which mitigates the effect of multiple source being present in the same tile (Section 3.5.1), and that of sources getting too close to tile boundaries (see Section 3.6.5). These simulation choices were made so we could explore potential improvements to flux measurement via the BLISS probabilistic output while mitigating issues in our current model that will be addressed in future work. Note however, that we do not completely eliminate these artifacts

as other galaxies in the image could land in the same tile or have their centroid close to a tile boundary. Finally, we choose the central galaxy to be sufficiently bright to avoid images where it is never detected, which would just waste computational time in this experiment.

We compare aperture photometry measurements of the central galaxy using BLISS in three different ways. The first way, denoted ‘MAP’, uses the most likely detections to reconstruct the light profile of sources and for flux measurement. These detections correspond to those with a tile detection probability larger than 0.5, and whose location is the mean of the predicted centroid posterior distribution. The second approach, uses SEP (using the same settings as in Section 3.6.2) for detections instead of BLISS, but the deblending before flux measurement is still performed using the BLISS deblender encoder. For the third way, denoted ‘Samples’, we draw 100 samples from the predicted distributions for counts and centroids to obtain an approximation to the posterior distribution of fluxes (for each image) that accounts for detection uncertainties. We use the mean of this flux posterior distribution as our new point estimator for comparison with the MAP and SEP flux predictions. For each image, we use the same method for aperture flux measurement as in Section 3.6.4, where detected galaxies besides the central one are removed using noiseless reconstructions from the deblender encoder. The key difference with the previous set of deblending results is that we use the predicted galaxy centroids rather than true centroids for both removing sources and to center the aperture. In all cases, flux is only measured when a predicted detection is less than 2 pixels away from central galaxy.

Our results are summarized as a function of the blendedness of the central galaxy in Figure 3.10. We choose a total of 20 blendedness bins, where 18 of them are in the range $[3.56 \times 10^{-4}, 3.76 \times 10^{-1}]$ and are set to ensure equal number of objects in each. All objects with value lower than 3.56×10^{-4} or higher than 3.76×10^{-1} are placed in the first and last bin respectively. The upper bound was chosen to ensure enough statistics on highly blended examples. Each bin contains at least 400 corresponding images used to obtain residuals. The curves represent the (fractional) median residual in each blendedness bin from each method, where the ‘samples’ approach uses the average of the flux measured across the samples to compute its residual. The shaded regions correspond to the 1σ bootstrap errors on the median obtained by resampling the residuals on each bin. In this figure we see that the sampling approach to measure photometry significantly outperforms the point-prediction from both BLISS (MAP) and SEP across blendedness bins. The gap in the median residuals seem to increase with blendedness and is particularly large for the last bin, where the residual jumps from approximately 20% to about 120% for the MAP, and about 400% for SEP.

In Figure 3.11, we show the flux residual results as a function of true SNR of the central source of each image. As before, the curves represent the median fractional flux residual and

the shading their bootstrap error for the same three methods. The SNR bins are chosen so that there is an equal number of images in each, resulting in over 400 images in each bin. From this figure, we see that the sampling approach outperforms the other two methods over the entire range of SNRs by at least 1%, although it underestimates the flux of very faint sources ($\text{SNR} < 10$). The other methods appear to overestimate the flux of dim sources instead, and perform comparably throughout.

We hypothesize, after looking at several individual image examples, that these improvements are driven by the large number of objects undetected by the MAP or SEP approach when the blendedness level is high or the SNR is low. Undetected objects will not be removed from the image with the deblender, and would thus lead to flux overestimation. On the other hand, the sampling approach has the potential to detect more sources as no hard cutoff is used for detection probability. Samples corresponding to sources in the image that are difficult to detect could be, on average, reducing the flux residual. It is also possible the sampling approach is less sensitive to the tile boundary artifact, as the probability of a source close to a boundary appears to be shared between the corresponding tiles (R. Liu et al., 2023). However, the comparison using the SEP detections demonstrate that this cannot be the only source of improvement, as the SEP algorithm does not use a tiling procedure.

Overall this result shows the potential for our method significantly photometry biases in highly blended systems. While out of scope for this paper due to our use of single-band image simulations, future work using multi-band images could investigate downstream applications to improve color and redshift estimation. We will also seek to stress-test this method using a larger number of simulations and develop a procedure to mitigate tile boundary effects.

3.7 Discussion and Summary

In this work, we introduce the Bayesian Light Source Separator (BLISS), a Bayesian method for detection, deblending, and measurement of astronomical light sources. We have presented the components of BLISS and illustrated its performance on LSST-like simulated images of galaxy blends. We find that BLISS can detect a significantly larger fraction of blended galaxies than SourceExtractor (Section 3.6.2), and that by combining probabilistic detection and deblending could lead to improvements in aperture photometry measurements of highly blended systems (Section 3.6.6). To our knowledge, *BLISS is the first deblender with joint probabilistic detection and deblending capabilities.*

Our other results are as follows:

- To enable inference of light source parameters for arbitrarily large images, we split our images into overlapping padded tiles. Our tiling scheme forces the neural network to

Figure 3.10: **Flux measurement in BLISS using probabilistic detections as a function of blendedness.** In this figure, we compare the (fractional) median flux residual for three different approaches to flux measurement using BLISS in the dataset `dataset-central`. In all three cases, the flux is measured on the central galaxy of each image using aperture photometry after deblending is performed using the same BLISS deblender encoder, but different detections are used. Detections are matched within 2 pixels of the true galaxy centroid on the center of the image. If no matches with the central galaxy, no flux measurement is performed for those set of detections. In the first case (MAP), the most likely detections (above 50% probability) from the BLISS detection encoder are used for deblending and aperture photometry. In the second case (SEP), detections from SEP are used instead. Finally, in ‘Samples’, we draw 100 detection samples from the BLISS detection encoder and used these as input to the deblender encoder. We take the mean over these measured fluxes as the flux estimator for each image. See Section 3.6.6 for more discussion on this figure.

learn only the details local to each light source. For more details. See Section 3.5.1.

- We present a Bayesian method consisting of three neural network which can be combined to jointly detect, classify, and detect galaxies. We demonstrate how this approach can be used to improve the photometry measurements of highly blended galaxies in the context of our LSST-like simulations. See Section 3.6.6.
- We thoroughly evaluate the point estimates from each our neural networks. We find that the detection encoder achieves comparable performance with SExtractor across SNRs, and is able to recover a larger fraction of very dim or highly blended sources (Section 3.6.2). Our classification encoder an F_1 score of over 70% when classifying stars with SNR larger than 12, and above 95% for galaxies with SNR larger than 10

Figure 3.11: **Flux measurement in BLISS using probabilistic detections as a function of SNR.** This figure presents the same results as Figure 3.3, but residuals are split into SNR bins based on the true SNR of the central source of each image. The bins are chosen so that there are an equal number of images in each. See Section 3.6.6 for additional discussion.

(Section 3.6.3). Finally, our deblender significantly improves the recovered flux and morphology of highly blended galaxies when the true centroid is known (Section 3.6.4).

- We carefully examine the probabilistic output of our method in the context of a simple simulation of a pair of galaxies. We find that BLISS is able to detect sources even at very low source separation, and that detection probabilities overall increase as sources become more separated, as expected. However, we find that detection probability can be degraded when sources get too close to tile boundaries. Finally, we find that individual galaxy reconstructions improve as the separation increases. See Section 3.6.5.
- The inference step of the BLISS pipeline is fast. Once trained using a single GPU, BLISS can perform full posterior inference on megapixel images containing galaxy and star blends in seconds.

We use an autoencoder (AE) trained on parametric simulated galaxies as our galaxy model. This model enables the training of the deblender encoder and reconstruction of galaxies (Section 3.5.4). This approach follows growing body of work on using deep neural networks for galaxy image modeling. Recent work on using deep learning for galaxy modeling commonly uses generative adversarial networks (GANs) and variational autoencoders (VAEs), and, more recently, score-based models (S. Ravanbakhsh et al., 2016; M. Dia et al., 2019; L.

Fussell & B. Moews, 2019; D. M. Reiman & B. E. Göhre, 2019; F. Lanusse et al., 2021; B. Arcelin et al., 2021; S. Hemmati et al., 2022; M. J. Smith et al., 2022; B. Biswas et al., 2024; M. L. Sampson et al., 2024). We used an AE in BLISS since autoencoders are generally more stable in training than GANs (D. P. Kingma & M. Welling, 2019) and have been shown to perform galaxy image reconstruction accurately (F. Lanusse et al., 2021; B. Arcelin et al., 2021). Recently, F. Lanusse et al. (2021) used VAEs to build deep generative models that can recreate realistic galaxy images using data from the HST COSMOS catalog (R. Mandelbaum et al., 2018). VAEs have also been used successfully for deblending in B. Arcelin et al. (2021). These types of methods have the potential to mitigate model bias often incurred by more standard parametric galaxy models, as demonstrated by B. Remy et al. (2022). Currently, we do not take full advantage of the modeling capabilities of deep generative models in BLISS, as our AE is deterministic and we train it exclusively on parametric galaxies, but we have plans to incorporate realistic galaxy profiles and use a VAE to capture the full uncertainty of galaxy properties in future work.

BLISS includes a detection encoder (Section 3.5.3) capable of outputting a posterior distribution for the centroids of stars and galaxies in astronomical images. BLISS accomplishes performance comparable with SourceExtractor (E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996; K. Barbary, 2016) as the combined result of its tiling approach and its neural network backend. Traditional detection approaches are based on peak finding or thresholding, such as the popular algorithm SExtractor (E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996). However, these types of classical approaches cannot characterize uncertainty in the number of sources found and are known to result in a significant number of ambiguously blended sources (W. A. Dawson et al., 2016). Probabilistic approaches for detection relying on MCMC have been proposed for deblending crowded starfields, such as in R. M. Feder et al. (2020), and predicting point estimates and uncertainties of star fluxes and centroids. However, these approaches are computationally expensive due to their use of MCMC.

BLISS also includes a classification encoder (Section 3.5.3) capable of assigning a probability of a detected source being a galaxy or a star. Approaches to star-galaxy separation have thus far often involved a neural network, such as the one used in SExtractor (E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996). This neural network differs from ours in that it does not use the images directly but rather 10 carefully chosen numerical features and a feedforward architecture. More recent approaches to star-galaxy classification include convolutional neural networks such as BLISS and avoid the need to carefully extract features (E. J. Kim & R. J. Brunner, 2016; P. Garg et al., 2022). Other approaches have used low-dimensional embeddings of optical images and Gaussian processes for classification (I. R. Goumiri et al., 2020; A. L. Muyskens et al., 2022). The CNN architecture used in BLISS could enable using information

from multiple bands or exposures for a given light source. These approaches will become more important as new surveys observe fainter objects, where the increase in blending of smaller galaxies makes classification difficult (C. T. Slater et al., 2020).

BLISS perform deblending using its deblender encoder (Section 3.5.4), which takes as input samples from the detection and classification encoders. The deblender encoder consists of a neural network that learns to target the galaxy at the center of an image, while removing the flux of surrounding galaxies. This approach to deblending is similar to DeblVader (B. Arcelin et al. (2021)) and MADNESS (B. Biswas et al. (2024)). Other deblenders such as SCARLET (P. Melchior et al., 2018), use constrained optimization to deblend light sources without deep learning. In future work, we also plan to conduct an extensive comparison of BLISS with these and other deblenders using the BlendingToolkit package (I. Mendoza et al., 2025).

As explored in Section 3.6.5, our tiling procedure (Section 3.5.1) has some potential drawbacks. We found that detection probability correlates strongly with distance from the source to the tile boundary. This makes the detection probability drop below 0.5 even for detectable and isolated sources. This effect could be impacting the results of Section 3.6.2 as well, degrading detections and reducing the BLISS recall across all SNR and blendedness bins. In a precursor paper to BLISS (R. Liu et al., 2023), the authors find that the probability is ‘shared’ between tiles when the source becomes too close to the tile boundary. Future work will perform a more in depth-analysis of tile boundary effects, and develop mitigation strategies.

In Section 3.6.6 we explored the potential of BLISS to jointly detect and deblend galaxies. We evaluated the impact of using samples from the detection encoder as input to the deblender encoder to improve photometry measurements. We find that using samples when deblending can reduce the median flux residual by approximately 100% for highly blended galaxies in our slightly simplified `dataset-central` simulations. The motivation for this experiment was understanding how the full posterior output from BLISS could potentially recover flux more accurately on highly blended sources, which in the future could be extended to improve color and thus redshift estimation. Previous work has already shown that an ML deblender can be used to improve photometric redshift estimation (G. Merz et al., 2025) in simulations. In a future paper, we will evaluate and investigate the color predictions of our sampling approach using multi-band LSST-like image simulations.

Our future work on BLISS will focus on making this algorithm ready to be used in real astronomical data and aid cosmological analyses from Stage-IV optical surveys such as LSST. Specifically, we plan to: (1) Develop BLISS so that processing multi-band data becomes possible. This might enable propagating our flux uncertainties to photo- z estimation. (2) Accommodate data with spatially-variable PSFs (A. Patel et al., 2025) and background,

as well as other effects present in real survey images. (3) Test and validate our approach using a specific set of science-driven metrics in more realistic LSST-like simulations. For example, a study in using BLISS detection samples to explore whether shear detection biases could be mitigated. (4) Address potential biases related to the tiling procedure in BLISS (Section 3.6.5). (5) Understand how robust BLISS is to significant and relevant differences between the training and test data. (6) Training and testing our models on real galaxy images. For instance, we could consider using a combination of deep fields and space observations from other cosmology surveys to build a more realistic model of galaxy morphology. In this work we have only trained and evaluated on parametric galaxies which might lead to biases in real survey data.

Data Availability

The code to reproduce all experiments is available in a public GitHub repository: <https://github.com/prob-ml/bliss>.

3.8 Appendix: Simulation Based Inference

In this appendix we illustrate at a high-level how the BLISS framework fits within the paradigm of simulation based inference in Figure 3.12. This figure was created using individual images from various sources.^{18,19,20,21}

3.9 Appendix: Bayesian framework for probabilistic cataloging

We describe the Bayesian framework that underpins the problem of probabilistic inference of catalogs from astronomical images. Given an image containing blended galaxies and stars, \mathcal{X} , we want to obtain a probability distribution over catalog \mathcal{Z} . A catalog corresponds to the set of all galaxy and star parameters that characterize the mean intensity of a given image. Our goal is then to obtain the posterior distribution, $P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X})$, defined as,

$$P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X}) = \frac{P(\mathcal{Z})P(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Z})}{P(\mathcal{X})}. \quad (3.18)$$

¹⁸<https://sbi-dev.github.io/sbi>

¹⁹<https://www.vecteezy.com/free-vector/gear>

²⁰flaticon.com

²¹<https://datasciencegenie.com/3d-contour-plots-of-bivariate-normal-distribution/>

Figure 3.12: **BLISS and Simulation Based Inference.** This figure lays out how BLISS fits into a simulation based inference (SBI) framework. First, galaxy properties θ are sampled from some synthetic or real galaxy catalog. In our context we use the CatSim (A. J. Connolly et al., 2014a) catalog, which comes from N-body simulations and a semi-analytic baryon model. This catalog implicitly represents the prior $p(\theta)$ in our model. Next, this sample of galaxy properties θ are passed into GALSIM (B. T. P. Rowe et al., 2015), the weak lensing image simulator, to create an image of a galaxy blend D . The process by which we create images with GALSIM implicitly defines the likelihood $P(D|\theta)$ of our model. Then, images are passed into the BLISS neural networks and these networks output the parameters characterizing an approximation to the posterior distribution $P(\theta|D)$ of inferred galaxy properties. Finally, the parameters of these networks are optimized via supervised learning by choosing a suitable loss function that encodes the difference between the true posterior and its approximation. **Image credit:** This image was created using elements from various sources (see Appendix 3.8 for attribution).

Here, $P(\mathcal{Z})$ is the prior distribution, $P(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Z})$ is the conditional likelihood, and $P(\mathcal{X})$ is the evidence or marginal likelihood.

The prior $P(\mathcal{Z})$ corresponds to an expected distribution of light source parameters before taking any particular astronomical image into account. This distribution could come from astronomical catalogs of precursor surveys or from cosmological knowledge. In our case, the prior over full images $P(\mathcal{Z})$ is defined implicitly by our choice of galaxy and star catalogs (see Section 3.4).

The conditional likelihood $P(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Z})$ corresponds to the probability that we have observed a specific astronomical image, \mathcal{X} , given a corresponding catalog \mathcal{Z} . The catalog \mathcal{Z} describes the source centroid locations and the mean intensity of stars and galaxies (from the flux and shape entries in the catalog). The combination of the catalog, the PSF, and the background determines the mean intensity of every pixel in the astronomical image. Using the normal approximation to the independent Poisson noise at every pixel of the image, the conditional likelihood reduces to a normal distribution that factorizes over each pixel where the mean and variance are the mean intensity $\tilde{\mathcal{X}}$ determined by the catalog:

$$P(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Z}) = \prod_{p \in \text{pixels}} \mathcal{N}(\mathcal{X}_p; \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_p, \tilde{\mathcal{X}}_p). \quad (3.19)$$

Though the conditional likelihood is known and tractable to evaluate in our context, we do not use it in our methodology for the detection and classification encoder. We use only the negative log conditional likelihood as the loss function for the galaxy autoencoder and deblender encoder (see Section 3.5.4).

Traditionally, Bayesian inference for astronomical catalogs might use the conditional likelihood paired with Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling (M. D. Schneider et al., 2015; S. K. Portillo et al., 2017; R. M. Feder et al., 2020). Given the light source counts in an image and a parametric source model, one can run an MCMC chain over all sources and source parameters targeting the conditional likelihood $P(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Z})$ to output a joint posterior distribution of the sources' parameters. Although this fully Bayesian approach promises exact posterior samples upon convergence, MCMC sampling is less computationally tractable over larger parameter spaces and data volumes compared with a variational inference approach (D. M. Blei et al., 2017).

Finally, the evidence, also known as the marginal likelihood and $P(\mathcal{X})$, is the marginal probability distribution of the pixel values in a given image. $P(\mathcal{X})$ is intractable for our case. We can rewrite this term as

$$P(\mathcal{X}) = \int P(\mathcal{Z})P(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Z})d\mathcal{Z}, \quad (3.20)$$

where the integral is over all possible catalogs. Intuitively, the marginal likelihood is the probability of a given astronomical image without reference to a specific corresponding catalog. Hypothetically, it would be the probability of obtaining a given set of pixels (an image) when pointing the telescope at infinite random realizations of the sky. The pixels in \mathcal{X} are correlated due to the effect of the PSF and existence of extended sources, so the probability $P(\mathcal{X})$ does not factorize. This probability has two contributions (1) the uncertainty over catalogs from the prior and (2) the noise in the image. This integral is intractable because the number of catalogs we need to consider to perform this integral is arbitrarily large for a given image \mathcal{X} . For example, a given set of pixel values in an image might be degenerate between any number of dim sources buried under noise, or any number of sources that sufficiently overlap for that resolution.

Given the intractability of computing Equation 3.20 and the computational challenges of the MCMC approach, we instead opt to use variational inference as our framework to perform tractable approximate posterior inference.

3.10 Appendix: Variational loss function derivation

In this appendix we derive the loss function used in BLISS corresponding to Equation 3.10 in Section 3.5.2.

We start with the FAVI loss function (Equation 3.8):

$$L(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} D_{\text{KL}}(P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X}) \parallel Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z})), \quad (3.21)$$

where $P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X})$ is the true posterior, Q_ϕ for $Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z})$ is the variational distribution, \mathcal{Z} are the light source parameters (Equation 3.7), \mathcal{X} is an astronomical image, and $D_{\text{KL}}(\cdot \parallel \cdot)$ is the KL divergence.

The goal is to find the neural network weights ϕ^* that minimize this loss. We can formulate this mathematically as follows:

$$\phi^* = \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q_\phi), \quad (3.22)$$

where P and Q_ϕ are shorthand for $P(\mathcal{Z}, \mathcal{X})$ and $Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z})$, respectively. We can now expand the KL divergence using the definition to obtain:

$$\phi^* = \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} \int P \log \left(\frac{P}{Q_\phi} \right) \quad (3.23)$$

$$= \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} \int P \log P - \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} \int P \log Q_\phi. \quad (3.24)$$

The first term can be ignored since it does not depend on ϕ and thus will not affect optimization. This gives:

$$\phi^* = \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmin}} -\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} \int P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X}) \log Q_\phi \quad (3.25)$$

$$= \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmax}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X} \sim P(\mathcal{X})} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{Z} \sim P(\mathcal{Z}|\mathcal{X})} \log Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}). \quad (3.26)$$

We can combine the two expectations to obtain:

$$\phi^* = \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmax}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z} \sim P(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z})} \log Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}) \quad (3.27)$$

$$= \underset{\phi}{\operatorname{argmax}} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z} \sim P(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z})} \sum_{t=1}^T \log Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}_t). \quad (3.28)$$

Next, using the rules of conditional probability for the variational distribution with each of

the light source parameters we get:

$$Q_\phi(\mathcal{Z}_t) = Q_\phi(n_t)Q_\phi(\ell_t|n_t)Q_\phi(b_t|n_t, \ell_t). \quad (3.29)$$

Finally, plugging this into Equation 3.28 we recover the loss used in BLISS for the detection and classification encoders (Section 3.5.3) and obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} L(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z} \sim P(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Z})} & \sum_{t=1}^T \log Q_\phi(n_t) + \log Q_\phi(\ell_t|n_t) \\ & + \log Q_\phi(f_t|n_t, \ell_t, b_t) + \log Q_\phi(b_t|n_t, \ell_t), \end{aligned} \quad (3.30)$$

which corresponds to Equation 3.10.

3.11 Appendix: Settings for SourceExtractor in Python

We use SExtractor in Python (SEP) v1.4.1 (K. Barbary, 2016). The convolution kernel (FILTER) corresponds to a Gaussian profile in a 3×3 array of pixel values with a equal to 2.0 pixels (0.4 arcsec).

The specific arguments used for detection through the `sep.extract` function are listed in Table 3.11. We aim to match the SExtractor (E. Bertin & S. Arnouts, 1996) settings used in J. Sanchez et al. (2021) as much as possible.

Argument	Value
thresh	1.5
min_area	5
deblend_nthresh	32
deblend_cont	0.005

Table 3.2: **SEP settings**. Arguments passed into the `sep.extract` function which roughly correspond classical SExtractor settings. See Appendix 3.11 for details.

3.12 Appendix: Centroid prediction for pair blend

In this appendix, we show the quality of the centroid predictions of the detection encoder in the pair blend example of Section 3.6.5.

In Figure 3.13, top row, we see the residual between the true centroid and mean of the centroid posterior that BLISS predicts for the tile containing ‘Galaxy 1’ (green) and ‘Galaxy 2’ (purple). In the bottom row, we see the uncertainty in the centroid predicted by BLISS for the tile containing each source. Both the residuals and uncertainties are significantly noisy, but all seem to decrease with increased separation between the sources. We also see spikes in all the curves at separations corresponding to tile boundaries, which was also observed for the detection probabilities in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.13: **Detection residuals and errors as a function of separation between galaxies.** In this plot we show the centroid location residual and BLISS predicted uncertainties in the x and y directions for the pair of galaxies in Section 3.6.5. Specifically, the top row shows the difference between the mean centroid predicted by the detection encoder for the tile containing each galaxy and the true centroid as a function of separation. The bottom row shows the predicted uncertainty on the centroid as a function of separation.

CHAPTER 4

Hierarchical Bayesian Shear Inference with Differentiable Forward Modeling

4.1 Preface

This chapter is reproduced in its entirety from a draft publication with the title “Differentiable Forward Modeling for Efficient and Accurate Shear Inference” which will be submitted for a first round of internal review in the LSST-DESC collaboration. The co-authors are: Axel Guinot, Camille Avestruz, Jean-Eric Campagne, Natalia Porqueres, Michael Schneider, Eleni Tsaprazi, and Matthew Becker. As the first author of this draft publication my contributions included: leading project within LSST-DESC, developing initial project proposal, implementing all project-specific code, being one of the lead developers of the JAX-GalSim library, and writing entirety of paper text.

This planned publication presents a Bayesian shear inference algorithm that leverages GPUs and gradient-based samplers to achieve higher efficiency than classical approaches.

4.2 Abstract

Forthcoming Stage-IV dark energy optical surveys, such as the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), have the ambitious goal of measuring cosmological parameters at sub-percent precision. Realizing their full scientific potential requires very precise measurement of the cosmic shear signal and control of the corresponding systematics. In this work, we present a modern implementation of the Bayesian shear inference framework from Schneider et al. (2014), in the case that the PSF and sky background are known. Our algorithm consists consists of two steps. First, a GPU-based model-fitting MCMC produces ellipticity samples for each galaxy. Next, these samples are aggregated to marginalize the intrinsic properties of galaxies and evaluate the shear likelihood, which enables sampling the

shear posterior. This framework automatically propagates the pixel-noise measurement error from each galaxy into the final shear estimate, and thus requires no external calibration to handle noise bias. We rigorously test the full shear inference procedure on simple LSST-like images with isolated parametric galaxies and realistic levels of shape and pixel noise. We estimate the absolute multiplicative bias $|m|$ of our approach to be below $1.0 \times 10^{-3} [3\sigma]$ when the intrinsic distribution of galaxy properties is known, and below $1.7 \times 10^{-3} [3\sigma]$ when these distributions are inferred alongside shear. Both results are within the LSST requirement of $|m| < 2 \times 10^{-3}$. Additionally, we make progress towards the algorithm’s computational feasibility in the context of modern wide-field surveys, where billions of galaxies must be processed, by leveraging differentiable forward models of galaxies, gradient-based samplers, and GPUs. Our final galaxy-fitting MCMC produces 300 effective samples of galaxy properties in 0.44 seconds per galaxy using a single GPU. In the future, we seek to generalize our algorithm to be applied on real survey data. In particular, our method does not currently account for biases related to realistic galaxy morphology, blending, detection, or sample selection, and these will be the subject for upcoming work.

4.3 Introduction

The gravitational potential generated by structure in our universe distorts the light from background source galaxies, altering their observed shapes due to weak gravitational lensing (WL) – an effect called *cosmic shear*. Cosmic shear traces the distribution of dark matter and the nature of dark energy, making WL one of the most powerful cosmological probes (D. Huterer, 2002; M. Kilbinger, 2015; J. Prat & D. Bacon, 2025). Cosmic shear measurements have been successfully used in several Stage-III optical cosmological surveys, including KiDS (M. Asgari et al., 2021; A. H. Wright et al., 2025), DES (DES Collaboration et al., 2022; L. F. Secco et al., 2022), and HSC (X. Li et al., 2023b; R. Dalal et al., 2023b) to constrain dark energy cosmological parameters to about a percent level. Modern Stage-IV optical surveys such as the Vera C. Rubin Observatory Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) (Ž. Ivezić et al., 2019a), Euclid (R. Laureijs et al., 2011b), and the Roman Space Telescope (D. Spergel et al., 2015) have the objective of constraining dark energy to a sub-percent, which could pave the way for beyond Λ CDM physics. Precise and accurate measurements of cosmic shear are critical to maximize the scientific return of these Stage-IV surveys.

Shear measurement is challenging: cosmic shear is about a 2% change in a galaxy’s axis ratio on an average cosmological line of sight (G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong, 2014; R. Mandelbaum, 2018). LSST, for instance, has the ambitious goal of performing shear measurement with statistical errors below 1 part in 1000 of this 2% (R. Mandelbaum, 2018).

Several shear measurement algorithms have been proposed over the years, but only a few have shown the potential to meet this challenging requirement. Currently, the dominant paradigm calibrates the ensemble shear estimator directly on the survey images by simulating the effect of a known shear, so-called *self-calibration*. This is the motivation for the METACALIBRATION (E. Huff & R. Mandelbaum (2017); E. S. Sheldon & E. M. Huff (2017)) algorithm, and its extension METADETECTION (E. S. Sheldon et al. (2020); H. Hoekstra (2021); H. Hoekstra et al. (2021); E. S. Sheldon et al. (2023)). Another related approach is Anacal (X. Li et al., 2024, 2025b,a), which analytically calibrates the shear response using auto-differentiation and a suitable basis of FPFS shapelets (X. Li et al., 2022). Both METADETECTION and Anacal have been shown to meet the LSST shear bias requirements, and METACALIBRATION and METADETECTION have already been successfully applied to real data in DES (J. Zuntz et al., 2018; M. Gatti et al., 2021; M. Yamamoto et al., 2025).

Despite the successes of self-calibration methods, they will face new challenges in the context of Stage-IV surveys. For example, the coupled effects of blending in both shear and redshift calibration were shown in DES weak lensing analyses to be an important contribution to the mean multiplicative bias (N. MacCrann et al., 2022). This effect is likely to worsen with the increased depth of surveys like LSST (J. Sanchez et al., 2021; P. Melchior et al., 2021). Another set of systematics gaining relevancy are *chromatic biases* (J. E. Meyers & P. R. Burchat, 2015; M. Eriksen & H. Hoekstra, 2018; S. G. Carlsten et al., 2018; S. Kamath et al., 2019; F. Berlfein et al., 2025). These arise because the Point Spread Function (PSF), a wavelength-dependent quantity, is modeled using stars which typically have different SEDs than galaxies. Currently, there is no METACALIBRATION extension accounting for these effects; Anacal cannot account for the aforementioned blending effect, but PSF-level corrections were recently implemented for chromatic biases and tested on Roman simulations (F. Berlfein et al., 2025). It is likely that these methods will require external calibration from simulations as demonstrated in N. MacCrann et al. (2022). Separately, both METACALIBRATION and Anacal require injecting additional noise to images as part of their procedure, significantly reducing the signal-to-noise ratio of measurements, and increasing systematic uncertainty. However, extensions of these methods that use deep field images are in development and might reduce the impact of this effect (Z. Zhang et al., 2023). Given some of the current limitations in self-calibration methods, exploring other shear inference methods might still be fruitful.

Another set of algorithms for shear measurement use a forward model of galaxy images that includes relevant systematics. In principle, this approach reduces the bias on the shear estimator at the expense of increased model complexity and estimated uncertainty. A recent implementation of this idea is LENSMC (Euclid Collaboration et al., 2024), which samples

galaxy ellipticities with an optimized MCMC and aggregates them across multiple galaxies to produce a final shear measurement. This algorithm has been tested on Euclid-like simulations and achieved reasonable shear measurement accuracy. One downside of LENS_{MC} is that the prescription to aggregate shapes into shear is an ad-hoc weighting and average scheme, and does not utilize the entire set of galaxy properties. Another related method is JIF (J. J. Buchanan et al., 2023) which used a physically-informed prior and selection corrections on the likelihood to obtain posterior samples of galaxy properties from images in the LSST DESC DC2 simulation (LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (LSST DESC) et al., 2021b). This algorithm is statistically rigorous and established good probabilistic calibration for many of the galaxies in this simulation. However, they have not demonstrated that their samples can be used to estimate shear. Both approaches might also be limited by their runtime in a Stage-IV survey: LENS_{MC} was estimated to process one galaxy in 5 seconds whereas JIF takes a few minutes.

In this work we propose a new shear inference algorithm based on the Bayesian hierarchical framework from M. D. Schneider et al. (2015). This framework infers shear from MCMC samples of galaxy properties obtained via model fitting based on a statistically rigorous formalism, and is parallelizable over non-overlapping galaxy groups. Our implementation leverages differentiable forward models of galaxies in JAX (J. Bradbury et al., 2018), gradient-based samplers such as NUTS (M. D. Hoffman et al., 2014), and GPUs to speedup the MCMC galaxy property sampling. Using this efficient implementation, we rigorously test our entire shear inference pipeline on a simple LSST-like dataset of isolated parametric galaxy images, and measure its multiplicative bias using the shape noise cancellation method in A. Pujol et al. (2019). We demonstrate that our shear inference algorithm fulfills the LSST requirement for shear bias in this setting.

In Section 4.4 we describe the dataset of galaxy images simulated with GALSIM (B. T. P. Rowe et al., 2015) that we use to test our shear measurement algorithm. Next, in Section 4.5 we describe our algorithm implementation in detail, laying out the statistical framework and the computational innovations. In Section 4.6, we present several tests we perform on our shear inference, including estimating its bias. Finally, we conclude and discuss future work in Section 4.7. ate from model-fitted samples is an ad-hoc weighting and average scheme, and does not utilize the entire set of galaxy properties.

4.4 Dataset

Our dataset for all our experiments consists of a set of 320k isolated parametric galaxy images with size 63×63 pixels simulated with GALSIM (B. T. P. Rowe et al., 2015). Every simulated

galaxy follows the exponential (disk) light profile, which corresponds to a Sérsic profile with $n = 1$ (J. Sérsic, 1963). The observing conditions and distributions of galaxy properties are chosen to approach the noise levels of a survey like LSST.

We choose parametric distributions for the flux f (in units of counts) and half-light-radius s (in units of arcsecs) of our galaxies:

$$\begin{aligned}\log_{10} f &\sim \text{SkewNormal}(\mu_f = 2.45, \sigma_f = 0.4, a_f = 14) \\ \log_{10} s &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_s = -0.4, \sigma_s = 0.05),\end{aligned}\tag{4.1}$$

and ignore the correlation between the flux and size of galaxies in the context of this paper. The first two parameters of each distribution represent the mean and standard deviation, respectively. The log-flux has a skew normal distribution with shape parameter $a = 14$, which creates a smooth but rapid cutoff below approximately $\log_{10} f = 2.5$. These choices for flux and size result in a SNR (signal-to-noise ratio)¹ distribution with a median of about 20. We use a sky level value of $b = 1$ for all images and assume the sky dominated approximation. We have chosen this flux distribution to mimic observational effects that exclude very dim galaxies from the sample. The size distribution is too narrow compared to real data and was chosen for convenience. These result in an SNR distribution which is more optimistic than the forecasted weak-lensing sample in LSST, but includes galaxies with SNR down to 12.²

Galaxy ellipticities $(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2)$ are sampled by first sampling the ellipticity magnitude $|\varepsilon| \equiv \varepsilon$ and orientation angle ϕ independently. Then, by taking the components of the complex ellipticity spinor:³

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \varepsilon_1 + i\varepsilon_2 = \varepsilon \cdot e^{2i\phi}.\tag{4.2}$$

We choose the prior distribution on the magnitude of ellipticities $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ to be the same distribution used in G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong (2014), which has the form:

$$f_e(\varepsilon) \propto \varepsilon(1 - \varepsilon^2)^2 \exp(-\varepsilon^2/2\sigma_e^2).\tag{4.3}$$

This distribution corresponds to a truncated Gaussian in polar coordinates with an additional factor of $(1 - \varepsilon^2)^2$. This factor ensures that the prior has two continuous derivatives at the $\varepsilon < 1$ boundary. We use a shape noise value of $\sigma_e = 0.2$. The orientation angle $\phi \in (0, \pi)$ is

¹The SNR is computed using the expression $\sqrt{\sum_p I_p^2/b}$ where I_p is the intensity at each pixel and b is the sky level.

²An additional reason for choosing this SNR distribution is that we observed that MCMC chains targeting images with galaxies below this SNR sometimes failing to converge. We choose to defer accounting for dimmer galaxies in our sample to future work. See Section 4.5 for details on these chains.

³We choose our ellipticity definition to match the ‘ ε ’ definition in M. Bartelmann & P. Schneider (2001), see Equation 4.10 from this paper. It also corresponds to the ‘reduced shear’ g definition in GALSIM.

chosen to be uniformly distributed.

The centroid (x, y) of each galaxy is uniformly distributed within the center pixel of each image. Finally, the PSF is the same for all images and it is modeled as a Gaussian with FWHM of 0.8 arcsecs, which is close to the median value at zenith for LSST (Ž. Ivezić et al., 2019b). The distribution of intrinsic galaxy properties including flux, size, SNR, and ellipticities are shown in Figure 4.1. Their mean and standard deviation are shown in the corresponding subtitles, while the median is shown as dashed black line and the value is in the legend.

In this paper we restrict to the case where both the PSF and background are known and constant. When applying this method in real survey data, separate survey pipelines could provide this information.

4.5 Methodology

We start by describing at a high-level the hierarchical Bayesian shear inference framework (Section 4.5.1). Next, we derive the shear likelihood which underpins our methodology in Section 4.5.2. Then, we detail our efficient implementation of this framework by taking advantage of differentiable forward modeling, gradient-based samplers, and GPUs (Section 4.5.4). Finally, we describe our method to measure multiplicative bias from inferred shear posteriors via the shape noise cancellation trick (Section 4.5.5).

4.5.1 Hierarchical Bayesian Shear Inference

In this section we describe the algorithm for inferring the shear posterior $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{g}|\mathbf{d})$, where \mathbf{g} is the shear and \mathbf{d} is a data vector corresponding to the pixels of a set of noisy individual galaxy images.

Our procedure is a special case of the framework presented in M. D. Schneider et al. (2015) in the limit of isolated, individual galaxy images with a known PSF $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ and background sky-level b . It consists of two steps. First, we sample ellipticities and other galaxy properties from each individual galaxy image independently using a differentiable parametric model of galaxies and a gradient-based MCMC chain. Second, we take these samples of galaxy properties and run an additional MCMC chain, which aggregates the samples across all the galaxies to evaluate the likelihood $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{g})$ and obtain a posterior on cosmic shear.

Importantly, we allow for joint inference of the hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ describing the distribution of intrinsic galaxy properties along with the shear \mathbf{g} using the same data \mathbf{d} . Thus, for full generality we include $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ in our target posterior: $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}|\mathbf{d})$. In our work, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ includes the

Figure 4.1: **Distribution of intrinsic galaxy properties.** In this figure we show distribution of intrinsic galaxy properties of our exponential galaxy dataset used in all our experiments. The mean and sigma of each distribution are shown in the title of each distribution, and the median is shown as a dashed black line. For more details on this figure see Section 4.4.

Figure 4.2: **Probabilistic graphical model** representing our forward model for shear inference. A constant shear \mathbf{g} is applied to every galaxy with intrinsic parameters $\boldsymbol{\omega}_n$ with corresponding pixels \mathbf{d}_n . The intrinsic properties of each galaxy are sampled from distributions characterized by hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_n$, which includes the distribution of intrinsic ellipticities. The PSF $\boldsymbol{\pi}_n$ and noise covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_n$ for each galaxy image are known and fixed.

parameters characterizing the skew normal distribution of log-fluxes (μ_f, σ_f, a_f) , the normal distribution of log-sizes (μ_s, σ_s) , and the intrinsic ellipticity magnitude distribution (σ_e) .

Our model is visualized as a probabilistic graphical model in Figure 4.2. Each node represents a random variable, the dots represent fixed constants, arrows encode conditional dependencies, and boxes signal independent groups of variables. For generality, we include the possibility of different, known PSFs $\boldsymbol{\pi}_n$ and noise covariances $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_n$ for each galaxy, although these are both fixed in our experiments.

4.5.2 Mathematical Formalism

In this section, we derive a general version of the joint shear and intrinsic parameter likelihood $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha} | \mathbf{d})$.

First, let $\boldsymbol{\omega}_n$ be the vector of galaxy properties (flux, size, centroid, and shape) characterizing the n th galaxy in our sample, and $\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n$ be the sheared properties.⁴ Specifically, our chosen ellipticity definition (Section 4.4) has the following response to shear [C. Seitz & P. Schneider \(1997\)](#):

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}' \equiv h_{\mathbf{g}}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \mathbf{g}}{1 + \mathbf{g}^* \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}, \quad (4.4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'$ is the sheared ellipticity, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the intrinsic ellipticity of the galaxy, and $h_{\mathbf{g}}$ is the invertible ‘shear’ transformation function. Now let $\boldsymbol{\phi}_i$ denote the vector of galaxy properties

⁴We do not model the effects of magnification and exclude it from our simulations, so that we can assume that cosmic shear \mathbf{g} only impacts galaxy ellipticity.

besides the shapes, ignoring magnification we have:

$$\begin{aligned}\boldsymbol{\omega}_n &= (\boldsymbol{\phi}_n, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n) \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}'_n &= (\boldsymbol{\phi}'_n, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_n) = (\boldsymbol{\phi}_n, h_{\mathbf{g}}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n)).\end{aligned}\tag{4.5}$$

We can evaluate likelihood of an image \mathbf{d}_n given the corresponding properties $\boldsymbol{\omega}_n$ of the galaxy in that image. Given that most objects for lensing are background dominated by a high-count sky level, we use the following Gaussian approximation to the Poisson distribution:

$$\log \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n | \boldsymbol{\omega}_n, \mathbf{g}) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{pixels}}} \frac{(d_{np} - \bar{d}_{np}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_n, \mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\pi}))^2}{b} + C,\tag{4.6}$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{d}}$ is the noiseless parametric model for galaxies convolved with the PSF $\boldsymbol{\pi}$, and C is a constant. In our chosen simulation setup the variance in every pixel is $b = 1$.⁵

In the context of this work, we require that shearing the galaxy models used to fit objects is equivalent to redrawing the models with the sheared parameters transformed as per Equation 4.4. This is not true for all possible ways to parameterize models. Under this assumption, the likelihood can be rewritten as:

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n | \boldsymbol{\omega}_n, \mathbf{g}) = \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n | \boldsymbol{\omega}'_n).\tag{4.7}$$

Our goal is to write down a tractable expression for the likelihood $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d} | \mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$, which will then allow us to run an MCMC to sample \mathbf{g} and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. We start by introducing the *sheared* galaxy properties by removing the marginalization:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d} | \mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) &= \prod_{n=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n | \mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \\ &= \prod_{n=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} \int d\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n \mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n, \mathbf{d}_n | \mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}),\end{aligned}\tag{4.8}$$

where the first lines comes from the fact that the images are conditionally independent of each other given \mathbf{g} and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ (see Figure 4.2). Next, we use the rules of conditional probability

⁵We currently ignore nearby pixel noise covariances from image coadding, unresolved background objects, or detector artifacts. In principle, these effects could be modeled and added to the likelihood. These extensions are left for future work.

to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) &= \prod_{n=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} \int d\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n \mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n|\mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n|\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n, \mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \\ &= \prod_{n=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} \int d\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n \mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n|\mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n|\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n).\end{aligned}\tag{4.9}$$

For the second line we note that conditioning on the sheared galaxy properties $\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n$ is redundant with conditioning alongside the shear \mathbf{g} , and the galaxy properties' hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ are irrelevant once $\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n$ is known. This expression for the likelihood remains impractical given the large dimensional integral over galaxy properties that would need to be performed at every step of the \mathbf{g} and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ chain. We instead follow the approach in [M. D. Schneider et al. \(2015\)](#) and introduce the *interim posterior*:

$$\mathcal{P}_0(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n|\mathbf{d}_n) = \frac{1}{Z_n} \mathcal{P}_0(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n) \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n|\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n),\tag{4.10}$$

where $\mathcal{P}_0(\cdot)$ denotes the *interim prior* and Z_n is a normalization constant. The interim prior on measured galaxy properties can be chosen for computational convenience and does not need to be similar to the true prior. However, $\mathcal{P}_0(\cdot)$ must have the same domain as the true prior $\mathcal{P}(\cdot|\boldsymbol{\alpha})$, and inference becomes more efficient the closer these two are.

We then substitute $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}_n|\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n)$ from Equation 4.10 into Equation 4.9 to obtain:

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \prod_{n=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} Z_n \int d\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n \frac{\mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n|\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{g})}{\mathcal{P}_0(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n)} \mathcal{P}_0(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n|\mathbf{d}_n).\tag{4.11}$$

Finally, we approximate the integral over $\boldsymbol{\omega}'_n$ of each galaxy with the usual Monte Carlo expression:

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{g}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \approx \prod_{n=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} \frac{Z_n}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_{nk}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{g})}{\mathcal{P}_0(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_{nk})},\tag{4.12}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega}'_{nk}$ are samples from the interim posterior $\mathcal{P}_0(\cdot|\mathbf{d}_n)$ of the n th galaxy, and K is the number of samples from each galaxy. The numerator $\mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_{nk}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{g})$ corresponds to the true

prior of sheared galaxy properties and can be evaluated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}'_{nk}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{g}) &= \mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{nk}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \mathbf{g}) \cdot \left| \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}'_n}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_n} \right| \\
&= \mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{nk}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \cdot \left| \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}'_n}{\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_n} \right| \\
&= \mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{nk}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \cdot \left| \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_n}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n} \right|,
\end{aligned} \tag{4.13}$$

where in the first equality we changed variables in the probability density and picked up the absolute value of the determinant of the Jacobian $|\partial \boldsymbol{\omega}'_n / \partial \boldsymbol{\omega}_n|$. For the second equality we use the fact that the unsheared (intrinsic) galaxy properties samples, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{nk}$, do not depend on the shear. Finally, the last equality uses the fact that only ellipticities transform when shear is applied. This Jacobian can be evaluated with Equation 4.4.

The density $\mathcal{P}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{nk}|\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ is the true prior on intrinsic galaxy properties and could either be learned from a subset of high-SNR galaxy observations (i.e., deep fields) or jointly with shear using the same wide-field images. In Section 4.6.2 we demonstrate that our framework can learn the parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ of this distribution alongside shear using the same set of images.

4.5.3 Phases and Settings

The likelihood in Equation 4.12 enables splitting shear inference in two phases:

- **Image Sampling Phase:** We sample the interim posterior (Equation 4.10) of each galaxy via MCMC independently to obtain galaxy property samples $\{\boldsymbol{\omega}'_{nk}\}$ using the interim prior \mathcal{P}_0 as the prior. These samples only need to be obtained once under the interim prior and are fixed thereafter.
- **Shear Sampling Phase:** We run a MCMC chain to jointly infer the shear \mathbf{g} and the hyperparameters of the intrinsic galaxy property distributions $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ by evaluating the likelihood in Equation 4.12 using the samples from the image sampling phase: $\{\boldsymbol{\omega}'_{nk}\}$.

We run four different ‘Settings’ of these two phases on our dataset of 320k exponential galaxies:

- shapes-fixed
- shapes-free
- all-fixed
- all-free

Setting	Image Sampling Phase		Shear Sampling Phase	
	Sampled	Fixed	Sampled	Fixed
shapes-fixed	$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2$	$f, s, \Delta x, \Delta y$	g_1, g_2	σ_e
shapes-free	$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2$	$f, s, \Delta x, \Delta y$	g_1, g_2, σ_e	-
all-fixed	$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, f, s, \Delta x, \Delta y$	-	g_1, g_2	$\sigma_e, a_f, \mu_f, \sigma_f, \mu_s, \sigma_s$
all-free	$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, f, s, \Delta x, \Delta y$	-	$g_1, g_2, \sigma_e, a_f, \mu_f, \sigma_f, \mu_s, \sigma_s$	-

Table 4.1: **Free and fixed parameters in each setting and phase.** In this table we summarize the four shear inference settings tested in this work. In the image sampling phase, galaxy properties are sampled by fitting individual galaxy images. In the shear sampling phase, shear is sampled alongside the parameters of the intrinsic galaxy property distributions. Each setting has different properties that are sampled or fixed to their true value in the corresponding phases. The definition of every parameter can be found in Section 4.4. For more detail on the settings see Section 4.5.3.

Here, the prefix ‘**shapes**’ means that only galaxy ellipticities are sampled in the image sampling phase. On the other hand, ‘**all**’ denotes that all galaxy properties (flux, shape, size, and centroid) are sampled in this phase. Next, the suffix ‘**fixed**’ means only the shear is sampled while the galaxy prior hyperparameters α are fixed to their true values in the shear sampling phase. For instance, in **shapes-fixed**, the shape noise σ_e is fixed to its true value used for generating the galaxy images ($\sigma_e = 0.2$), and used when evaluating the true prior on the shear likelihood in Equation 4.12. Finally, ‘**free**’ means that the relevant hyperparameters of the true galaxy prior are sampled alongside shear. We test all combinations of these choices for the image sampling phase and the shear sampling phase in Section 4.6. These settings are also summarized in Table 4.1.

In the next section we discuss the implementation details of the MCMC chains in each phase.

4.5.4 Implementation

Given the billions of galaxies that might need to be analyzed for weak lensing analysis in the era of Stage-IV surveys, our shear algorithms need to be highly efficient and scalable. The main bottleneck for our shear inference framework is the image sampling phase, as it requires one MCMC chain per galaxy in our dataset, which could easily become unfeasible with unoptimized chains.

We make our Bayesian framework efficient by leveraging differentiable forward modeling of galaxy images and GPU acceleration. Our forward model of galaxies is implemented in JAX

(J. Bradbury et al., 2018) and is provided by the python library `JAX-GalSim`⁶ `JAX-GalSim` is a partial reimplemention in `JAX` of the popular weak-lensing simulation package `GALSIM` (B. T. P. Rowe et al., 2015). `JAX-GalSim` does not currently contain the full feature suite of `GALSIM`, but available features have been tested using the unit tests available within `GALSIM`, and are correct to about the same level of accuracy. Specifically, `JAX-GalSim` currently allows for rendering a core set of the parametric models available in `GALSIM` and convolutions. In our experiments, we have used `GALSIM` to create our simulated galaxy dataset and `JAX-GalSim` for the forward model to evaluate the image likelihood (Equation 4.6). The fact that our shear measurement algorithm outputs accurate shear measurements (Section 4.6) indicates that these two codes are largely numerically interchangeable in the regime we are using them.

Using `JAX-GalSim` enables us to perform all image rendering operations in a GPU and parallelize over multiple galaxies simultaneously via `jax.vmap`. Furthermore, since our models are automatically differentiable, the likelihoods we use for MCMC sampling (Equations 4.6 and 4.12) are also automatically differentiable. Thus, we can take advantage of gradient-based MCMC like Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) (R. M. Neal et al., 2011) and the popular extension: No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) (M. D. Hoffman et al., 2014). These gradient-based approaches are known to exhibit higher efficiency and faster convergence for high dimensional distributions or those with complex geometries compared to classical random-walk MCMC (M. Betancourt, 2017). For all our experiments we use the `BlackJAX` (A. Cabezaz et al., 2024) implementation of the NUTS algorithm, which is also implemented in `JAX` and therefore enables our entire sampling procedure to run exclusively in GPUs.

To be concrete, in the image sampling phase we run NUTS chains in parallel within the same GPU. Each chain runs 500 warmup steps of dual averaging (Y. Nesterov, 2009) to optimize the step size.⁷ The target distribution for the chains is the likelihood in Equation 4.6 multiplied times the interim prior. We choose the interim prior $\mathcal{P}_0(\cdot)$ distribution to factorize

⁶This library is publicly available at <https://github.com/GalSim-developers/JAX-GalSim>, and was developed by the authors of this work.

⁷`BlackJAX` attempts to follow the STAN implementation (B. Carpenter et al., 2017) of this algorithm as closely as possible.

over galaxy properties and be relatively uninformative:

$$\begin{aligned}
\log_{10} f &\sim U(-1, 9) \\
\log_{10} s &\sim U(-2, 1) \\
\Delta x &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{xy} = 0.5) \\
\Delta y &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{xy} = 0.5) \\
\varepsilon &\sim p(\varepsilon; \sigma_e = 0.3) \\
\phi &\sim U(0, \pi)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.14}$$

where Δx and Δy are deviations from the true galaxy centroid. Importantly, we sample $(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2)$ rather than (ε, ϕ) directly. The joint density is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{P}(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2) &= \mathcal{P}(\varepsilon, \phi) \left| \frac{\partial(\varepsilon, \phi)}{\partial(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2)} \right| \propto f_e(\varepsilon) / \varepsilon \\
&\propto (1 - \varepsilon^2)^2 \exp(-\varepsilon^2 / 2\sigma_e^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.15}$$

where $f_e(\cdot)$ is the ellipticity magnitude prior density in Equation 4.3 and $|\partial(\varepsilon, \phi) / \partial(\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2)|$ is the determinant of the Jacobian determined by the transformation in Equation 4.2.

We produce 300 samples of galaxy properties following the warmup for all our experiments (samples produced during the warmup are discarded). We initialize the chains for each n galaxy as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{n,\text{init}} &= \sum_{p=1}^{n_{\text{pixels}}} d_{np} \\
\log_{10} r_{n,\text{init}} &\sim U(\log_{10} r_n - 0.015, \log_{10} r_n + 0.015) \\
\Delta x_{n,\text{init}} &= 0 \\
\Delta y_{n,\text{init}} &= 0 \\
\varepsilon_{n,1,\text{init}} &\sim U(\varepsilon_{n,1} - 0.1, \varepsilon_{n,1} + 0.1) \\
\varepsilon_{n,2,\text{init}} &\sim U(\varepsilon_{n,2} - 0.1, \varepsilon_{n,2} + 0.1)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.16}$$

In other words, the flux is initialized as the sum of the image pixels, the size and shapes are initialized with small balls around the true value to represent some degree of measurement error, and the initial deviation from the true centroid is assumed to be 0. The NUTS chains use a `max_num_doublings` parameter of 5 for all galaxies.⁸ For settings `shapes-fixed` and

⁸This parameter controls the maximum number of times the NUTS trajectory is doubled before returning if no U-Turn or divergence has occurred. See (M. D. Hoffman et al., 2014) for more details.

shapes-free, we only use the galaxy ellipticities to infer shear. In these cases, all of the other galaxy properties are fixed to their true values when running the MCMC chains and ellipticities are initialized in the same way as above.

For the shear sampling phase, we use the likelihood in Equation 4.12 to sample the shear \mathbf{g} and the galaxy properties' hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. The true prior in the numerator is defined by the data-generating process in Section 4.4. The interim prior in the denominator is defined in Equation 4.10. It is critical to include the Jacobian factor for galaxy ellipticities in the numerator as shown in Equation 4.13.

For settings **shapes-free** and **all-free**, we use the following uninformative hyperpriors for the sampled $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_e &\sim U[10^{-4}, 1] \\
 \mu_f &\sim U[-2, 6] \\
 \sigma_f &\sim U[0, 2] \\
 a_f &\sim U[-100, 100] \\
 \mu_s &\sim U[-2, 2] \\
 \sigma_s &\sim U[0, 0.5]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.17}$$

where μ_f , σ_f , and a_f are the mean, sigma, and shape of the skew normal distribution for log-fluxes, and μ_s and σ_s are the mean and sigma of the normal distribution of log-size (see Section 4.4). In all settings, for estimating shear \mathbf{g} , we use a uniform prior on the unit disk. We note that the true prior on deviations from the true centroid Δx and Δy are the same as the interim prior by construction. Thus, their contributions to the likelihood cancel on a sample-by-sample basis and we completely ignore the centroid samples and their priors in shear sampling phase.

Finally, for the shear sampling phase we use a `max_num_doublings` of 2 for settings **shapes-fixed** and **all-fixed**. We use a value of 3 for setting **shapes-free** and 7 for **all-free** given their higher dimensionality. We keep 500 warmup steps for all cases, except in **all-free** where we use 1000 steps.

4.5.5 Multiplicative bias and shape noise cancellation

In the context of cosmological surveys, the requirement for the accuracy and precision of shear measurements is typically expressed in what is known as *multiplicative m* and *additive c* biases. Given a shear estimator $\hat{\mathbf{g}}$ and the true shear applied \mathbf{g} these quantities are defined

by the following equation:

$$\hat{\mathbf{g}} = (1 + m)\mathbf{g} + c, \quad (4.18)$$

which assumes that shears are weak enough that we can typically neglect higher-order terms. The requirement for Stage-IV dark energy surveys on shear is $|m| < 2 \times 10^{-3}$ (R. Mandelbaum, 2018).

We employ the shape noise cancellation trick introduced in (A. Pujol et al., 2019) to reduce the number of simulations needed to verify that our shear inference method fulfills this requirement. This trick consists of running two simulations with the exact same galaxy properties and pixel noise, but one simulation uses a small positive shear and the other uses the opposite shear. Next, by combining the shear estimator obtained from each simulation in a specific way, the multiplicative bias is estimated such that errors from shape and pixel noise are approximately canceled out. Reducing the impact of noise on our estimators reduces the total number of simulations that are needed.

Assuming that we apply a shear with only a non-zero g_1 component (0.02 for all our experiments), the multiplicative m and additive c biases can be estimated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{m} &= \frac{\hat{g}_{+,1} - \hat{g}_{-,1}}{2|g|} - 1 \\ \hat{c} &= \frac{\hat{g}_{+,2} + \hat{g}_{-,2}}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (4.19)$$

In our case, we choose our shear estimator to be the mean of the posterior $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{g}|\mathbf{d})$,⁹ and create two datasets \mathbf{d}_+ and \mathbf{d}_- with the exact same 320k galaxies in both sets of images, same noise realization, but with the opposite shear applied.

We also approximate the error on both \hat{m} and \hat{c} by creating independent subsets of galaxies and applying the shape noise cancellation procedure on each of the subsets independently. We divide the 320k galaxies into 500 equally sized subsets. The error on the mean multiplicative bias is then the error on the mean of these subsets (i.e., the standard deviation of these subsets divided by the square-root of the number of subsets).¹⁰ Our final estimate of the mean multiplicative bias uses the full shear posterior from all galaxies jointly, not the subsets.

⁹We have verified that none of the conclusions of this work change if the median of the posterior is used as the shear estimator instead of the mean. In general, our resulting shear posteriors (see Figure 4.6.2) visually seem very close to a Gaussian distribution. So we do not expect large differences their mean, median, or mode.

¹⁰Another approach to estimating the error on m is the bootstrap technique, where the full set of galaxies is resampled with replacement into sets of the same total size. This procedure is a more precise and computationally expensive way of computing the error for the multiplicative and additive bias. We compare the error of the subset and bootstrap approach (using 200 total bootstrap resamplings) for settings `shapes-fixed` and `all-fixed` with a smaller subset of galaxies (10,000) and find that the estimated errors are consistent in these cases.

4.6 Results

We present our results in this section. In Section 4.6.1 we evaluate individual galaxy chains on a subset of the full dataset. Specifically, we look at their convergence and sampling efficiency. Next, in Section 4.6.2 we present examples of shear and true prior’s parameters posteriors obtained with our method. Finally, in Section 4.6.3 we present the multiplicative bias of our method in the four different settings outlined in Section 4.5.4.

4.6.1 Quality and Efficiency of Individual Galaxy Chains

We focus on evaluating the samples of galaxy properties in the image sampling phase with all galaxy properties free. These corresponds to settings `all-fixed` and `all-free` (Section 4.5.3). Every chain uses the likelihood given by Equation 4.6, the prior used is the interim prior from Equation 4.14, and each chain is initialized independently using the procedure in Equation 4.16. All NUTS chains in this section use 500 warmup steps, 500 sampling steps, and an `max_num_doublings` of 5.

We first use a random subset of 10k exponential galaxies from the full dataset to evaluate the convergence. For this purpose we use the \hat{R} metric (A. Gelman & D. B. Rubin, 1992), which compares the intra- and inter-variance of the chains to assess convergence. According to the STAN manual, a value of \hat{R} larger than 1.05 suggests that the chains have not mixed well (B. Carpenter et al., 2017). To obtain an \hat{R} estimate for each galaxy we run four independent chains on the same image with different initializations (sampled independently from Equation 4.16), and each using a different random seed. We use the BlackJAX implementation of the \hat{R} metric with the `potential_scale_reduction` function. We find that all the \hat{R} value for all galaxies in our dataset (which has a minimum SNR of 12) is < 1.01 .¹¹

Next we evaluate the efficiency of sampling galaxy properties by calculating the time taken to produced a given number of *effective samples* in a A100 GPU.¹² We define the number of effective samples using the *effective sample size* (or ESS) (e.g., A. Gelman et al., 1995), which uses the autocorrelation length of the chain to estimate how many independent samples are produced. We summarize the results in Figure 4.3, where we show the number of galaxies processed per second for a given number of effective samples and a given number of galaxies being sampled in parallel on one A100 GPU. For a given number of chains, the

¹¹We separately evaluated the convergence on a dataset with SNR values below 12 and find that a significant portion of galaxy chains do not converge. This is why we choose the skew normal log-flux distribution in Equation 4.1, which produces an SNR distribution with minimum value of 12 (Figure 4.1).

¹²This GPU has a total memory of about 40GB, which allows us to run in parallel (with `jax.vmap`) over 5000 individual galaxy NUTS chains.

time is computed by picking that number of random galaxies from our dataset and running independent chains in parallel on a single GPU. Additionally, an overall slowdown factor is applied across all cases which is determined by the average relative ESS across all parameters and galaxies in the sample of 10k galaxies used for the convergence results.

Figure 4.3: **Efficiency of sampling galaxy properties.** We show the number of galaxies processed per second for a given number effective samples obtained per galaxy and a given number of galaxies (blue to red gradient in lines) being sampled in parallel in a single A100 GPU. Producing zero effective samples corresponds to warming up the chains, which takes a non-negligible amount of time. See Section 4.6.1 for more discussion of this figure.

From this figure we see that the sampling efficiency increases as more galaxies are sampled in parallel in the same GPU. However, the efficiency increases very slowly once at least 500 chains are ran in parallel, even though the GPU has enough memory for additional chains. This is surprising as chains are running independently and in parallel on the GPU, so naively we would expect that the efficiency keeps increasing until the GPU saturates. The issue is that the NUTS sampler requires a variable number of likelihood evaluations at each step, which means that all chains need to wait for the slowest chain at each iteration (P. Sountsov et al., 2024). This problem becomes more severe as the `max_num_doublings` parameter is increased.

4.6.2 Posteriors on Shear and True prior parameters

In this section, we show examples of the posteriors on shear \mathbf{g} and the intrinsic distribution hyperparameters α inferred by our method on our exponential galaxy dataset.

First, in Figure 4.4 we compare the shear posteriors inferred in settings **all-fixed** and **all-free** applied to the same dataset of 320k exponential galaxies with positive shear applied. In **all-free**, the shear is inferred alongside the intrinsic galaxy distribution hyperparameters α . In both settings, we use the same samples of galaxy properties obtained from the image sampling phase to sample posteriors in the shear sampling phase. We see that the shear posteriors contours from each setting seem consistent with each other. Both contours seem centered at the black dashed line plotted, which corresponds to the true shear value plus the mean ellipticity of the galaxy distribution. Importantly, we do not expect the contours to be centered at the true shear value, since they represent a single realization of the posterior inferred from a dataset with a finite amount of shape noise. The width of the contours, however, accounts for shape noise so that the true shear value should be contained within them in most cases. For both of these posteriors, we find that the true shear value is within 2σ of their mean.

Next, in Figure 4.5 we see the rest of the posterior contours inferred in **all-free** for intrinsic galaxy distribution hyperparameters α . These are comprised of the skew normal parameters for the log-flux, the normal parameters for the log-size, and the shape noise σ_e . For all variables we see that the true hyperparameters fall roughly within the 2σ contours of each posterior. All of the variables also seem uncorrelated, except for the parameters of the skew normal distribution on fluxes. We also see that most hyperparameter posteriors are very narrow. For instance, the scatter in the posterior of the shape noise parameter σ_e is approximately 0.125% of the true value of this parameter (0.2).¹³ The fact that these parameters are so precisely determined explains why the width between posterior shear contours in settings **all-fixed** and **all-free** (Figure 4.4) is essentially the same.

Figures 4.4 and 4.5 demonstrate that we can successfully estimate shear and the intrinsic hyperparameters jointly on the same images without a significant increase in the error of the shear inferred. In the next section, we explore the multiplicative bias of our shear inference method in all settings.

¹³The reason that σ_e is so precisely determined is that most of the galaxy shape data is driven by shape noise.

Figure 4.4: **Comparison of shear posteriors.** In this plot we compare the inferred shear posterior 1σ and 2σ contours obtained from our method applied to our dataset of 320k isolated exponential galaxies with $g_1 = 0.02$ and $g_2 = 0$ true shear applied. The blue contours is the shear posterior inferred in setting **all-fixed**: the true prior of intrinsic galaxy properties is fixed and known, and only the shear is inferred. The green contours is the shear posterior in setting **all-free**: we jointly infer the shear alongside the hyperparameters of the intrinsic galaxy property distributions. The black dashed lines correspond to the true shear value plus the mean ellipticity of the dataset. See Section 4.6.2 for more details of this figure.

4.6.3 Multiplicative Bias

In this section we present the multiplicative and additive bias estimated for our shear inference algorithm. These biases and their errors are estimated using the shape noise cancellation trick. Their errors are estimated with a subset approach. See Section 4.5.5 for details.

In Table 4.2 we show the results for each of our four settings. For each type of bias, the first number corresponds to the mean multiplicative bias and its error is the 3σ uncertainty in the mean. We see that the multiplicative and additive biases are consistent with zero and within the Stage-IV weak lensing requirements for all cases. The error on multiplicative bias seems to be larger for the cases when the true prior hyperparameters are free (cases **shapes-free** and **all-free**) compared to when these are fixed (cases **shapes-fixed** and **all-fixed**) as expected. The additive bias error seems to be approximately the same in all settings.

Figure 4.5: **Posteriors of the hyperparameters of distributions of intrinsic galaxy properties.** In this contour plot, we show 1σ and 2σ contours of the posterior of hyperparameters of galaxy properties' distributions. Specifically, σ_ϵ corresponds to the scatter of the intrinsic ellipticity magnitude distribution (Equation 4.3), μ_f and σ_f are the mean and sigma of the lognormal distribution of fluxes, and μ_{hlr} and σ_{hlr} are the mean and sigma of the lognormal distribution of half-light-radii (see Section 4.4). These hyperparameters are sampled jointly with shear using the same set of samples of galaxy properties. For more details see Section 4.6.2.

Setting	Multiplicative Bias $m/10^{-3}$	Additive Bias $c/10^{-3}$
shapes-fixed	-0.361 ± 0.758	-0.176 ± 1.000
shapes-free	-0.267 ± 0.946	-0.172 ± 0.999
all-fixed	-0.177 ± 0.778	-0.155 ± 1.004
all-free	-0.313 ± 1.330	-0.160 ± 1.004

Table 4.2: **Multiplicative and additive shear bias.** In this table we present the main results of this work, the multiplicative and additive bias (in units of 10^{-3}) of our shear inference method in four different settings. In all cases the shear inference method is applied on the same dataset of 320k galaxies generated as detailed in Section 4.4. The mean multiplicative and additive bias is reported alongside with its 3σ error, which is estimated by dividing galaxies into subsets. Each setting samples different sets of galaxy properties (`shapes` or `all`), and either fixes or samples the hyperparameters of the intrinsic distributions of galaxy properties (`fixed` or `free`). See Section 4.5.3 and Table 4.1 for more details on these settings. See Section 4.6.3 for additional discussion on this figure.

4.7 Conclusions

In this work, we have provided a modern re-implementation of the shear inference framework in (M. D. Schneider et al., 2015) in the case that the PSF and sky background are known. We have rigorously tested our approach in a dataset of LSST-like images of parametric, isolated galaxies and measured its multiplicative bias using the shape noise cancellation procedure in A. Pujol et al. (2019). We find that our algorithm’s multiplicative bias is consistent with LSST requirements. In addition, our approach leverages GPUs, differentiable forward modeling, and gradient-based samplers to improve the sampling efficiency of individual galaxy properties.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- We present an alternative derivation of the shear inference formalism from M. D. Schneider et al. (2015) in the special case of known PSF and background (Section 4.5.2).
- We present an efficient method to sample galaxy properties using model-fitting by taking advantage of a gradient-based sampler (NUTS), GPUs, and a differentiable model of parametric galaxies enabled by JAX-GalSim. Our implementation produces one effective sample per galaxy in 0.6 milliseconds after a burn-in phase that takes 0.26 seconds per galaxy using a single GPU (Section 4.6.1).
- We perform rigorous testing of our shear inference algorithm and use the shape noise cancellation trick (A. Pujol et al., 2019) to estimate its multiplicative bias. We use a

simple simulation with realistic shape and pixel noise levels consisting of 320k isolated parametric galaxies. The properties of these galaxies are drawn from simple parametric distributions. If the true prior on intrinsic galaxy properties is known, we find a multiplicative bias m of $(-0.177 \pm 0.778) \times 10^{-3}$ (3σ confidence). If the form of the prior is known, but its parameters are unknown, we find $m = (-0.313 \pm 1.330) \times 10^{-3}$ (3σ confidence). In both cases m is consistent with zero and satisfies the requirements for a Stage-IV dark energy survey $|m| < 2 \times 10^{-3}$. Our additive biases are also consistent with zero (Section 4.6.3).

- We demonstrate that our method accurately infers the hyperparameters of simple galaxy property distributions alongside with shear without incurring on multiplicative bias (Section 4.6.2 and 4.6.3). This is an important step towards the applicability of the method in real data, where the distribution of galaxy properties will not be known.

Our approach is a new Bayesian shear measurement algorithm based on framework from [M. D. Schneider et al. \(2015\)](#). Other recent Bayesian shear measurement approaches include Bayesian Fourier Domain (BFD) ([G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong, 2014](#); [G. M. Bernstein et al., 2016](#)) and LENSMC ([Euclid Collaboration et al., 2024](#)).

The Bayesian Fourier Domain (BFD) method ([G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong, 2014](#); [E. S. Sheldon, 2014](#); [G. M. Bernstein et al., 2016](#)) compresses images into a vector of moments \mathbf{M} measured in Fourier space, and derives an analytical expression for the likelihood of these moments $P(\mathbf{M}|\mathbf{g})$ to ultimately arrive at the shear posterior. Our approach differs from BFD in that we forward model galaxies in real space and use samples of the corresponding galaxy properties to perform shear inference. We require a model for the effect of shear on these galaxy properties, which in the context of this work is provided by Equation 4.4. On the other hand, BFD compresses the pixel information \mathbf{d} of galaxies into Fourier space moments \mathbf{M} , for which it is possible to analytically model the effect of shear. BFD should be less sensitive to model bias than a model-fitting approach such as ours, since its fundamental ‘modeling’ assumption is that the true distribution of galaxy moments is equal to the moment distribution of galaxies in a deep sub-survey. However, because BFD works in Fourier space, it currently cannot account for galaxy blends or pixel data that has been contaminated by cosmic rays or defects. Our method can in theory include these effects by introducing them in our forward model.

LENSMC shares more similarities with the approach presented here, as LENSMC fits galaxy images and corresponding ellipticity samples are used to estimate shear. This method is an extension of an older Bayesian shear algorithm: LENSFIT ([L. Miller et al., 2007](#); [T. D. Kitching et al., 2008](#); [L. Miller et al., 2013](#)). LENSMC introduces a clever marginalization

which reduces the dimensionality of the MCMC sampling and improves efficiency when fitting isolated galaxy images. Galaxy blends are handled separately by fitting the corresponding galaxies jointly. However, the final shear estimator is based on a heuristic re-weighting of ellipticities, does not use all galaxy properties, and does not return a shear posterior. In contrast, since our method is based on [M. D. Schneider et al. \(2015\)](#)’s framework, it is statistically rigorous and returns a full shear posterior.

Future work on this method will aim to enable its application on modern survey data. There are several significant challenges remaining. One of them is to account for selection shear biases. These biases arise when the set of galaxies selected for shear estimation depends on the shapes of these galaxies ([E. S. Sheldon & E. M. Huff, 2017](#); [R. Mandelbaum, 2018](#)). In this case, the ellipticity distribution of galaxies in the sample will not follow the original distribution, since galaxy orientation is no longer uniformly distributed. Our current implementation cannot account for this type of bias since our prior distribution on ellipticities explicitly assumes that orientation angles are uniformly distributed (Section 4.4). One potential way to handle this bias is making the distribution of ellipticities more flexible to allow for skewness, and fitting the parameters of this distribution jointly with shear. An important type of selection bias is detection shear bias ([E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020](#)). This bias occurs because the output of standard detection algorithms depends on the shear applied, which leads to a selection effect. Another related source of bias is *blending* ([P. Melchior et al., 2021](#)), which refers to visually overlapping light sources in astronomical images. If all the sources in the galaxy blend are accurately detected, we could account for blends by jointly fitting the galaxies in the group during the image sampling phase. This is similar to the approach used in LENSIMC. Even if the centroid of every source is perfectly known, jointly fitting blended galaxies becomes more difficult, due to the correlated nature of their parameters and higher-dimensionality. It remains to be seen if our current sampling algorithms can efficiently handle this more difficult setting. One complication in handling blended galaxies arises if these are too blended to be detected individually, so-called *unrecognized blends* ([W. A. Dawson et al., 2016](#); [E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020](#)). In this case, our parametric model of galaxies cannot account for the resulting ‘hybrid source’, and measured ellipticities will likely not transform under shear via Equation 4.4. This could lead to model shear biases ([G. M. Bernstein, 2010](#); [L. Voigt & S. Bridle, 2010](#)). Finally, there is no finite-parameter model that describes the light profiles of galaxies in the universe ([G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong, 2014](#)). Thus, fitting survey data with a parametric model of galaxies could cause model bias. We plan to use COSMOS Real galaxies in GALSIM ([R. Mandelbaum et al., 2012](#)) in a future paper to quantify model shear bias with our method. One possible way to mitigate model bias would be to adopt a more flexible galaxy model learned from the data itself via machine

learning (F. Lanusse et al., 2021; B. Arcelin et al., 2021; B. Remy et al., 2022; B. Biswas et al., 2024).

An additional important challenge comes from the fact that our method requires the true prior on galaxy properties to evaluate the shear likelihood (Equation 4.12). In this work we have assumed that the true prior on galaxy properties is known or that it has a simple form, and shown that we can learn its parameters from the same set of data used to infer shear in the latter case. In real surveys, the prior will not necessarily be parametric so another approach is needed. M. D. Schneider et al. (2015) suggests using a flexible distribution based on Dirichlet processes to learn the distribution of ellipticities and even accommodate different subsets of galaxies (e.g., blue vs. red galaxies) having different parameter distributions. Another flexible model for learning the prior might be normalizing flows (NFs) (I. Kobyzev et al., 2020; G. Papamakarios et al., 2021), which are based on neural networks and have been shown to learn even high-dimensional and multi-modal distributions. Regardless of the flexible model we pick to learn the intrinsic galaxy property distribution, there are two ways we can employ them to perform shear inference. First, we could apply them to learn the prior from a low-noise subset of the data, i.e., deep fields. This is the approach employed in BFD (G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong (2014); G. M. Bernstein et al. (2016)) and has the disadvantage that sample variance must be accounted for. Another approach is learning the shear alongside the parameters of the true prior using the same subset of data as demonstrated in this work. However, this approach will become more difficult as the flexibility of the distributions used increases. A comprehensive study and comparison of both approaches will be carried out in the context of simulations to design a strategy that could be used for real survey data.

Finally, another avenue for development is speeding up our galaxy property sampling. We have chosen to use No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) (M. D. Hoffman et al., 2014) because it has been shown empirically to be successful in a diverse set of target distributions (M. Betancourt, 2017) and its JAX implementation is available in BlackJAX (A. Cabezas et al., 2024). However, given the adaptive nature of NUTS, different chains require a different number of likelihood evaluations. So that when running multiple chains in parallel in a single GPU, each chain will need to wait for all the others to complete a given step before advancing to the next. This makes NUTS a suboptimal sampling algorithm for GPUs (P. Sountsov et al., 2024) as demonstrated in Section 4.3. We plan to explore other recently developed approaches for gradient-based sampling that are designed to be GPU compatible to further improve the efficiency of our inference (M. Hoffman et al., 2021; M. D. Hoffman & P. Sountsov, 2022).

Data Availability

The code to reproduce all of the data and plots presented in this work can be found in the following public GitHub repository: <https://github.com/LSSTDESC/BPD>. The repository for JAX-GalSim, which provides the differentiable model for parametric galaxies used in our results, is also publicly available and can be installed from the following repository: <https://github.com/GalSim-developers/JAX-GalSim>.

CHAPTER 5

Closing Remarks

Stage-IV cosmological surveys such as LSST will offer unprecedented amount of statistical power to constrain the dark energy equation of state. Combining multiple probes and experiments will be necessary to achieve their sub-percent precision goal. One of the most powerful probes of dark energy is weak lensing, the subtle distortion of light rays from distant galaxies due to the matter along its path to us. Weak lensing has been successfully used in previous surveys such as DES ([Dark Energy Survey Collaboration et al., 2016](#)) to constrain dark energy properties. However, modern surveys will face new challenges. As the statistical power of cosmological experiments has improved, many previously ignored sources of lensing systematics need to be addressed so that the corresponding uncertainty does not dominate the error budget.

Weak lensing is quantified in dark energy surveys using cosmic shear, which refers to the deviation of observed galaxy shapes from pure random orientations. Cosmic shear directly traces the integrated (baryon and dark) matter density along the line of sight. Cosmology can thus be directly constrained by constructing large enough ‘shear maps’ using survey observations. Stage-IV surveys have placed the stringent requirement on algorithms to measure cosmic shear with an accuracy of 1 part in a 1000 to achieve their scientific goals. This is complicated by a wide variety of existing observational systematics including low SNR galaxies (noise bias), selections or cuts made on the galaxy sample that changes the measured ellipticity distribution (selection bias), the realistic morphology of galaxies including ellipticity gradients (model bias), PSF misestimation, chromatic-related biases, among others. Our shear measurement algorithms will require extensive testing to demonstrate that they can handle the systematics present in astronomical images.

Blending is one systematic that has gained increased importance in the context of LSST. The increased depth of this survey means that the number density of potentially observable sources will also increase dramatically. Specifically, it is forecasted that LSST will build a catalog of over 40 billion objects (galaxies and stars), have an effective number density of 26 arcmin^{-2} (compared to less than 10 arcmin^{-2} for DES Y6), and probe approximately

5 Gpc³ of volume (10 times more than DES Y6). In turn, this increase in density means that the likelihood of any two observable sources overlapping will be much larger than previous surveys. It is expected that the number of sources blended to some degree will comprise more than half of the LSST survey – discarding more than half of the statistical power of the survey is not an option.

Much of this thesis is devoted to making progress towards the “blending problem”. In Chapter 2, we developed a new software package (BTK) to study the impact of blending in a controlled way using image simulations. This package generates small-scale simulations of blended galaxies, provides a framework for standardizing and comparing deblending algorithms, and includes a library of metrics to perform said comparisons. This package was created through contributions from many members of the LSST-DESC collaboration, and has been used to train and evaluate new ML deblenders developed within the collaboration (e.g., [B. Biswas et al., 2024](#)). There are several possible extensions for BTK. First, this software could be expanded to include more realistic image simulations of galaxy blends. Specifically, we have not simulated all the effects that can interact with blending, including: stars, correlated pixel noise, variation in galaxy morphology in different color bands, and galaxy clustering. Second, additional metrics could be implemented to enable more types of science analyses besides those involving simple galaxy properties such as fluxes or centroids. Finally, more off-the-shelf deblending algorithms could be added to the BTK library to enable a more comprehensive comparison with deblenders in development.

In Chapter 3 we applied probabilistic machine learning techniques to implement a novel deblending algorithm: BLISS. BLISS uses neural networks to approximate the posterior of galaxy catalogs from astronomical images. Specifically, BLISS returns probability distributions capturing the uncertainty in counts, centroids, and galaxy properties due to blending and pixel noise. Despite our Bayesian framework, our algorithm is highly computationally efficient after training has been completed. Inference only requires a single forward pass on a neural network which corresponds to a few seconds for megapixel images (in a GPU). We train and evaluate BLISS on LSST-like image simulations, and find significant improvement on recovering the measured flux on images of highly blended galaxies. This work lays the foundation for a method that could be applied in real survey images to (1) improve the estimate of galaxy properties in highly blended systems (2) estimate the uncertainty in measurements due to blending, and (3) propagate this uncertainty to cosmological analysis to reduce systematic errors. The biggest downside of BLISS is that its performance depends heavily on the training data used. In this chapter, we have only evaluated BLISS on training and testing sets that come from the same simulator. Thus, more work needs to be done to understand how the BLISS performance changes when the training and testing data differ

in realistic and important ways. Another important avenue of future work is to extend our algorithm to multi-band image simulations. By using images with multiple bands, we can evaluate the ability of our algorithm to reduce bias in measured galaxy colors, which could translate to improvements in photometric redshift estimates of galaxies in highly blended systems.

Blending will impact cosmic shear measurements by inducing selection, detection, and model biases. Several calibration algorithms have been developed to address these biases, including self-calibration algorithms such as METADETECTION (E. S. Sheldon et al., 2020) and Anacal (X. Li et al., 2023a). One type of blending bias that only recently has been studied in detail is the coupled effect of blending on shear and redshift calibration, which arises due to the majority of blended galaxies being at different redshifts. This effect cannot be currently accounted for by self-calibration methods. N. MacCrann et al. (2022) proposes a calibration method which creates separate image simulations for each tomographic bin used in the survey. They apply this method in the context of DES Y3 and estimate the corresponding multiplicative bias due to this blending effect to be approximately -2% . This bias will likely increase in the context of Stage-IV surveys like LSST given their higher number density. Additionally, it remains to be seen if this simulation-based calibration method is computationally feasible for LSST given the complexity and volume of simulations required. Blending will likely continue to be a daunting challenge for weak lensing surveys and necessitate the development of new and efficient methodologies.

Another perspective on accounting for shear measurement biases is to forward model the relevant sources of systematics and use Bayesian statistics to marginalize the corresponding uncertainty in estimated properties. If the forward model is an accurate representation of the systematics and the posterior is correctly approximated, biases would automatically be calibrated. This is the approach taken by algorithms such as LENSFIT (L. Miller et al., 2007; L. Miller et al., 2013) and LENS_MC (Euclid Collaboration et al., 2024). This method also offers a potential way to handling blending related shear biases. First, the entirety of the blend could be forward modeled to account for the uncertainty in the system’s configuration. Second, although challenging, we could in principle model and infer the redshift and shear of blended galaxies simultaneously. This could alleviate the coupled effect of blending in shear and redshift calibration discussed above. Despite its statistical appeal and potential to mitigate novel systematics, this Bayesian methodology usually suffers from computational limitations as it requires performing inference on a complex (and potentially high dimensional) model. This limitation has so far rendered it unfeasible for modern surveys where tens of billions of galaxies must be processed.

In Chapter 4, we have made progress on the computational feasibility of forward mod-

eling approaches to shear inference. We created a modern implementation of the Bayesian hierarchical framework in [M. D. Schneider et al. \(2015\)](#). This algorithm approximates the shear posterior of an ensemble of galaxy images by marginalizing the effects of pixel noise using MCMC samples of galaxy properties. We leveraged GPUs and gradient-based MCMC sampling to make this Bayesian method efficient, and tested it on isolated parametric galaxy image simulations with realistic levels of pixel and shape noise. We found that our algorithm is approximately an order of magnitude faster than classical MCMC approaches using a CPU. Finally, we demonstrated that this method can accurately estimate shear within the LSST requirement in the context of our simulations, even when the true distribution of galaxy properties is unknown. There are several possible extensions to our methodology that need to be implemented so it can be applied to real data. First, we do not handle many of the aforementioned shear biases besides pixel noise bias. Specifically, we do not currently have a prescription for handling selection and detection shear biases in our methodology. Additionally, we will need to incorporate realistic galaxy morphology into our forward model to handle model shear bias in actual survey images. It is likely that our method is particularly vulnerable to this type of bias unlike the self-calibration approaches. Second, in this project we demonstrated how to jointly infer cosmic shear and the intrinsic distributions of galaxy properties, but only in the case where the latter distributions have a simple and known form. Thus, it will be important to generalize and use a more flexible model that can accurately represent these galaxy distributions. Two possible models that have been previously applied are Dirichlet processes ([M. D. Schneider et al., 2015](#)) and normalizing flows ([I. Kobyzev et al., 2020](#); [G. Papamakarios et al., 2021](#)). Finally, we want to extend this methodology to handle blending related shear biases. This would require improving the efficiency of our method to jointly fit several galaxies simultaneously, which becomes difficult since the number of correlated dimensions becomes really high. Additionally, blending exacerbates detection and model shear biases through unrecognized blends, which are estimated to form between 20 and 30% of sources in LSST. ([W. A. Dawson et al., 2016](#); [M. A. Troxel et al., 2023](#)).

Observational systematic errors in weak lensing surveys represent one of the biggest challenges in realizing their scientific potential. Stage-IV surveys such LSST have set out strict accuracy requirements for cosmic shear measurements that need to be met in order to achieve their expected constraints on dark energy properties. The WL community has made significant progress in methods (e.g., self-calibration) that can calibrate many systematics at the accuracy level required including pixel noise, selection effects, detection, realistic galaxy morphology and several types of image artifacts. However, systematics like blending have not been fully accounted for, and require further study and algorithm development. For example, in [E. Nourbakhsh et al. \(2022\)](#) the authors estimate the impact of unrecognized blending

on the derived structure growth parameter S_8 by computing the shear-shear correlation function on a LSST-like simulation. They find that unrecognized blending produces a bias greater than the 2σ statistical error on S_8 . More generally, one area in particular that remains understudied is the impact of blending on photometric redshifts, whose accurate determination is vital for tomographic weak lensing analyses. Only a small set of algorithms have recently been proposed to mitigate these biases (D. M. Jones & A. F. Heavens, 2019b,a; G. Merz et al., 2025). This thesis develops computational tools and algorithms that leverage modern software and hardware to tackle lensing systematics such as blending. The BLISS algorithm (Chapter 3) has the potential to reduce the bias in measurements of properties of highly blended objects. We demonstrated a large reduction in the residual bias of flux measurements in single-band simulations of galaxy blends. Future work could translate these improvements to color and photometric redshift estimation, potentially reducing the rate of catastrophic outliers. Finally, extensions to the shear inference framework in Chapter 4 could account for a wider range of systematics by including them in our forward model. Particularly exciting is the potential to handle the coupled effect of blending on redshift and shear calibration (N. MacCrann et al., 2022) by building a more complete hierarchical model that also includes redshift (e.g., G. M. Bernstein & R. Armstrong, 2014; G. M. Bernstein et al., 2016). In principle, blending can be naturally accounted for in our algorithm by jointly fitting the galaxies that comprise a blend.

My thesis makes the case that modern Bayesian methods could pave the way to fully addressing image-level systematics in Stage-IV dark energy surveys and maximize the amount of cosmological information gained.

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